

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE CONNECT OPEN CALL

Deliverable D5.3 EELISA Connect meetings report

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the outcomes of the open calls for workshops funded by the EELISA INNOCORE project, under the initiative EELISA CONNECT open call. These workshops, designed to foster interdisciplinary collaboration among EELISA partners, focused on strategic research topics aligned with EELISA's mission and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. The workshops facilitated the exchange of ideas, the generation of new research proposals, and strengthened international collaboration within the EELISA Alliance. In total EELISA Innocore has founded 11 workshops in several research fields and involving all EELISA partners.

The data on EELISA INNOCORE workshops illustrate a broad and inclusive engagement across various themes and institutions. A total of 392 participants attended the 11 workshops over 26 days, highlighting the extensive collaborative efforts within the network.

The workshops created contexts in which researchers could not only deepen their understanding of related research topics but also, and above all, understand the best forms of collaboration within the EELISA context.

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Review and quality check by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the following people from EELISA have been consulted for the production of this deliverable: Isabel Salgueiro and Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa (UPM) and Mustafa Sevimli (ENPC).

Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 41 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years, and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

2 EELISA Connect open call

The EELISA INNOCORE project aims to strengthen research and innovation collaboration among the EELISA partner universities. One of the key initiatives under this project is the implementation of open calls for research workshops. These workshops are designed to bring together researchers from at least three different EELISA partner universities to explore and develop new research ideas in areas of mutual interest. EELISA Connect workshops are an initiative put in place by EELISA InnoCORE (the R&I wing of EELISA) with the aim of providing a setting for the discussion among EELISA researchers and academicians. During the workshops, EELISA researchers can meet in person at one of the EELISA partner institutions to discuss and develop joint research ideas. The EELISA INNOCORE project issued multiple open calls to fund workshops aimed at enhancing research collaboration among EELISA partners. The workshops addressed specialized research topics relevant to the EELISA Strategic Research Areas (SRAs) and aimed to foster new joint research initiatives and proposals. The selection of the workshops has been done via two open calls: EELISA Connect 1st call for workshops and EELISA Connect final call for workshops. In total EELISA InnoCORE has founded 11 workshops in several research fields and involving all EELISA partners.

2.1 Specific aims of the EELISA Connect

EELISA Connect is a bottom-up initiative meant for providing a setting for the discussion among EELISA researchers and academics and generating new proposals for future joint research projects.

The aim of the open call is to facilitate an exchange of ideas between EELISA researchers and academicians, sharing new ideas, experiences, contacts, capacities, infrastructures, and research projects with international peers.

EELISA Connect workshops are an initiative put in place by EELISA InnoCORE with the aim of providing a setting for the discussion among EELISA researchers and academicians. During the workshops, EELISA researchers can meet in person at one of the EELISA partner institutions to discuss and develop joint research ideas. The open calls for research workshops have the following main objectives:

- To stimulate new research collaborations among EELISA partner universities.
- To foster the exchange of ideas and expertise across different disciplines.
- To identify and develop promising new research directions for EELISA.
- To promote the development of innovative and new joint research proposals for Horizon Europe and other funding opportunities.
- To facilitate discussions on specialized research topics.
- To enhance the research and innovation dimension of the EELISA Alliance.

2.2 Inside the EELISA Connect CALL

The main features of the open calls are described below. Annex 1 1 to this report contains the call and application texts in full and Annex 2 contains the application form. Both documents were discussed and validated by partners and the Advisory Council for Research and Innovation (ACRI) members.

2.2.1 The WHO -ELEGIBILITY-

EELISA researchers and academicians (research staff, researchers and academicians from EELISA partners working full time for the partner institution either with a permanent or a fixed-term contract; the work contract must cover the duration of EELISA InnoCORE until 31 May 2024). **In the application form the main information on the WHO is listed in the table.**

Title of the workshop	
Local organiser Researcher from the institution where the onsite event will take place, i.e. the hosting institution	Title/First name/Last name:
	EELISA Institution (hosting institution):
	Research structure:
	Category:
	Telephone:
	Email:
Short biography of the organizer (max. 200 words)	<i>Please include a description of the position at the University and the experience in organizing this type of events</i>

Table 2: Details of the workshop and organizers

2.2.2 The WHAT

The call aims at funding workshops able to promote an active face to face exchange of research ideas to develop research proposals (i.e. under European or international calls). Workshops aim at providing a forum to present work and receive feedback from EELISA peers in an interactive atmosphere. Moreover, researchers and academicians will be able to share their experiences, contact networks, capacities, and facilities.

In the application form the main information on what are mainly listed in the table.

Moreover, considering the results of the first call, the teams from the ACRI member add a new criteria in the second call, specifying that winning proposals are not allowed to submit a new application. Unfunded applications from the first call can and are encouraged to resubmit a new application.

Table 3: Details of the workshop proposal

Section 2 – WORKSHOP PROPOSAL

4. Description of the workshop (compulsory)

4.1. Title of the workshop
4.2 Motivation
4.3. Description of the technical issues and scientific areas covered, and link with EELISA Strategic Research Areas <i>The aim of the workshop is to provide a structured setting for the discussion among relevant EELISA researchers and academicians, of specialized technical topics that align with EELISA structures, tools and strategic research areas. Please describe how the topic of the workshop is linked with the EELISA Strategic Research Areas and its relevance for the challenges faced within EELISA Communities. Where possible describe also its connection with EELISA research clusters.</i> <i>At the same time, workshops should provide a forum for EELISA researchers and academicians to present their work and receive feedback from EELISA peers in an interactive atmosphere. The workshop must be an EELISA event and it must serve to strengthen activities of the Alliance. Please explain the capacities you can bring into the Alliance, how the workshop will serve to build the tools for new collaborations and strengthen the R&I dimension of the Alliance.</i> <i>Please explain the potential of the workshop to trigger new research proposals under Horizon Europe and other European or international calls.</i>
4.4. Description of the workshop's expected impact <i>The ultimate aim of the workshop is to generate future joint research projects and joint research collaborations. Please describe expected potential future collaborations (joint EU projects, joint publications). If you are planning to apply for a European or international call for proposals, please name it. Please explain how the workshop will serve to build the tools and strengthen the R&I dimension of the Alliance.</i>

2.2.3 The WHERE and the FORMAT

The workshop organization must involve at least three EELISA partners located in different countries. **One of them acts as a local organizer and will be in charge of the organization of the logistics of the onsite event. Only onsite workshops or hybrid workshops** (both onsite and online) will be funded. Online workshops will not be taken into consideration.

6. Format of the workshop (compulsory)

Duration of the workshop (It is recommended to have between one and two days and a half full day workshop)	
Format of the workshop (onsite or hybrid)	
Tentative date (identify the month)	
Expected number of participants	
Location (identify the facilities of the EELISA partner for the meeting)	

Table 4: Details of the workshop format

2.2.4 The WHY

The aim of this **call for proposals for EELISA InnoCORE research workshops – EELISA Connect** is to provide a **setting for the discussion among EELISA researchers and academicians of specialized research topics that align with the EELISA InnoCORE Strategic Research Areas (SRAs).**

The workshops are welcome to contribute involving researchers in **EELISA Communities** and to establish connections among them.

What do we mean by Strategic Research Area?

SRAs are broad categories of research areas that are prioritized for the **potential development of joint strategic research efforts.** Strategic research areas are strongly linked with the research areas of EELISA (“SMART, GREEN & RESILIENT CITIES” and “SUSTAINABLE & SMART INDUSTRIES”), however, they are also strongly associated with the European Union R&I framework and sustainable development goals.

Figure 4 - EELISA Communities

What are EELISA Communities?

The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Community members share a common interest and offer or participate in learning, research, innovation and third mission activities in the European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance. By doing so, EELISA Communities contribute to a common mission that is based on solving diverse challenges. EELISA Communities are open places that embrace the inclusion of different stakeholders – academics, students, staff members and external university ecosystem players from EELISA universities.

Figure 5 - EELISA Communities

2.2.5 The HOW – ELIGIBLE COSTS-

EELISA INNOCORE will provide up to €17,000 to cover the costs of each workshop. The eligible expenses include:

- **Travel, Accommodation, and Subsistence:**
 - For researchers, academic staff, and PhD students from EELISA universities.
 - All participants should have a work contract with the partner institution covering the entire duration of EELISA INNOCORE.
- **Catering:**
 - Costs for coffee breaks and lunch breaks offered during the workshop.
- **Transportation:**
 - Expenses for buses if needed.
- **Dissemination:**
 - Costs for materials such as leaflets and printing.
- **Personnel Costs:**
 - For support in organizing the event (up to 10% of the total cost).
 - This cannot be used to cover personnel costs or allowances for research and academic staff from the partner institutions.
- **Other Costs:**
 - Any other expenses directly linked to the organization of the workshop.

These funding guidelines ensure comprehensive support for the logistical and organizational needs of the workshops.

The policy sets the limit on expenditures for personnel outside the alliance to a maximum of 10 percent of the planned budget.

An upfront payment has been made to the hosting institution equal to 50% of the total planned costs of the workshop. The remainder up to the actual total costs of the workshop organization has been settled after the workshop takes place, against the submission of invoices and the final by the hosting institution.

2.2.6 Other Workshop Requirements

The guidelines for conducting workshops under the EELISA INNOCORE initiative are clear and structured to ensure accessibility, accountability, and visibility. By mandating that workshops be free of charge, the program promotes inclusivity and ensures that financial barriers do not hinder participation. The requirement for workshops to take place within four months of acceptance ensures timely execution and relevance. Acknowledging EU funding and disseminating information through the EELISA website helps maintain transparency and broadens the reach of the initiative. Finally, the obligation for organizers to submit a detailed final report within a month after the workshop fosters a culture of accountability and allows for the assessment of the workshop's impact on participants and the broader EELISA INNOCORE objectives. Overall, these stipulations are designed to maximize the effectiveness and impact of the workshops while maintaining high standards of operation and reporting.

2.2.7 The CRITERIA for evaluation

The evaluation criteria for the EELISA INNOCORE workshops emphasize the importance of fostering connections and collaborations among EELISA researchers. Proposals were evaluated by the EELISA INNOCORE Advisory Council for Research and Innovation based on the following criteria:

1. Capacity of the workshop to boost **connections** among EELISA researchers (up to 30 points).
2. Potential of the workshop to trigger **new research collaborations**, including new research proposals under Horizon Europe and other European or international calls (up to 15 points).
3. Potential of the workshop to trigger **new connections between facilities** of EELISA partners (up to 5 points).
4. Relevance of the topic for EELISA partners and links with EELISA InnoCORE **SRAs** (up to 10 points).
5. Relevance of the topic for the challenges faced within EELISA **Communities** (up to 10 points).
6. **Long-term impact** of the collaboration fostered by the workshop; likeliness that the activity can be sustained or prolonged, e.g. in an ongoing programme (up to 10 points).
7. **Gender balance** (up to 10 points).

2.2.8 Call Details

In terms of scheduling, EELISA INNOCORE, in agreement with ACRI members, decided to conduct two open calls for research workshops instead of the initially planned three. This decision was made to enhance efficiency and simplify communication and budget management. The first call allocated funding for a minimum of three workshops with a total budget of €51,000, while the second call planned for a larger scope, funding at least seven

workshops with a total budget of €119,000. These structured calls ensure effective resource utilization and provide clear timelines for applicants, contributing to the overall success and impact of the research workshops. As described below, savings from the first calls were added in the budget of the second call. Finally, the total budget of the second call was 134,000 euro.

The details of each call are provided below.

First Open Call

- **Announcement:** March 7, 2023
- **Info session:** 27 March 2023
- **Deadline for Applications:** April 20, 2023
- **Notification of Acceptance:** May 10, 2023
- **Minimum Number of Workshops Funded:** 3
- **Maximum Budget per Workshop:** €17,000
- **Estimated Funding Available:** €51,000
- **Final report and submission of invoices:** within one month after the workshop

Second Open Call (as managed at september 2023)

- **Announcement:** 29 September 2023
- **Info session:** 24 October 2023
- **Deadline for Applications:** 27 November 2023
- **Notification of Acceptance:** 15 December 2023
- **Minimum Number of Workshops Funded:** 7
- **Maximum Budget per Workshop:** €17,000
- **Estimated Funding Available:** €119,000
- **Final report and submission of invoices:** within one month after the workshop

By consolidating the calls, EELISA INNOCORE aims to streamline processes, ensure clearer communication, and manage the budget more effectively, ultimately fostering a more organized and impactful research workshop program.

3. Calls Communication Process

To give maximum dissemination to the open calls, several communication initiatives were organized on different channels. These initiatives were made possible thanks to the full support of UPM and the EELISA alliance communication team, as leader of the dissemination and communication tasks.

The communication strategy for EELISA INNOCORE's EELISA CONNECT workshop initiative is well-structured and comprehensive, utilizing multiple platforms to reach a wide audience. The dedicated webpages provide essential information about the calls, including important dates and application formats. Interviews and Q&A sessions help clarify the core aspects of the ECOC. Online info sessions facilitated by UPM offer direct support to potential applicants. The publication of selected workshops, along with detailed partner information, ensures transparency. Additionally, Instagram campaigns enhance visibility and engagement through

social media. This multi-channel approach effectively promotes the initiative and fosters community participation.

The table below describes the initiatives and details.

Initiatives	Details	Eventual link
A dedicated image for the EELISA CONNECT workshop		https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-connect-workshops/
Dedicated webpage on EELISA website	A general page with main information of the call	https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-connect-workshops/
An interview to underline the core of the EOCO	Questions and answer about the EOCO	https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-connect-first-innocore-joint-call/
Two dedicated webpages for each of the two calls	For each of the two calls a specific webpage with important date, text of the call and application format	https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-connect-final-call-for-workshops/
Info session	For each of the two calls an online info session was organized with UPM to better explain the EELISA CONNECT workshop and answer to eventual questions and doubts	https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-connect-final-call-for-workshops/
Publication of the selected workshop on the web	For each of the selected workshop, details on partners, coordinator, title, and date were published on the web.	https://eelisa.eu/results-of-the-first-eelisa-connect-call-for-workshops/ https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-connect-workshops/
EELISA Instagram (reel, picture...)	For each of the call and event (info section, results...) data info e results were also published on the EELISA Instagram	Following some image of the Instagram campaign.

Table 5: Communication initiatives

Figure 1 – Examples of communication campaigning on Instagram

The participation data for the EELISA INNOCORE info sessions shows a substantial increase in engagement, highlighting growing interest and awareness within the community. The first online info session saw 17 participants, while the second session experienced a significant rise to 51 participants. This notable increase in attendance underscores the effectiveness of outreach efforts and the escalating enthusiasm among researchers and academicians for the EELISA INNOCORE initiatives. This upward trend in participation bodes well for the future success and collaborative potential of the project.

4. Evaluation and Selection Process

The evaluation and selection process for the EELISA INNOCORE workshops was methodically organized into two distinct steps to ensure thoroughness and fairness. Initially, a preliminary assessment of eligibility and an initial evaluation were conducted by an operational jury, consisting of one representative from each partner institution. Following this, the Advisory Council for Research and Innovation (ACRI) carried out a formal evaluation based on predefined criteria. This two-step process allowed for a comprehensive review and selection of proposals that aligned with the available budget and strategic objectives of the call.

The two figures below describe the evaluation process in time and manner for each of the two calls.

Figure 2/3- Agenda for the selection and evaluation process

5. Results of the calls

The two calls were quite successful, and there was a significant increase in terms of interest and applications sent between the first and second calls. the table below describes the main results in numerical terms.

DATA	First call	Second call	Total
Number of Proposals Received	6	10	16
Partners involved as coordinators (received proposal)	3 (4 UPM, 1 SSSA, 1 BME)	3 (6 UPM, 2 ITU, 2 BME)	4 (10 UPM, 3 BME, 2 ITU, 1 SSSA)
Partners involved as participants (received proposal)	All partners	All partners	All partners
Number of Funded Proposals	3	8	11
Success Rate	50%	80%	69%
Partners involved as coordinators (funded proposals)	3 (1 UPM, 1 SSSA, 1 BME)	3 (5 UPM, 2 ITU, 1 BME)	4 (7 UPM, 1 SSSA, 2 BME, 2 ITU)
Partners involved as participants (funded proposals)	All partners	All partners	All partners

Table 6: Results of the two calls

5.2Connections with SRAs and Communities (received proposals)

The data on proposals received and funded for the EELISA INNOCORE open call indicates a high level of engagement and success across the participating partners. For the first call, we received 6 proposals and financed 3 out of 6, with a success rate of 50%. For the second call, we received 10 proposals and financed 8 out of 10, with a success rate of 80%. All partners participated, reflecting widespread collaboration. The hit rates and diverse involvement highlight the initiative's effective support for innovative research projects. Considering the participation of each partner, there is a clear predominance in favor of some partners, particularly in favor of UPM, and on the other hand the non-participation as organizers of other partners (FAU, ENPC, PLS). However, all alliance partner universities participated in the various workshops with research and teaching staff staff.

In terms of EELISA INNOCORE SRAs, the received proposals covered many areas and have links with several EELISA communities. In particular, the SRAs more quoted are listed in the next table.

SRAs (were quoted)	Number of SRAs citation
Culture, creativity and inclusive society	8
Social Sciences and Humanities	6
Artificial intelligence	4
Climate energy and mobility	3
Digitalisation	3
Health	2
Smart industry and space technologies	2
Energy and climate change	1
Connetivity	1

Table 7: Connections with SRAs

The data on the Strategic Research Areas (SRAs) cited in the proposals highlight a strong focus on interdisciplinary collaboration within the EELISA INNOCORE initiative. The most frequently cited SRAs include "Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society" (8 citations) and "Social Sciences and Humanities" (6 citations), reflecting a significant interest in addressing societal and cultural challenges. Additionally, the areas of "Artificial Intelligence" (4 citations) and "Climate, Energy and Mobility" (3 citations) indicate a commitment to advancing technological innovation and sustainability. The diversity of SRAs cited showcases the comprehensive approach of EELISA INNOCORE in fostering research across a wide array of critical fields.

The received proposals for the EELISA INNOCORE open call demonstrated a strong alignment with various EELISA communities, indicating the interdisciplinary and collaborative nature of the initiatives.

The proposals spanned diverse areas such as TechDiplomacy, Ethics, Social Commitment, and Entrepreneurship, highlighting the commitment to addressing ethical and social dimensions of engineering education. Communities involved include those focused on water management, innovation in education, and sustainable science, reflecting a broad engagement with key societal and environmental challenges. This variety underscores the

comprehensive and inclusive approach of EELISA INNOCORE in fostering collaborative research. In details, the received proposals were linked to these following communities as quoted in the proposals: EELISA TechDiplomacy community (1) <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/tech-diplomacy-international-cooperation/>; EELISA ESCE (Ethics, Social Commitment and Entrepreneurship) community (3) <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/ethics-social-commitment-and-entrepreneurship/> (1); Water in an area in change community (2); EELISA DISCOVERY (1) <https://eelisa.eu/project/eelisa-discovery-designing-a-sustainable-and-decarbonized-university/>; Innovation and Design in European Engineering Education (IDEEE) (1); SSERIES - Science for Sustainably Envisioning Reality and Information for an Engaged Society (1) <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/sseries-science-for-a-sustainable-envision-of-reality-and-information-for-an-engaged-society/>; CIRCULAR EELISA (2) <https://community.eelisa.eu/communities/circular-eelisa-community/> .

Considering SRAs and EELISA communities involved, the received proposals for the EELISA INNOCORE open call highlight a robust focus on interdisciplinary collaboration and alignment with various EELISA communities and Strategic Research Areas. These results underscore the comprehensive and inclusive approach of EELISA INNOCORE in fostering collaborative research across a broad spectrum of critical fields.

5.2 Selected proposals: the EELISA CONNECT WORKSHOPS

The list of workshops financed under the EELISA CONNECT initiative demonstrates a diverse and comprehensive approach to addressing various contemporary challenges through collaborative research and innovation. Each workshop, coordinated by experts from different institutions like UPM, BME, ITU, and SSSA, covers critical topics such as sustainable urban transition, AI ethics, circular economy, and language technologies in the era of generative AI. The workshops, set to take place between June and October 2023 and March and April 2024, underscore EELISA's commitment to fostering interdisciplinary connections and advancing research aligned with societal needs and technological advancements. This diverse lineup reflects EELISA's strategic focus on enhancing research collaborations and addressing global challenges through joint efforts and innovative solutions.

The table below briefly describes the funded workshops, specifying the coordinator, host institution, title, and dates of the workshops.

Title of the workshop	Coordinator	Hosting institution	Date
City of Proximity: the power of local-based initiatives to boost urban transition	Francesca Olivieri francesca.olivieri@upm.es	UPM	18 & 19 March 2024
The EELISA Workshop on Sustainable Business Models and Value Creation for Stakeholders	Jaime J. González Masip jaime.gonzalez.masip@upm.es	UPM	4 & 5 March 2024
Data Spaces for Researchers: Fostering Collaborative Research and Innovation	Esteban González Guardia esteban.gonzalez@upm.es	UPM	4 & 5 March 2024
Teaching and Learning Language Technologies (text and speech) in light of Generative AI	Elena Montiel-Ponsoda emontiel@fi.upm.es	UPM	7 & 8 March 2024
Interactions in nonlinear analysis: variational methods, reaction-diffusion equations, dynamical systems and applications	Andrea Tellini andrea.tellini@upm.es	UPM	10th & 12th of April, 2024
Circular Models: research, innovation, and partnerships towards circularity	Prof. Justo García-Navarro justo.gnavarro@upm.es	UPM	3 & 5 July 2023
EELISA Workshop on AI Ethics and Law	Mihály HÉDER heder.mihaly@gtk.bme.hu	BME	18 & 19 March 2024
Technology Diplomacy in Engineering Education	Balázs Vince Nagy, PhD nagy.balazs.vince@bme.hu	BME	26-27 October 2023
New horizons: Partnerships for circularity-driven sustainability research and innovation	Imge Akcakaya Waite imgeawaite@itu.edu.tr	ITU	April 17-19, 2024
Engineering a Sustainable Future: Bridging Minds, Building Skills	Hamza Salih Erden erdenh@itu.edu.tr	ITU	18 & 19 March 2024
Ways of Water – Ethical, Socio-Economic, Environmental, and Engineering Perspectives on Riverine and Oceanic Commons	Prof. Alberto Pirni alberto.pirni@santannapisa.it	SSSA	11 & 12 June 2023

Table 7: Details of the selected workshop

5.3 The EELISA CONNECT WORKSHOPS: participants.

The data on EELISA INNOCORE workshops illustrate a broad and inclusive engagement across various themes and institutions. A total of 392 participants attended 11 workshops over 26 days, highlighting the extensive collaborative efforts within the network. Notably, the gender distribution was fairly balanced with 211 males and 185 females, reflecting a commitment to gender inclusivity. Workshops covered diverse topics from AI ethics to sustainable business models, with four hybrid sessions facilitating wider accessibility. External participation was significant, with 44 external attendees contributing to the exchange of ideas and fostering new collaborations. This comprehensive engagement underscores EELISA INNOCORE's dedication to interdisciplinary research and innovation.

Table shows main data on participants.

DATA	N.
Total participants	392
Total duration	26 days
Hybrid workshops	4
Gender balance	211 male, 181 female
Total external participants	44 (the data was available only for 8/11 workshops)

Table 8: General DATA

Next table shows the number of participants for each partner of EELISA alliance.

Partner	N.
UPM	72
ITU	55
SSSA	22
BME	19
UPB	19
FAU	7
PSL	6
SNS	5
ENPC	2

Table 9: Data on participants²

These figures offer insight into the engagement levels of different partners in the workshops, reflecting varying degrees of involvement and interest across the participating organizations. These numbers assess the effectiveness of collaboration efforts and identify areas for potential improvement or focus in future workshops.

² The total number of participants, disaggregated by partners, does not correspond to the total (396) because we do not have disaggregated data for all workshops.

Table shows main data for each workshops.

Workshop and webpage	Total participants	Participant by partner	Duration	Blended workshop	Gender balance	External participants
AI ETHICS AND LAW (18-19 MARCH 2024)	66	Not specified	2 days	no	45 male, 21 female	not specified
DATA SPACE FOR RESEARCHERS: (4-5 March 2024)	12	2ITU 3UPB 1 UPM	2 days	no	7 male, 5 female	2
WAYS OF WATER (12-13 JUNE 2023)	19	11 SSSA 4 BME 1 SNS 3 PSL	2 days	no	13 male, 6 female	not specified
INTERACTIONS IN NONLINEAR ANALYSIS (10-12 APRIL 2024)	40 (31 partners + 9 external participants)	19UPM 4 SNS 4 UPB 2 PSL 1 SSSA	3 days	yes	29 male, 11 female	9
TECHNOLOGY DIPLOMACY (26-27 OCTOBER 2023)	56	Not specified	2 days	no	31 male, 25 female	yes but the number was not specified
CIRCULAR MODELS (3-7 JULY 2023)	39	17 UPM 4 ITU 1 SSSA 3 UPB	3 days	no	15 male, 24 female	14 ³
ENGINEERING A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE (18-19 MARCH 2024)	45	5 UPB 2 UPM 18 ITU 15 BME	2 days	yes	20 male, 25 female	6
CITY OF PROXIMITY (18-19 MARCH 2024)	28	18 UPM 2 PSL 3 ITU 3 FAU	2 days	yes	14 male, 14 female	1
TEACHING AND LEARNING LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGIES (7-8 MARCH 2024)	30	5 ITU 3 SSSA 1 UPB 14 UPM	2 days	no	12 male, 18 female	7
NEW HORIZONS	38	3 UPM 3 UPB 2 SSSA 2 ENPC 2 PSL 2 ZHAW 19 ITU	3 days	no	14 male, 24 female	4
SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODELS (3-5 MARCH 2024)	19	4 FAU 4 ITU 4 SSSA 6 UPM	3 days	no	11 male, 8 female	1

Table 10: Details of the workshop

³ The workshop took place in Madrid, and UPM did not cover travel expenses for external participants from Madrid.

6. Insights from The EELISA CONNECT WORKSHOPS

The workshops created contexts in which researchers could not only deepen their understanding of related research topics but also, and above all, understand the best forms of collaboration within the EELISA context.

In general terms, three main aspects can be highlighted on which the workshops had a significant impact:

- **In-depth Research Topics Exploration:** The workshops provided researchers with a valuable opportunity to delve into research topics related to EELISA initiatives. Through presentations, interactive sessions, and discussions, participants were able to access new perspectives, discoveries, and methodologies relevant to their specific research areas.
- **Enhanced Collaboration:** A significant impact of the workshops was the improvement of collaboration within the EELISA community. Through collaborative activities, discussions, and sharing of best practices, researchers were able to develop new professional relationships, identify collaboration opportunities, and create synergies that promote the development of shared projects.
- **Stimulus to Creativity and Innovation:** The workshops also stimulated creativity and innovation among researchers, providing them with a safe and stimulating space to explore new ideas, approaches, and solutions. Through brainstorming sessions, wordcafé session, and informal exchanges, participants were able to test their ideas, receive feedback, and contribute to the generation of new knowledge and innovations in the field.

Following some comments on the impacts and dimensions of innovation and collaboration of the workshops with some examples of quotations from final reports of the EELISA CONNECT workshops. All the final reports are reported on the annex III.

These quotes and dimensions highlight the multifaceted benefits and the far-reaching impact of the EELISA CONNECT workshops on innovation and collaboration. By fostering an environment of diverse, multidisciplinary interaction, and continuous learning, the workshops have evidently driven significant progress in both individual and collective capacities.

6.1 Focus on Young Research

The workshops within the EELISA INNOCORE initiative highlighted the necessity for regular interactions to foster the development of future research projects. To enhance collaboration, particularly among young researchers, organizing seasonal schools that combine introductory mini-courses with participant presentations is recommended. Additionally, discussions emphasized the importance of career continuity for young researchers, with a focus on postdoctoral contracts and early career positions available across EELISA alliance universities. The EELISA internships and job postings webpage serves as a valuable resource for exploring these opportunities. Regular funding stability is crucial for sustaining these initiatives.

"Since this was a first contact between such different groups, in order to fully conceive and develop research projects in the future, workshops of this type would need to be repeated with a certain regularity, which requires a certain stability of funding. Due to the presence of many young researchers, another possibility to strengthen the links between the different research groups in the future is the organization of seasonal schools, combining mini-courses of initiation to new research topics with presentation of the results by the participants. To this end, the different possibilities offered by EELISA will be analyzed. Another important aspect that has arisen in relation to young researchers has been the continuation of their careers. Different possibilities for postdoctoral contracts and early career positions in the different countries of the EELISA alliance universities participating in the workshop have been compared. For this purpose, the web page <https://eelisa.eu/internshipsjob-postings-2/> is a very useful tool." (Interactions in nonlinear analysis: variational methods, reaction-diffusion equations, dynamical systems and applications)

6.2 Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing

In general, the EELISA CONNECT workshop initiative successfully achieved their anticipated outcomes, identifying research opportunities within their academic contest and generating collaborative research project ideas and proposals aligned with EELISA's Strategic Research Areas and fostering inter-university and also university-industry collaborations. This approach facilitated dynamic exchanges among stakeholders, contributing to the growth of the EELISA alliance and supporting high-quality research initiatives.

*As part of the TechDiplomacy community activities the workshop brought up a continuing discussion on related topics (ethics, education, standardization, interdisciplinarity etc.) that are being further addressed by the community members internally and towards external partners in future events.
(Technology Diplomacy in Engineering Education)*

“In line with the workshop proposal submitted to EELISA innoCORE’s second EELISA Connect call in November 2023, the anticipated outcomes of New Horizons were met as follows:

- **Identification of research opportunities:** *The workshop provided a dynamic environment for participants to delve into and discuss experiences, challenges, and research opportunities within the realm of the circular economy, emphasizing social, citizenship, and industrial dimensions from an inclusive perspective. This collaborative exploration aimed to uncover promising research areas, defining specific topics, and leveraging knowledge and infrastructure to collectively address shared challenges.*
- **Generation of joint research project ideas and proposals:** *Facilitating an exchange of knowledge, experiences, and innovative approaches, the workshop became a fertile ground for generating research project ideas aligned with the three EELISA Strategic Research Areas. Participants shared insights that led to the creation of original and viable ideas for collaborative research endeavors. Drawing on the support and feedback from fellow academics, researchers, sector representatives and students, participants were able to refine their project ideas and craft robust proposals that align with the requisites of European funding calls or other potential funding sources.*
- **Further enhancement of ongoing project ideas and/or proposals** *from the former EELISA Connect workshop, Circular Models: In addition to the primary aim of generating new joint research ventures, as indicated in the second aim of the workshop mentioned above, the workshop intended to act as a follow-up opportunity for the ideas generated during the first EELISA Connect workshop of the Circular EELISA Community held in Madrid in July 2023. This was to ensure that those ideas are further elaborated and matched with possible new consortiums and administrative decisions.*
- **Promotion of inter-university and university-industry collaborations:** *An integral objective was to promote the EELISA Alliance among a diverse spectrum of stakeholders, including students, researchers, academics, companies, and partners. Through vibrant idea exchange between participating institutions, the workshop fostered the establishment of research networks, laying the foundation for joint research projects, and expansion of the Circular EELISA Community.*
- **Capacity building for research and innovation:** *Beyond project ideation, the workshop housed capacity-building and training activities encompassing research methodologies, innovation techniques, and other pertinent aspects of the circular economy. These activities aimed to enhance the research and innovation capacities of participants, ultimately elevating the quality of the proposals generated.*

(New horizons: Partnerships for circularity-driven sustainability research and innovation)

6.3 Identifying Expertise and Interests

The EELISA CONNECT workshop achieved significant milestones by fostering peer-to-peer contacts among participants who were largely unfamiliar with each other's work prior to the event. It established stable communication channels and platforms to facilitate ongoing collaboration, including a timetable for monitoring progress and organizing follow-up meetings. Participants committed to further developing their **collaborative projects**, with some dates already set for new **meetings**. Additionally, the EELISA partner universities expressed interest in **future EELISA Connect calls** to secure funding for new workshops, ensuring continuity and sustained collaboration.

“The objectives achieved in the event can be grouped into three main sets listed below. Firstly, participants had the opportunity to get to know each other's lines of work and research. It should be noted that, with a few exceptions, the participants did not know each other before the workshop. In this sense, peer-to-peer contacts were made, with plans for collaboration following the affinity criterion in lines of work.

Secondly, stable communication channels and platforms were established for coordination among the participants to facilitate collaboration on initiatives of group interest. Table 3 compiles a list of lines of collaboration grouped by type of action that the participants identified as being of common interest. For its realisation, a timetable was defined to monitor the progress of the tasks. The group committed to organizing and following up on the work through meetings to continue developing the projects with the workshop leaders interested in each case. Some dates were set for the first online meetings, and some verbal commitments were made for immediate meetings. In addition, the EELISA partner universities participating in the workshop will be attentive to new EELISA Connect calls of the EELISA innoCORE project to consider applying for grants to organise new workshops that give continuity to the Sustainable Business Research Week workshop.”

Table 3. Collaboration lines

GROUP	Initiative or Program	Collective actuation
Existing conferences or initiatives	EURAM Conference (Florence, 2025)	Propose a specific track or session.
	New Business Models Conference 2025	Propose a specific track or session.
	R&D Management Conference (Rome, 2025)	Propose a specific track or session.
	EGOS conference (Athens, 2025)	Propose a specific track or session.
	Academy of Management (2025, Copenhagen)	Participate in a specific track or session.
	Society for Business Ethics Conference (Chicago, 2024)	Participate in a specific track or session (for the next year).
	European Marketing Academy (EMAC) Annual Conference (Madrid, 2025)	Propose special sessions or a Symposium (+Journal Special Issue).
Funding	European Funding (HORIZON/Erasmus +)	Information gathering and sharing.
	Workshop not European funding (Research + Methodologies)	Information gathering and sharing.
Research and publish	Book on the topic covered in the workshop	Publication of a book by compilation of chapters with the participation of all workshop attendees.

(Sustainable Business Models and Value Creation for Stakeholders)

The EELISA CONNECT workshop aimed to establish an alliance among EELISA researchers focused on specific tasks and issues, with the goal of collaboratively applying for European calls for proposals. It significantly impacted the EELISA community by integrating the workshop into a broader process of participating in international calls. In some cases, the selected call for proposals was the **Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Staff Exchanges**, which promote international and intersectoral collaboration through staff exchanges. This program funds short-term exchanges to foster sustainable projects between academic and non-academic sectors across Europe and beyond.

*“The proposed workshop aimed to create and formalize an alliance between the different EELISA researchers, specialized in the sustainable transition of cities, to join efforts and knowledge to carry out proposals to European calls for proposals.
This workshop has been able to guarantee an important impact for the EELISA community, as the session has been part of a broader process of participation in international calls for proposals. This broader process has allowed to deepen the sessions in different phases, deepening in each of them the most important issues required to participate in international calls for proposals.
The call for proposals selected for the workshop has finally been Staff Exchange: the European Staff Exchange Project, also known as Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Staff Exchanges, is a program that promotes international, intersectoral and interdisciplinary innovative collaboration in research and innovation through the exchange of staff and the sharing of knowledge and ideas.
The main objective of the Staff Exchanges is to fund short-term international and intersectoral exchanges of staff members involved in research and innovation activities of participating organizations. The ultimate goal of this proposal is to develop sustainable collaborative projects between different organizations from the academic and non-academic sectors (in particular SMEs), based in Europe and beyond.
Staff exchanges are open to international consortia of universities, research institutions, companies, SMEs and other non-academic organizations. They must include at least three organizations from three different countries, two of which must be located in an EU Member State or in a Horizon Europe associated country.”
(City of Proximitv)*

6.4 Capacity Building

EELISA CONNECT workshops served as a forum for researchers to explore potential synergies between institutions, enhancing mutual understanding and collaborative opportunities. **Additionally, they promoted capacity building through training activities, enhancing participants' research and innovation capabilities.** Overall, the workshops were deemed a great success, highlighting the convenience of knowing participants' capabilities and common interests. Looking forward, new possibilities emerged for **professor exchanges** within the EELISA community and the organization of **seasonal schools**. Funding has been secured for future EELISA activities following its renewal, promising sustained collaboration and growth.

*“The workshop provided a valuable opportunity to understand the participants capabilities and shared interests. It served as a forum for researchers to foster a deeper understanding of the potential synergies between institutions.[...] In general, the workshop was considered a great success, since it was very convenient to know the capabilities of the participants and the common interests. Looking ahead, some possibilities were opened about professor exchanges within EELISA community and the feasibility of organising a summer school, with funding secured for future EELISA activities following its renewal.”
(Teaching and Learning Language Technologies (text and speech) in light of Generative AI)*

The workshop successfully brought together a diverse group of participants, fostering various lines of activity and interests. There was notable engagement also in some cases from companies and organizations in research, development, and education, leading a commitment **to public-private collaboration** for international projects, for example focused on circularity and sustainability. Notable some new proposals included **joint degree programs**.

*“Among the participants, a great variety of lines of activity stands out [...]Regarding companies and other organizations, there is a great interest in research, development, professional training, educational institutions, and international support. In accordance with this variety, it was necessary to approach the proposals from different perspectives, which generated the development of six different proposals and a commitment between the public and private sectors for the participation in projects at an international level towards circularity and sustainability. One of the main objectives achieved was to promote the generation of research projects in a collaborative way. Likewise, the strengthening of alliances between universities, companies and other institutions, the establishment of cooperation channels and agreements for future cooperation.
Proposals for the development of joint degrees in the field of the EELISA Alliance of Universities stand out, such as the aforementioned Master's and Doctorate programs. Also, or the possible alliance led by the University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest, with Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and SURUS, in the field of the circularity of wind farms.[...] The results of the workshop make the balance very satisfactory, with six large projects in the development process for presentation in future European calls, with the aim of implementing new circular models.”
(Circular Models)*

The EELISA workshops by effectively bridging the gap between theoretical frameworks in academia and practical industry expectations, they showcased best practices that can serve as a model for others. The interactive sessions were particularly impactful, highlighting the crucial need to integrate some issues (as sustainability) into curricula and emphasizing the development of skills that align with industry demands. Furthermore, the discussions on collaboration opportunities underscored the importance of **inclusive education and capacity building in higher education**. Programs like **Jean Monnet Activities and Erasmus+** were rightly highlighted for their role in promoting international cooperation, policy experimentation, and excellence in creating a dynamic educational ecosystem.

*The workshop exemplified the innovative spirit and commitment of EELISA towards sustainable education. It successfully showcased good practices to bridge the gap between academia's theoretical frameworks and the industry's practical expectations. Interactive sessions highlighted the importance of integrating sustainability into curricula, emphasizing skills development to address industry needs effectively.
Good practices from the Circular Community provided a template for integrating companies and communities in educational programs. The STEAM approach suggested by Dr. Elena Fleaca signified the shift towards incorporating more management and entrepreneurship within technical curricula, an essential step for fostering project experience and skills of the future.
Discussion on collaboration opportunities shed light on the value of inclusive education and capacity building in higher education. Programs like Jean Monnet Activities and Erasmus+ highlighted the need for international cooperation, policy experimentation, and the pursuit of excellence in creating an adaptive and responsive educational ecosystem. Furthermore, the session pinpointed research interests, spotlighting the importance of linking sustainability with corporate life.
(Engineering a Sustainable Future: Bridging Minds, Building Skills)*

The commitment and enthusiasm expressed by the workshop attendees towards sustaining the collaborative ethos are commendable. Their collective dedication to leveraging expertise and resources for the benefit of compelling projects and initiatives reflects a strong sense of

community and shared purpose within the EELISA network. Additionally, the decision to promote the adoption of the **OS ambassador network within EELISA** and strengthen collaborations with other alliances and the **EELISA OS community** demonstrates a commitment to expanding networks and fostering broader engagement also with others work package of Innocore.

The proposed utilization of the **EELISA Training Platform** to facilitate knowledge dissemination and skill development is strategic, particularly in enhancing accessibility to educational resources for researchers and students alike. Collaborating with **European projects** to offer high-quality courses further enhances the value proposition of the EELISA Training Platform.

Following the conclusion of the workshop, the attendees expressed their willingness to sustain the collaborative ethos established during the event. With a collective commitment to harnessing each other's expertise and resources, they envisaged an array of compelling projects and initiatives poised to benefit from their combined efforts. We agree to explore the use of data spaces, together with INESData, in the different scenarios developing some prototypes in master thesis or final undergraduate works. Also, we agree to encourage the adoption of the OS ambassador network in EELISA and to strength the collaboration with other alliances and with the EELISA OS community. The EELISA Training Platform can play a crucial role in this task. We plan to foster the use of this platform by creating innovative content for researchers and students. We plan to collaborate with the European projects RITRAINPLUS and FAIR IMPACT to offer courses of high quality. Also, we will study the participation of the institutions involved in the workshop in future calls related to education.

(Data Spaces for Researchers: Fostering Collaborative Research and Innovation)

7. SWOT analysis of EELISA CONNECT WORKSHOPS

The "EELISA Connect Open Call for Workshop" presents numerous strengths and opportunities that can be leveraged to promote collaboration and innovation among participating universities. However, it is crucial to address the weaknesses and mitigate the threats through strategic planning, effective resource management, and continuous monitoring of impact and outcomes.

We conduct a SWOT analysis of the EELISA CONNECT workshops, followed by a SWOT analysis of a specific workshop.

Strengths

1. Interdisciplinary Collaboration

- Promotion of Collaboration: Encourages interaction among students, faculty, and researchers from diverse disciplines and universities, enhancing cross-pollination of ideas.
- Knowledge Sharing: Facilitates the exchange of skills and expertise among participating institutions, enriching the research experience.

2. Innovation and Creativity

- Fostering Innovation: Supports the creation of workshops on cutting-edge and relevant topics, promoting inventive thinking in line with SRAs.
- Development of Ideas: Provides a conducive environment for generating new concepts and research ideas in EELISA.

3. Networking

- Networking Opportunities: Creates avenues for students and faculties from various universities to connect, fostering professional and academic bonds.
- Building Relationships: Helps in establishing long-term relationships among EELISA professionals that can benefit career development and collaborative projects.

4. Visibility and Recognition

- Increased Visibility: Enhances the profile of participating universities and their programs, attracting more attention and potential partnerships.
- Recognition: Acknowledges the efforts of partners involved in organizing and participating, boosting morale and reputation within EELISA.

Weaknesses

1. Limited Resources

- **Resource Shortages:** Potential lack of sufficient funds and resources to support all workshops, limiting the initiative's scope.
- **Dependency:** Reliance on the resources of participating universities, which may vary in availability and support.

2. Heterogeneous Participation

- **Variability in Participation:** Uneven commitment and involvement from different universities can affect the quality and consistency of workshops.
- **Quality Differences:** Disparities in the organization and delivery of workshops due to varying institutional capabilities.

3. Coordination and Communication

- **Coordination Challenges:** Difficulty in synchronizing activities across various institutions and departments, leading to potential inefficiencies.
- **Communication Issues:** Possible problems in managing expectations and ensuring clear communication among all participants.

4. Coordination Imbalance

- **Dominant Coordinator:** UPM's significant role, especially in later rounds, may create an imbalance in leadership and an over-reliance on a single institution.

5. Variable Hit Rate

- **Fluctuating Success Rates:** Variability in proposal success rates (50% to 80%) indicates inconsistent proposal quality or competition levels.

6. Impact Evaluation

- **Measuring Impact:** Challenges in assessing the long-term effects of the workshops, making it hard to quantify success.
 - **Tracking Progress:** Difficulty in effectively tracking outcomes and progress over time, potentially undermining efforts to improve.
- Impact Measurement:** The true impact of workshops often unfolds over time and involves qualitative changes in knowledge, skills, and networks, which quantitative metrics might fail to capture.

Opportunities

1. Expansion and Scalability

- Expanding Reach: Opportunity to include more partners of EELISA, broadening the initiative's impact.
- Scalability: Potential to scale up the number of workshops and participants, enhancing the initiative's scope and influence.

2. Funding

- Additional Funding Sources: Opportunities to secure funding from governmental bodies, foundations, and companies, ensuring sustainability.
- Sponsorships: Potential for sponsorships from industries and commercial partners, providing financial support and resources.

3. Professional Development

- Practical Experience: Enhances students' professional growth through hands-on experiences and training.
- Skill Acquisition: Fosters the development of cross-disciplinary and sector-specific skills, making participants more versatile.

4. Improvement and Standardization

- Standardized Processes: Developing best practices for proposal preparation could enhance consistency and quality, improving overall success rates.

5. Connection to other EELISA TOOLS

- EELISA NETWORKING PLATFORM, in order to find partners with similar ideas.
- EELISA FACILITIES PLATFORM, in order to share facilities.
- EELISA COMMUNITIES, to amplify the collaboration and spread the ideas.

Threats

1. Competition and Overlap

- Competing Initiatives: Risk of competition with similar programs at national and international levels, potentially diluting impact.
- Activity Overlap: Possible duplication of efforts with existing university activities, leading to inefficiencies.

2. Execution Risks

- Organizational Failures: Risk of failures in organizing and managing workshops effectively, which could undermine the initiative.
- Logistical Issues: Potential administrative and logistical challenges that could hinder successful execution.

3. Sustainability of Engagement

- Maintaining Participation: Long-term engagement may be difficult due to resource constraints and shifting institutional priorities.

4. Dependency on Key Institutions

- Over-Reliance on Certain Institutions: Heavy dependence on key institutions like UPM could pose risks if these institutions face challenges or reduce their involvement.

5. Funding Fluctuations

- Variable Funding Availability: Changes in funding criteria or availability could impact the number of funded proposals, affecting initiative continuity.

6. Administrative and Logistical Challenges

- Managing Growth: Increased proposals and participants could lead to administrative and logistical difficulties, impacting efficiency and effectiveness.

7. Selection process:

- Quantitative criteria: using quantitative criteria alone might not capture the full complexity of a proposal, such as the context, the underlying rationale, and the expected qualitative benefits.
- Continuity of the workshop: in order to spread the call and the resources, the limit to not refund the same team could be a risk to have a real impact (same team could meet more than one to prepare their reserach proposal).

SWOT Analysis of an EELISA Workshop

Strengths:

1. **International participants:** The workshop attracted participants from various countries, enhancing its diversity and bringing together a wide range of perspectives and experiences.
2. **Availability and good faith:** The participants demonstrated a strong willingness to engage and contribute, fostering an atmosphere of openness and collaboration.
3. **Spontaneous academics from the EELISA university network:** The presence of academics from the EELISA university network added depth and expertise to the discussions, enriching the overall content of the workshop.
4. **Networking opportunities:** The workshop facilitated the establishment of new connections and friendships, allowing for potential future collaborations and partnerships.
5. **Establishment of Sant'Anna as a valuable host:** Both academic and administrative resources have shown to be up to the task of providing adequate conference infrastructure.
6. **Dynamically structured form:** The workshop's flexible structure enabled open brainstorming sessions, encouraging participants to freely exchange ideas and explore different perspectives.
7. **Wide-reaching topics:** The workshop's reach was intentionally broad to account for as many different perspectives and overlaps as possible.

Weaknesses:

1. **Lack of content clarity:** The quick organization of the workshop resulted in a somewhat ambiguous content structure, leaving the specific topics up in the air. This ambiguity may have affected the overall focus and cohesiveness of the discussions.
2. **Time-consuming introductions:** The considerable time invested in self-introductions slowed down the pace of the workshop, potentially limiting the time available for more substantive discussions and activities. Nevertheless, this was also due to the high number of interested participants and will, in the long run, likely be seen as a strength.

Opportunities:

1. **Solid collaborations for the future:** The extensive time dedicated to getting to know the participants allowed for the establishment of clear lines of communication and the identification of potential collaboration opportunities. These connections can serve as a foundation for future joint projects and initiatives.
2. **In-depth exploration of topics:** The decision to hold a follow-up call in early July presents an opportunity to delve deeper into the identified overlapping topics. This additional time will allow for a more comprehensive examination of specific areas and facilitate a more in-depth understanding of the subject matter.

Threats:

1. **Potential lack of focus:** Without a clearer structure or defined focus, the workshop may risk losing sight of specific objectives and fail to achieve tangible outcomes.
2. **Time constraints:** The need to cover the topics in more detail during the upcoming call may pose a challenge due to limited time availability. It is crucial to ensure that sufficient time is allocated to each topic to avoid rushing through important discussions.

Overall, the workshop provided a valuable platform for interdisciplinary exchange and networking among international participants. Many of the weaknesses can be also seen as strengths, as well as vice-versa. While the quick organization and lack of content clarity posed challenges, the workshop's positive aspects, such as the availability of participants, the establishment of collaborations, and the open brainstorming sessions, create a promising foundation for future endeavors. By addressing the weaknesses and capitalizing on the opportunities, the workshop can progress towards achieving its goals and fostering meaningful advancements within the collaborative framework.

(Ways of Water)

Annex I

IMPLEMENTATION 'OPEN CALLS'

EELISA InnoCORE – CONNECTING RESEARCHERS FINAL CALL FOR WORKSHOPS

1. WHAT: CALL FOR THEMATIC WORKSHOPS – EELISA CONNECT

The aim of this **call for proposals for EELISA InnoCORE research workshops – EELISAconnect** is to provide a setting for the discussion among EELISA researchers and academicians of specialized research topics that align with the [EELISA InnoCORE Strategic Research Areas](#) (SRAs)⁴. Workshop proposals should include research topics aligned with the [EELISA mission](#) and be relevant for the achievement of the [Sustainable Development Goals](#) set up by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015.

The format of the proposed workshops should be designed to promote and active face to face exchange of ideas between EELISA researchers and academicians, sharing their experiences, contact networks, capacities, and infrastructures, etc., with the purpose of generating new proposals for future joint research projects and increasing international mobility and collaborations. Particularly, workshops should have the potential to trigger new research proposals under Horizon Europe and other European or international calls. Workshops aim at providing a forum for EELISA researchers and academicians to present their work and receive feedback from EELISA peers in an interactive atmosphere. The workshops could also help to share facilities via the [for any updates please check the website catalogue of research infrastructures](#) (for research and teaching). Preceding engagement in EELISA InnoCORE research clusters⁵ or [EELISA Communities](#)⁶ is welcome but not required.

Online workshops will not receive funding. Onsite and hybrid workshops will receive up to 17,000 euros of funding for travel and accommodation expenses of participants, as well as other eligible costs such as dissemination, catering, and transport, as described in section 2 below. Costs exceeding the funded amount must be covered by the partners organizing the workshop.

The **workshop organization** must involve at least **three researchers from three EELISA partners**. One of them acts as a local organizer and will be in charge of the organization of the logistics of the onsite event. The organisers must be research staff, researchers and academicians from EELISA partners working full time for the partner institution either with a permanent or a fixed-term contract. For researchers with a fixed term contract, the work contract must cover the duration of EELISA InnoCORE until 31 May 2024.

The workshop organizers will identify a tentative list of **workshop participants**. They will identify their position, responsibilities, and affiliation. The Research Networking Platform at this link <https://community.eelisa.eu/research-network/> can be used to facilitate connections and partners among EELISA institutions. The size of the workshop is open and will depend on the scope and aims of the event.

⁴ **EELISA InnoCORE SRAs (Strategic Research Areas)** are research areas selected as “key strategic” by the EELISA consortium at the Kick-off meeting, namely: 1. Digital; 2. Climate, Energy & Mobility; 3. Social Sciences & Humanities; 4. Health; 5. Artificial Intelligence; 6. Connectivity; 7. Food, Bio-economy, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment; 8. Culture, Creativity & Inclusive Society; 9. Smart Industry & Space Technologies; 10. Natural Sciences; 11. Advanced Materials Science and Engineering.

⁵ **EELISA Clusters** are research and innovation-based working groups addressing the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities. Clusters will be created by means of a matching function included in the EELISA Networking Platform.

EELISA Proto-Clusters are the first Clusters obtained by manual selection starting from RPs uploaded in the excel file. This exercise is meant to setup the entries of the EELISA Networking Platform. Clusters will be automatically created by the platform in a second stage.

⁶ The **EELISA Communities** are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

Considering the results of the first call, a different team might submit a proposal on the same topic of the winning workshops to continue the collaboration established under those topics. However, new applications from the winning proposals are encouraged.

The budget available for this call is 119,000 euros for the funding of a minimum of 7 workshops (a maximum of 17,000 euros per workshop). Savings from the previous call may be used to support the funding of the eventual shortlisted applications.

2. FUNDED COSTS

EELISA InnoCORE will provide up to 17,000 euros to cover the costs of each workshop. The funds will be paid from this open call budget. The funds may cover:

- Travel, accommodation, and subsistence for researchers or academic staff from EELISA universities. PhD students are eligible. All researchers, academic staff and PhD students should have a work contract with the partner institution covering the whole duration of EELISA InnoCORE.
- Catering (coffee breaks, lunch break offered during the workshop).
- Buses if needed.
- Dissemination (e.g., leaflets, printing).
- Personnel costs for the support in the organisation of the event (up to 10% of the total cost). This cannot be used for covering personnel costs or allowances for research and academic staff from the partner institutions.
- Other costs directly linked to the organisation of the workshop.

The EELISA InnoCORE budget **cannot be used** to cover travel expenses for undergraduate students or to pay for gifts or social programmes.

The budget must be used to fund primarily travel, accommodation and subsistence costs for researchers and academic staff from EELISA institutions. However, in order to give the possibility to invite a renowned keynote speaker, **the budget that can be used to cover travel, accommodation and subsistence expenses of external stakeholders is limited to a maximum of 10% of the budget of the workshop.**

As indicated in section 5 “Financial management”, **the financial management of the workshop will be done following the rules and procedures of the hosting institution, always complying with Horizon 2020 rules and the principle of best-value for money and efficiency. Please check cost categories with your hosting institution and check with them any doubts you may have regarding categories of costs.**

3. APPLICATION

Applicants should send the application form (template in Annex 1) as PDF by 27 November 2023 to eelisa@santannapisa.it reporting in the email subject line “Open Call EELISA Connect”. Applicants (organiser and co-organisers) should include a brief description of their curriculum, describing their experience and merits (section 1). In section 2, applicants are expected to describe how the workshop meets the aim of the call: capacity to boost connections among EELISA researchers and to trigger new research collaborations, including new research proposals under Horizon Europe and other European and international calls; alignment of the topic with EELISA InnoCORE SRAs; relevance and importance of the technical topic for EELISA partners; positive impact on the challenges faced within EELISA Communities; long-term impact of the collaboration fostered by the workshop; likeliness that the activity can be sustained or prolonged, e.g. in an ongoing programme.

4. SELECTION OF PROPOSALS TO BE FUNDED

EELISA InnoCORE Advisory Council for Research and Innovation (ACRI) will do the evaluation and selection. Proposals could be accepted as received or an aggregation of the proposals received could be suggested to reach a wider audience and to get a critical mass of researchers in a greater combined event. The following criteria will be used for the evaluation of proposals:

Capacity of the workshop to boost connections among EELISA researchers (up to 30 points).

- Potential of the workshop to trigger new research collaborations, including new research proposals under Horizon Europe and other European or international calls (up to 15 points).
- Potential of the workshop to trigger new connections between facilities of EELISA partners (up to 5 points).
- Relevance of the topic for EELISA partners and links with EELISA InnoCORE SRAs (up to 10 points).
- Relevance of the topic for the challenges faced within EELISA Communities (up to 10 points).
- Long-term impact of the collaboration fostered by the workshop; likeliness that the activity can be sustained or prolonged, e.g. in an ongoing programme (up to 10 points).
- Gender balance (up to 10 points).

5. FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

The financial management of the workshop will be done following the rules and procedures of the hosting institution, always complying with Horizon 2020 rules and the principle of best-value for money and efficiency. An upfront payment will be made to the hosting institution equal to 50% of the total planned costs of the workshop. The remainder up to the actual total costs of the workshop organisation will be settled after the workshop takes place, against the submission of invoices and the final report (please see section 6) by the hosting institution.

6. FINAL REPORT

The organisers must send a final report of the workshop to eelisa@santannapisa.it reporting in the email subject line “Final Report Open Call” within one month after the workshop, with following minimum content:

1. Workshop general information: date, place, title, program.
2. Number of participants and gender balance.
3. Relationship with the strategic research areas and, where possible, with EELISA InnoCORE research clusters and EELISA Communities.
4. Participants' institutions.
5. Main outcomes, with respect to:
 - a. Future research projects.
 - b. Infrastructures.
 - c. Teaching (doctoral networks, laboratory visits ...).

7. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION BY SELECTED APPLICATIONS

The selected applicants must promote and communicate the workshop using EELISA InnoCORE communication tools and channels. The workshop must be duly disseminated among EELISA InnoCORE teams. When promoting the workshop, it must be clear that the workshop has been selected under EELISA Connect call for workshops launched under EELISA InnoCORE. In compliance with the EU rules, any communication and dissemination material must (a) display the EU emblem and (b) include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811”. When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. Legend and logo:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

8. OTHER REQUIREMENTS AND CONSIDERATIONS

- One grant per organising person (one organising person will only receive one grant).

- The grant will never exceed the total costs of the workshop.
- Acknowledgement of EU funding.
- Dissemination via EELISA website.
- Report to be done after the workshop with the proceedings, results, impact for and contribution to EELISA InnoCORE.
- The workshop must be free of charge.
- The workshop must take place within the four months following the acceptance notification.

9. IMPORTANT DATES (for any updates please check the website)

- Opening: 29 September 2023
- Info Session: 24 October 2023
- Deadline: 27 November 2023
- Acceptance notification: 15 December 2023
- Take place: within four months after the acceptance notification (15th April 2024 at the latest)
- Final report and submission of invoices: within one month after the workshop

Annex II

APPLICATION FORM Workshop proposal – EELISA Connect

Section 1 - ORGANISERS

1. Basic data of the main applicant of the local organizer (compulsory)

The proposal must involve at least three EELISA partners, i.e. the workshop must be jointly organised by at least three researchers or academicians from different EELISA institutions. Eligibility: Research staff from EELISA partners working for the partner institution either with both a permanent or a fixed term contract. For researchers with a fixed term contract, the work contract must cover the duration of EELISA InnoCORE until 31 May 2024.

Title of the workshop		
Local organiser Researcher from the institution where the onsite event will take place, i.e. the hosting institution	Title/First name/Last name:	
	EELISA Institution (hosting institution):	
	Research structure:	
	Category:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	
Short biography of the organizer (max. 200 words)	<i>Please include a description of the position at the University and the experience in organizing this type of events</i>	

2. Co-organisers (compulsory)

The two co-organisers must be researchers or academicians from an EELISA institution different from the hosting institution.

Title of the workshop		
Co-organizer (1) Researcher from an EELISA institution different from the hosting institution	Title/First name/Last name:	
	EELISA Institution (hosting institution):	
	Research structure:	
	Category:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	
Short biography of the co-organizer (max. 200 words)	<i>Please include a description of the position at the University and the experience in organizing this type of events</i>	

Title of the workshop		
Co-organiser (3) Researcher from an EELISA institution different from the hosting institution	Title/First name/Last name:	
	EELISA Institution (hosting institution):	
	Research structure:	
	Category:	
	Telephone:	
	Email:	
Short biography of the co-organizer (max. 200 words)	<i>Please include a description of the position at the University and the experience in organizing this type of events</i>	

3. External participants (optional)

Title/First name/Last name:	University/Company/NGO others, Country

Section 2 – WORKSHOP PROPOSAL

4. Description of the workshop (compulsory)

4.1. Title of the workshop

4.2 Motivation

4.3. Description of the technical issues and scientific areas covered, and link with EELISA Strategic Research Areas

The aim of the workshop is to provide a structured setting for the discussion among relevant EELISA researchers and academicians, of specialized technical topics that align with EELISA structures, tools and strategic research areas. Please describe how the topic of the workshop is linked with the EELISA Strategic Research Areas and its relevance for the challenges faced within EELISA Communities.

Where possible describe also its connection with EELISA research clusters.

At the same time, workshops should provide a forum for EELISA researchers and academicians to present their work and receive feedback from EELISA peers in an interactive atmosphere. The workshop must be an EELISA event and it must serve to strengthen activities of the Alliance. Please explain the capacities you can bring into the Alliance, how the workshop will serve to build the tools for new collaborations and strengthen the R&I dimension of the Alliance.

Please explain the potential of the workshop to trigger new research proposals under Horizon Europe and other European or international calls.

4.4. Description of the workshop's expected impact

The ultimate aim of the workshop is to generate future joint research projects and joint research collaborations. Please describe expected potential future collaborations (joint EU projects, joint publications). If you are planning to apply for a European or international call for proposals, please name it. Please explain how the workshop will serve to build the tools and strengthen the R&I dimension of the Alliance.

5. Budget for activity organizers (compulsory)

Proposed budget for the workshop (add rows if necessary). Please estimate the costs considering that accommodation will cover: 2 nights for 1 day or two days and a half workshop, 3 nights for a two-day workshop.

No.	Item	Description	Costs (€)
1	<i>Travel, accommodation & subsistence of organizers</i>		
2	<i>Travel, accommodation & subsistence of participants</i>		
3	<i>Travel, accommodation & subsistence of invited speakers</i>		
4	<i>Catering, dissemination and other costs</i>		
5	<i>Personnel costs (up to 10%)</i>		

6. Format of the workshop (compulsory)

<i>Duration of the workshop (It is recommended to have between one and two days and a half full day workshop)</i>	
<i>Format of the workshop (onsite or hybrid)</i>	
<i>Tentative date (identify the month)</i>	
<i>Expected number of participants</i>	
<i>Location (identify the facilities of the EELISA partner for the meeting)</i>	

Annex III FINAL EELISA CONNECT WORKSHOP REPORT

DATA SPACES FOR RESEARCHERS: **Fostering Collaborative Research and Innovation.** **REPORT OF THE WORKSHOP**

Workshop name: Data Spaces for Researchers: Fostering Collaborative Research and Innovation	Place: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM-ETSIIINF) Date: 04/03/2024 to 05/03/2024 Format: Face-to-face
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The primary goal of this workshop is to enlarge and strengthen the network of Data Space stakeholders to generate new proposals for future joint research projects, enhance international mobility, and foster collaborations that will drive innovation and academic excellence.

The workshop aligns perfectly with the EELISA vision of redefining the role of engineers in society and fostering inclusivity, collaboration, and innovation by bringing together researchers, academicians, and institutions. We are enthusiastic about the potential of this workshop to make a meaningful impact and look forward to your support and participation in realizing this vision.

The implementation of data policies in universities is a gradual process and differs between them. The situation in the EELISA network is not different. When researchers of these institutions try to work together, they face several challenges:

- Each university has different regulations. with different data policies. In many cases, institutions don't have an explicit policy published.
- Sharing infrastructures are closed to university researchers.
- Difficulty to work with researchers from other institutions in a collaborative space.

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3 1 PARTICIPANTS LIST:

Table #1: List of attendees:

#	SURNAME AND NAME	COMPANY / INSTITUTION	ASSISTANCE (Yes/No)	
			04/03/2023	05/03/2023
	EELISA			
1	GONZÁLEZ GUARDIA ESTEBAN	FAIR IMPACT	Yes	Yes
2	RUIZ CARLOS	INESData	Yes	Yes
3	PARDO JOEL	INESData	Yes	Yes
4	LIU JIAYUN	INESData	Yes	Yes
5	BULUT BURCU	ITU	Yes	Yes
6	UGUR HANDAN	ITU	Yes	Yes
7	GHEORGHE VIOLETA	UPB	Yes	Yes
8	DOBRE CIPRIAN	UPB	Yes	Yes
9	MANASIA LOREDANA	UPB	Yes	Yes
10	NEGRU CATALIN	UPB	Yes	Yes
	EXTERNAL			
11	AUÑON JUAN MIGUEL	GMV	Yes	No
12	GARCÍA SILVA ANDRES	Expert.AI	Yes	No

4 2. WORKSHOP

4.1 2.1 AGENDA

March 4th, 2024

9:00 - 9:30	Registration
9:30 - 9:40	Welcome
9:40 - 10:10	What is a Data Space? Speaker: Carlos Ruiz INESData Language Data Space. Speaker: Andrés García, Expert.AI INESData Mobility Data Space. Speaker: Juan Miguel Auñón, GMV
10:10 - 10:15	FAIR principles Speaker: Esteban González
10:15 - 10:30	Open Science in EELISA Speaker: Dana Gheorghe
10:30 - 11:00	Presentation of scenarios
10:30 - 10:40	Dr. Eng. Catalin Negru, UNSTP- Data space as an educational
common space	
10:40 - 10:50	Dr. Burcu Bulut, ITU - Data space as an Interoperability Platform
10:50 - 11:00	Dr. Carlos Ruiz - Artificial Intelligence in Data spaces
11:00 - 11:15	Coffee Break
11:15 - 13:00	Working time for scenarios (in parallel)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch
14:00 - 16:00	Working time for scenarios (in parallel)
16:00 - 16:15	Coffee Break
16:15 - 16:45	Presentation of progress & next steps

March 5th, 2024

9:30 - 10:30	Recap & synergies
10:30 - 10:45	Coffee Break
10:45 - 12:00	Working time
12:00 - 12:30	Peer learning
12:30 - 13:00	Presentation of results & wrap-up
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch

4.2 2.2 Day 1: 4th March 2024

Esteban González (UPM), co-organizer of the workshop, opened the session and welcomed all the attendees, explaining the agenda and the objectives. After that, each participant was introduced, highlighting their expectations. Considering the number and diversity of participants, we **agree to modify the agenda** to accommodate the active involvement of all attendees in the sessions.

After this decision, the workshop continued with a block of presentations about Data Spaces. All these presentations were done by INESData initiative members. The first presenter was Carlos Ruiz, project manager of INESData, was an introduction to general concepts of data spaces and its role in the European Data Strategy. Participants discerned potential correlations between this infrastructure and their respective scenarios, facilitating INESData's identification of stakeholder requirements, including those from librarians and academicians.

Next presentation was more technical. The first, by Andres García Silva (Expert.AI), was focused on the application of language models in Data Spaces. In the case of the scenarios, language models' tools can be used **to detect hypothesis and methods defined in scientific publications**, as well as can be used to enrich the metadata associated with them.

In the last presentation of the block, by Juan Miguel Auñón (GMV), were a demo of the application of a Data Space in the mobility domain. Participants could observe a real implementation and its potential use in their domains. The demo was focused on the description of a **content negotiation process to access to data based on the requirements given by the user**, and the license of the content.

The subsequent session focused on Open Science, during which Esteban González from the FAIR IMPACT project elaborated on the implementation of FAIR principles in data, with a specific emphasis on repositories and education. Dana Gheorghe, from UNSTP - UPB, described the application of the Open Science in the EELISA alliance, and outlined the Open Science Strategy of the alliance, including the next steps. Also, the actions of the ambassador network were discussed during this session.

After a coffee break, was the turn of the presentations related to the scenarios proposed in the workshop. Each scenario was presented by their representants: Catalin Negru, Burcu Bulut and Carlos Ruiz. During these presentations, they present their objectives, expectations and open questions.

As we commented before, we decided to focus this first day in the Data Space as an Interoperability Platform scenario, relegating the second for the next day. It is noteworthy that Scenario 3, Artificial

Intelligence in Data Spaces, is a common theme shared with the other two scenarios. It means that the objective of this scenario is to identify AI elements in the other two.

In the first scenario, the speaker presented some open questions to guide the conversation:

- Can we think of institutional repositories as part of distributed learning systems?
- Can we as librarians support open educational practices if we store educational resources in institutional repositories for open sharing and enable them to be used in teaching and learning processes?
- If we can; what should be done to increase the interconnectivity/interoperability of institutional repositories to realize education integration within EELISA?
- Can data spaces be a solution?

As conclusions, we point the importance of deploying repositories for publications and data that **implement standards like DCAT and protocols like OAI-PMH**. These mechanisms favor the interconnection of the repositories between them and with a data space. What is the role of the data space in this infrastructure? A data space can define a **data policy for sharing and reusing the content, based on the licenses and metadata of the content**. Also, allow to negotiate the exchange of information with other repositories and data spaces.

During this session, the comments and interests of the attendees were exchanged. There was a high level of participation. Participants express the willingness to study the application of data spaces as an element and facilitator for sharing information. It's worth highlighting that beyond merely hosting data, a data space can offer services aimed at enhancing connectivity and facilitating discovery. These services may include AI-driven features: i) to extract metadata from publications, ii) to enrich the information present in the repository, iii) to recommend alternative/similar resources, etc.

4.3 2.3 Day 2: 5th March 2024

On the second day, we started with two presentations related to the scenario two: Data Spaces as an Educational Platform. These presentations set out potential uses of the data space infrastructure in education, that were discussed during the rest of the day.

Dr Ciprian Dobre presented a case of study about reproducible experiments using notebooks. He showed how a student can execute a notebook from a Github repository using the tool binder. This tool provides an execution environment to students, so they don't need to install these development tools in their computer. Plus, all students use the same execution environment. After a discussion, we agreed that **this service could be provided by the data space**, together with the data needed to run the experiment/assessment.

After this presentation, Dr. Catalin Negru presented the first version of the **Open Science Training Hub** developed by the project EELISA innoCORE. This is a catalog of Open Science courses created by the EELISA alliance and it is based on a distributed solution. The central

node is deployed on the UPB servers, and the rest of the nodes can be deployed on the servers of the different EELISA institutions. Moodle is the technology selected to create this network of catalogs.

Regarding this case study, a data space can play a central role in this platform. Thanks to the development of connectors, we can **connect a data space with a moodle instance**, which allows students of these platforms to access to the information hosted in a data space, together with the services provided by its, like a notebook or a binder. Plus, researchers can easily create and share assessments that can be completed by the students using the resources of their workspace.

What is the role of the AI in this scenario? For example, the AI can be used in this scenario to customize the exercises to the skills of the student. Also, can recommend to students some additional lectures based on their preferences, motivating them to deepen their learning. We must not forget the use of chatbot to tutorize them. This can be potentially dangerous because currently, large language models can introduce hallucinations, generated content that may be unreliable or misleading.

The workshop was truly engaging and captivating, characterized by a palpable energy fueled by the active participation of all attendees. From the outset, participants eagerly immersed themselves in the topics discussed, fostering a dynamic exchange of ideas and experiences. Through thought-provoking discussions, hands-on activities, and interactive group exercises, everyone contributed their insights and perspectives, creating a vibrant atmosphere of collaboration and learning.

4.4 2.4 Conclusions.

4.4.1

1. **Integration and Interoperability:** Across all presentations, there was a strong emphasis on the need for data spaces to be interoperable and able to support a diverse range of applications and use cases. This suggests a move towards standardized protocols and frameworks within these data spaces.
2. **Sector-Specific Applications:** Each presentation highlighted the importance of tailoring data spaces to specific sector needs—language technologies and mobility—demonstrating the versatility and necessity of data spaces in addressing sector-specific challenges.
3. **Future Strategies:** Given the importance of data sovereignty and the emphasis on open and transparent data handling practices, future strategies should focus on enhancing user trust and security in data spaces. This includes developing robust data governance frameworks that are transparent and user-centric.
4. **Collaboration Opportunities:** The workshops identified multiple opportunities for collaboration between academia, industry, and government to further explore and exploit the potentials of data spaces. This could involve joint development initiatives, shared resources, and cooperative policy-making efforts.

5. **Research and Development:** Continued research and development are crucial to address existing challenges in data management, particularly in handling large-scale, dynamic data sets across distributed environments. This should include the development of new tools and technologies that can facilitate data handling, analysis, and decision-making processes in real-time.

4.4.2

5 3 PENDING TASK AND AGREEMENTS

Following the conclusion of the workshop, the attendees expressed their willingness to sustain the collaborative ethos established during the event. With a collective commitment to harnessing each other's expertise and resources, they envisaged an array of compelling projects and initiatives poised to benefit from their combined efforts. We agree to explore the use of data spaces, together with INESData, in the different scenarios **developing some prototypes in master thesis or final undergraduate works.**

Also, we agree to encourage the adoption of the OS ambassador network in EELISA and to strength the collaboration with other alliances and with the EELISA OS community. The EELISA Training Platform can play a crucial role in this task. We plan to foster the use of this platform by creating innovative content for researchers and students. We plan to collaborate with the European projects RITRAINPLUS and FAIR IMPACT to offer courses of high quality.

Also, we will study the participation of the institutions involved in the workshop in future calls related to education.

6 4 FORTHCOMING MEETINGS

The attendees participate in regular meetings of the project EELISA innoCORE, where we can share the new developments and to discuss the next actions.

We will continue our collaboration in the context of EELISA 2.0 and we will be waiting for new funding opportunities and open calls in European projects.

**EELISA CONNECT
WORKSHOP**

**CITY OF PROXIMITY: THE
POWER OF LOCAL-BASED
INITIATIVES TO BOOST URBAN
TRANSITION**

Final Report

This is an activity funded under EELISA INNOCORE project EELISA INNOCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101059111

REPORT OF THE WORKSHOP

6.1.1 GENERAL DATA:

Workshop name:

Place: Escuela Técnica Superior de Arquitectura de Madrid, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (ETSAM-UPM)

City of Proximity: the power of local-based initiatives to boost urban transition

Date: 18/03/2024 – 19/03/2024

Format: Hybrid on the first day and on-site on the second day

The workshop "City of Proximity: the power of local-based initiatives to boost urban transition", organized by EELISA DISCOVERY in the framework of the EELISA Connect call promoted by EELISA InnoCORE, took place in Madrid on March 18-19, 2024, and brought together an interdisciplinary team of researchers from the different EELISA Universities.

The workshop is based on the concept of City of Proximity, which refers to the idea that the dimension of proximity is a powerful tool to formulate urban transition strategies that improve the quality of life and contribute to the decarbonization of cities. The workshop focused on the sustainable and inclusive

transition of existing neighbourhoods and communities, as the smallest units of the city that can substantially contribute to cities’ climate targets.

The workshop aimed to create a space for reflection and debate, identifying common interests and fostering the exchange of best practices among EELISA Alliance researchers.

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1. PARTICIPANTS LIST AND AGENDA

6.1.2 1.1 PARTICIPANTS LIST

#	SURNAME AND NAME	COMPANY / INSTITUTION	ASSISTANCE (YES/NO)	
			18/03	19/03
	EELISA			
1	FRANCESCA OLIVIERI	UPM	YES	YES
2	EMMANUELLE CUNNINGHAM SABOT	PSL	YES	YES
3	NORMA SCHEMSCHAT	PSL	YES	YES
4	ESTER HIGUERAS	UPM	YES	YES
5	JOSÉ CARPIO	UPM	YES	YES
6	MIGUEL NÚÑEZ	UPM	YES	YES
7	JESÚS FRAILE	UPM	YES	NO
8	JUAN IGNACIO PÉREZ	UPM	YES	YES
9	WILLI BAUER	FAU	YES	YES
10	ASUDE BOLAT	ITU	YES	YES
11	FATIH TERZI	ITU	YES	YES
12	EBRU ERBAS GURLER	ITU	YES	YES
13	LOUISE NOUR SASSENOU	UPM	YES	YES
14	TOBIAS HABERER	FAU	YES	YES
15	MARC QUESADA	UPM	YES	YES
16	MARTINA DELL UNTO	UPM	YES	YES
17	DAVID SPENGER	FAU	YES	YES
18	ALVARO GUTIERREZ	UPM	YES	NO
19	MANUEL BLANCO	UPM	YES	NO
20	ALBERTO GARRIDO	UPM	YES	NO
21	ISABEL SALGUEIRO	UPM	YES	NO
22	PATRICIA BENITO	UPM	YES	NO
24	IRENE DEL HIERRO	UPM	YES	NO
25	BRUNILDA PEREZ	UPM	YES	NO
26	ANA MACÍAS	UPM	YES	NO
27	DANIEL FERNANDÉZ	UPM	YES	NO
	EXTERNAL			
28	LEONOR DE LA CUEVA	R2M	YES	YES

Gender balance

1.2 AGENDA

DAY 1		
Time	Session	Speaker
08:45	Registration- Meeting point	
09:00	Institutional welcome: ETSAM	Manuel Blanco Lage - ETSAM Director
9:10	Institutional welcome: EELISA Alliance	Alberto Garrido Colmenero - Vice Rector for Quality and Efficiency
9:20	Institutional welcome: EELISA InnoCORE	Asunción Gómez Pérez - Vice Rector for Research, Innovation and Doctoral Studies
9:30	General introduction of “City of Proximity” approach & Agenda of the event	Francesca Olivieri - “City of proximity” and EELISA DISCOVERY Coordinator
9:50	Introduction of subtopics (10 min each): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy and climate change - Transformation of urban space - Responsible and just habits - Monitoring and impact assessment 	Louise-Nour Sassenou, Researcher, ETSAM, UPM José Carpio Pinedo, Associate Professor, ETSAM, UPM Martina Dell’Unto, Researcher, ETSAM, UPM Miguel Nuñez Peiró, Assistant Professor, ETSAM, UPM
10:30	Coffee Break	
11:00	Presentations of Universities (20 min each) related to subtopics of “City of Proximity”	Jesus Fraile-Ardanuy, Associate Professor, ETSIT, UPM Juan Ignacio Pérez-Díaz, Associate Professor, ETSICCP, UPM Emmanuèle Cunningham Sabot, Full Professor, Department of Geography, PSL Fatih Terzi, Full Professor, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, ITU Asude Bolat, Researcher, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi Tobias Häberer, Profesor, Department of Geography, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg David Spenger, Researcher, Department of Geography, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg
13:00	Lunch	
14:30	Introduction on calls of Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions	Patricia Benito Martin, Ofician de Proyectos Internacionales I+D+i, UPM
15:30	Strategy for collaboration and proposal preparations	Louise-Nour Sassenou, Researcher, ETSAM, UPM
15:40	Work session 1- Idea Brainstorming – Part 1	All Partners
16:00	Coffee Break	
16:30	Work session 1 – Idea Brainstorming – Part 2	All Partners
17:30	Closing of the day	UPM
20:00	Project dinner, City Centre (El Fogón Verde, https://maps.app.goo.gl/hDvDim8hZAiV8MH77)	<i>In charge of partners</i>

DAY 2		
Time	Session	Speaker
08:45	Arrival – Meeting Point “Sala de Consejos”	
09:00	Welcome and Agenda of the day	UPM
09:15	Inputs from work session 1 & selection of idea	All Partners
10:00	“How to facilitate the writing of powerful and disruptive European proposals” + inputs consortium	Leonor de la Cueva, R2M, Innovation Division - EU project manager
10:30	Work session 2 – Consortium	All Partners
11:30	Coffee Break	
12:00	Work session 3 – Organization of proposal writing and preparation	All Partners
13:00	Closing of the event	UPM
13:30	Lunch, Museo del Traje Madrid	All Partners

2. INTRODUCTION

City of Proximity provides participants with the chance to delve into the integration and combination of various facets of urban sustainability on a local level.

The City of Proximity concept refers to the idea that the proximity dimension is a powerful tool for formulating urban transition strategies that improve the quality of life and contribute to the decarbonization of cities. This concept is based on the idea that cities can be more sustainable and inclusive if we harness the power of proximity to foster locally based urban transitions. In the framework of the "City of Proximity" workshop, several questions related to this concept are explored. The workshop focuses on the sustainable and inclusive transition of existing neighbourhoods and communities as smaller units of the city that can contribute substantially to cities' climate goals.

Thus, it has been decided that the four sub-topics on which the development of the workshop should focus are the following: Energy and climate change, Transformation of urban space, Responsible and just habits, Monitoring and impact assessment. These four dimensions are the most important in order to achieve more sustainable cities.

City of Proximity is intimately linked to six of EELISA's Strategic Research Areas. Firstly, the overarching theme of sustainable and inclusive transition at the local level aligns with the "Smart, Green, and Resilient Cities" area. Specifically, the subtopics "Energy and Climate Change" and "Transformation of Urban Space" are designed to cover the primary challenges a neighbourhood faces on its journey towards sustainability. These subtopics are also connected to the EELISA clusters "Climate Energy and Mobility" and "Advanced Materials Science and Engineering." Moreover, the subtopic "Responsible and Just Habits" addresses potential social strategies (such as governance models, training, and workshops) that aim to engage and include citizens and various stakeholders in the local sustainable transition process. This subtopic is in harmony with the EELISA domains of "Social Sciences and Humanities," "Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society," and "Health." Lastly, the fourth subtopic of City of Proximity considers the cross-sectional inclusion of smart assets for monitoring and impact assessment, which ties into EELISA's focus areas on "Digitalisation" and digital innovation via "Artificial Intelligence".

City of Proximity is orchestrated by EELISA DISCOVERY, a community led by Francesca Olivieri, the local researcher from the host institution. EELISA DISCOVERY is dedicated to addressing the ecological transition and the decarbonization of cities. In particular, the community's researchers share a common focus on pertinent topics related to sustainability and energy transition, such as urban resilience, building energy efficiency, nature integration in urban settings, waste recovery, water reuse, and the adoption of circular economy principles, alongside shifts in consumption habits.

The objective of forming a consortium with other universities was to combine resources and knowledge. Each university could have its own specialty or focus, and by working together, they were able to address the problem from multiple angles and develop more comprehensive and effective solutions. In the context of this workshop, this also provided students and academics the opportunity to learn from each other and experience different approaches.

3. MEETING DEVELOPMENT

6.1.3 3.1 DAY 1 – MARCH 18

The first part of Day 1 was an open and hybrid session, through ZOOM, in order to introduce the theoretical framework of City of Proximity and to give the opportunity to showcase the research work being done in the other universities of the EELISA alliance.

Manuel Blanco Lage, ETSAM Director, opened the session and welcomed all the attendees. Also, Alberto Garrido Colmenero, Vice Rector for Quality and Efficiency, and Isabel Salgueiro on behalf of Asunción Gómez Pérez, Vice Rector for Research, Innovation and Doctoral Studies, extended a warm welcome to the participants and introduced the EELISA Alliance and EELISA InnoCORE.

Francesca Olivieri, coordinator of the project, started explaining the agenda, the objectives of the workshop and presenting the workshop consortium. The coordinator then presented the conceptual framework of the city of proximity with the challenges and possible solutions at the local level.

Figure 2-Opening of the day

Once the introductions were finished, the coordinator opened the way for the presentations and introductions of the subtopics. Four presentations took place, by members of the UPM team, about Energy and climate change, transformation of urban space, responsible and just habits, and monitoring and impact assessment.

Figure 3-Sub-topics presentations

Afterward, the participants of the other universities (ITU, FAU, PSL, and UPM) were then invited to present their organizations, activities, ongoing projects, and their respective interests in the research and innovation areas they would like to participate in.

Figure 4-Universities presentation

In the afternoon, the session was exclusively open to workshop participants. The first part of the session focused on framing the call of the workshop (Staff Exchange) and the second part of the session focused on the thematic focus of a possible proposal.

Patricia Benito from OPI UPM's International Projects Office, explained in detail the alternatives to competitive calls at European level, the types of projects, and the funding timetables, with the aim of giving participants a broad vision of their projects and motivating them to participate and submit calls. The last presentation before work session 1, by Louise-Nour Sassenou, consisted of strategy for collaboration and proposal preparations.

The workshop was based on brainstorming, consisting in the elaboration of 3 whiteboards, each one for one of the subtopics (Energy and climate change, Transformation of urban space and Responsible and just habits) where the participants, divided into groups, rotating among the whiteboards, placed post-it notes with concepts or ideas. Finally, all participants voted on the best ideas, and several were selected for discussion the following day.

The three boards were divided into four parts: innovation, challenges, solutions, and opportunities. The different groups, made up of members from various universities, posted ideas on the four issues raised on each board for ten minutes. When the time was up, the groups rotated until they had worked on the three different sub-topics.

Figure 5-Presentation of "Introduction on calls of Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions" by Patricia Benito from OPI and Work session 1

At the end of the 30 minutes, all the groups met to evaluate the different proposals, establishing relationships between them, and valuing all ideas as a whole, not independently. To evaluate them and select the most interesting ones, each member was given 5 stickers with which to select the proposals.

Citizen participation, resilience of urban space, diversity, community partnerships, and easy replicability of the projects were some of the principles that were agreed upon for the evolution of the project. In this way, through a community and participatory process, the course was set for the next day's workshop sessions.

Table 2-Institution presentations day 1

Nº	PRESENTATION / AREA OF WORK	RESPONSIBLE	INSTITUTION / COMPANY
OPEN SESSION (HYBRID)			
1	WELCOME ETSAM	MANUEL BLANCO LAGE	UPM - ETSAM
2	WELCOME EELISA ALLIANCE	ALBERTO GARRIDO COLMENERO	UPM
3	WELCOME EELISA INNOCORE	ASUNCIÓN GÓMEZ PÉREZ	UPM
4	INTRODUCTION OF CITY OF PROXIMITY	FRANCESCA OLIVIERI	UPM – ETSAM
5	ENERGY AND CLIMATE CHANGE	LOUISE-NOUR SASSENOU	UPM - ETSAM
6	TRANSFORMATION OF URBAN SPACE	JOSÉ CARPIO PINEDO	UPM - ETSAM
7	RESPONSIBLE AND JUST HABITS	MARTINA DELL'UNTO	UPM - ETSAM
8	MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT	MIGUEL NÚÑEZ PEIRÓ	UPM - ETSAM
9	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID	JESÚS FRAILE-ARDANUY & JUAN IGNACIO PÉREZ-DIAZ	UPM – ETSIT & UPM - ETSICCP
10	PARIS SCIENCES & LETTRES	EMMANUÈLE CUNNINGHAM SABOT	PSL
11	ISTANBUL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY	FATIH TERZI & ASUDE BOLAT	ITU
12	FAU ERLANGEN-NÜRNBERG	TOBIAS HÄBERER & DAVID SPENGER	FAU
SESSION ONLY FOR WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS (IN PERSON)			
13	MARIE SKLODOWSKA- CURIE ACTIONS	PATRICIA BENITO MARTÍN	UPM - OPI
14	PROPOSAL PREPARATIONS	LOUISE-NOUR SASSENOU	UPM – ETSAM
15	WORK SESSION 1	ALL PARTNERS	ALL PARTNERS

6.1.4 3.2 DAY 2 – MARCH 19

On the second day, the session started with a short presentation of the agenda of the day. Later, the day started with the inputs of project proposals, where the participants discussed the feasibility, main issues, strengths, and weaknesses of the proposals. As a conclusion of this session, a diagram of ideas was framed, which was taken up again in the following session, after R2M's presentation.

Figure 6-Work Session 2

The day continued with a presentation by Leonor de la Cueva, from R2M, about how to facilitate the writing of powerful and disruptive European proposals and keys on how to set up a consortium for the Staff Exchange proposal.

Figure 7-Presentation "How to facilitate the writing of powerful and disruptive European proposals" by Leonor de la Cueva from R2M and work session 3.

Finally, the last session consisted of a reflection on the skills that each entity has, and which entities will be needed to constitute a strong consortium. In addition, this session discussed the next steps to be taken in order to organize the writing of the proposal, and an overall idea of the proposal that will continue to be worked on in the following months was put forward.

Table 3-Institution and company presentation day 2

Nº	PRESENTATION / AREA OF WORK	RESPONSIBLE	INSTITUTION / COMPANY
1	INPUTS FROM WORK SESSION 1 & SELECTION OF IDEA	LOUISE-NOUR SASSENOU AND MARTINA DELL UNTO	UPM
2	“HOW TO FACILITATE THE WRITING OF POWERFUL AND DISRUPTIVE EUROPEAN PROPOSALS”	LEONOR DE LA CUEVA	R2M
3	WORK SESSION 2	ALL PARTNERS	ALL PARTNERS
4	WORK SESSION 3	ALL PARTNERS	ALL PARTNERS

Figure 8- Whiteboards of Work session 1 and 2

4. PENDING TASK, AGREEMENTS AND NEXT MEETING

As mentioned, the debate to decide on the proposal is still open. Work is being carried out through surveys

(https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSddqX226iID_dzvnVh1wH1M8HNReOC1N61MD63c_tmKkfJ7A/viewform?usp=pp_url) in which the commitment of the different partners is being defined, and the main concept and the main objective are both being finalized. In addition, a video of the activities that took place during the workshop will be published in the coming months. This video, recorded by a professional, will be used to disseminate the activity within the framework of EELISA Connect.

The members committed to organizing and following up on the work through meetings to continue developing the proposal, with the objective of its subsequent presentation to the corresponding competitive call. The next meeting date established with the workshop participants will be June 2024, where the work schedule for the Staff Exchange proposal will be defined. The survey is also defining in which other call frameworks the City of Proximity alliance will be interested in working

and so far, the partners have defined the following collaboration frameworks: COST Action, New European Bauhaus and Smart Cities Marketplace, and Scalable Cities.

5. MAIN OUTCOMES

The proposed workshop aimed to create and formalize an alliance between the different EELISA researchers, specialized in the sustainable transition of cities, to join efforts and knowledge to carry out proposals to European calls for proposals.

This workshop has been able to guarantee an important impact for the EELISA community, as the session has been part of a broader process of participation in international calls for proposals. This broader process has allowed to deepen the sessions in different phases, deepening in each of them the most important issues required to participate in international calls for proposals.

The call for proposals selected for the workshop has finally been Staff Exchange: the European Staff Exchange Project, also known as Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Staff Exchanges, is a program that promotes international, intersectoral and interdisciplinary innovative collaboration in research and innovation through the exchange of staff and the sharing of knowledge and ideas.

The main objective of the Staff Exchanges is to fund short-term international and intersectoral exchanges of staff members involved in research and innovation activities of participating organizations. The ultimate goal of this proposal is to develop sustainable collaborative projects between different organizations from the academic and non-academic sectors (in particular SMEs), based in Europe and beyond.

Staff exchanges are open to international consortia of universities, research institutions, companies, SMEs and other non-academic organizations. They must include at least three organizations from three different countries, two of which must be located in an EU Member State or in a Horizon Europe associated country.

The collaborative approach of MSCA staff exchanges should exploit the complementary competencies of the participating organizations and create synergies between them. Secondments should be essential to carry out the R&I activities of the joint project. The project should allow for networking activities and the organization of workshops and conferences to facilitate knowledge sharing and the testing of innovative approaches to specific R&I topics.

For all these reasons, this call was selected, as the City of Proximity proposal could be an excellent opportunity to create links between researchers and define a common research framework that includes the challenges of the city in the different countries of the participating universities.

City of Proximity was also intended to contribute to the main objective of the EELISA alliance - "transforming European higher education while strengthening the links between engineering and society" - and is in line with the approach the proposal has taken in this direction. Indeed, the fact that the selected call focuses on linking education and research allows the inclusion of a large number of universities in the consortium, without impacting the chances of success of the proposal.

Therefore, finally a first general framework of the City of Proximity proposal agreed with the different partners has been as follows:

The proposal aims to address the concept of the “City of Proximity” with a multidisciplinary approach, providing different points of view through each area of expertise and research of the participating entities. This multidisciplinary concept will be applied to existing "local lighthouse" projects in each country, such as Hangar 0 in France, a project carried out with the participation of the PSL university. The study of these lighthouses will help to define a methodology for the replicability of these spaces in other countries and cities. This learning can be accompanied by the participation of students and different stakeholders in summer schools or week-long workshops. This transversal approach will foster transdisciplinary learning, facilitating mutual exchange and bi-directional impacts, both in/for research and practice.

Below is the initial consortium proposal while waiting to define which entities need to be involved in the proposal. This part will be defined in the coming months through a survey and meetings with partners.

Figure 9-Initial consortium proposal

#EELISAConnectWorkshop:

Teaching and Learning Language Technologies in light of Generative AI

Workshop Report

The poster features a dark blue background with a glowing human head silhouette on the right, containing neural network-like patterns. The text is in yellow and white. The main title is at the top, followed by the dates '7-8TH', the month 'March 2024', and the location 'Madrid, Spain'. A QR code is in the bottom right corner, and a location pin icon is in the bottom left corner.

Teaching and Learning Language Technologies in light of Generative AI

7-8TH

March 2024

Madrid, Spain

Salón de Grados, Edificio A, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Telecomunicación (ETSIT)
Avenida Complutense, 30, Moncloa – Aravaca

SCAN OUR LOCATION

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1. MOTIVATION AND OBJECTIVES

There is a recent and avid burst in universal language models applied to translation, automatic text generation, text summarization, chatbots, speech and language recognition, speaker diarization and multi-speaker speech synthesis. One might have the feeling that only one technology can solve most language processing challenges. At the same time, some experts fear that there might be a hyper expectation on the capabilities of what is possible with these technologies today and about the knowledge that is needed to solve such challenges.

In terms of the training required by future developers of such technologies, there are many uncertainties on what they should learn and know about the relevant disciplines or fields that play a role in the next generation language technologies. What should an expert in linguistics, cognitive science, or psycholinguistics know about speech engineering, natural language processing, machine learning and/or artificial intelligence? Or the other way around, what should an expert in machine learning and/or artificial intelligence know about linguistics, cognitive science or psycholinguistics? In light of the recent advancements, one may think that none of them is needed anymore, or that rather all of them are needed for pushing forward science knowledge and technology in this area.

In the research world, we also observe a shift in the type and number of topics being discussed at conferences. Some years ago conferences were much more focused on and restricted to a few topics. Nowadays, conferences are seeking for research works that combine several technologies coming from disciplines apart. By way of example, when speech synthesis from text used to be an exclusive topic of Signal Processing Conferences, one would find conferences such as Interspeech and International Conference on Acoustic, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP). Nowadays, one can find papers on the same topic in conferences related to Learning Representations (ICLR), Machine Learning (ICML), Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS), Artificial Intelligence (AAAI), or Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD).

In many European countries, disciplines are still dealt with as “independent, self-contained areas” and the added value of interdisciplinary approaches is not always appreciated. For instance, in specialised technical universities such as the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, future engineers rarely are taught and learn about other disciplines outside their majors.

This workshop reflected on these matters and reached coherent conclusions on the following scientific areas:

- What is the (real) state of the art of language technologies? (strengths and weaknesses of large language models)

- What can language models teach us about the organisation of the brain and its language areas?
- What can linguistics and neuroscience teach us about creating better artificial models of language?
- What are the job opportunities and entrepreneur chances in this interdisciplinary topic?
- What are the teaching needs of future developers and users of these technologies?
- What are the different frameworks used by each EELISA members, the philosophy behind them, how they resonate with the needs of employers?
- Share experiences in terms of implementation (teaching and evaluations).
- The establishment of cooperation with Universities teaching complementary topics such as humanities faculties.

These action points are related with several EELISA SRAs:

- Social Sciences and Humanities, since the workshop discussed language technologies, linguistics, and the cooperation with universities with humanities faculties.
- Digitalisation, since the workshop tackled language technologies and related digital humanities issues.
- Culture, creativity and inclusive society, since we discussed the fair use and implications of technologies in society
- Health, since the workshop included discussions on neuroscience and the organisation of the brain and language areas.
- Artificial Intelligence, since the workshop discussed topics related to Natural Language Processing, Large Language Models, Language Technologies and Language Data Informatics.

Regarding the contributions, we would highlight the following aims:

- Contributions from people from the linguistic domain: linguists possess a deep understanding of language structures, semantics, and the cultural nuances that shape communication. In this workshop, linguists had the opportunity to share their insights into the complexities of human language and explore how this knowledge can be

harnessed to enhance AI applications, especially in natural language processing, sentiment analysis, and language generation. They also learnt how to use technology in their everyday life.

- **Contributions from Engineers:** engineers play a crucial role in developing cutting-edge technologies, including AI. Through this workshop, engineers gained valuable insights into linguistic theories and methodologies, enabling them to create more linguistically informed AI solutions. We envision engineers learning how linguistic expertise can contribute to the design of algorithms that better understand and respond to the subtleties of human language.
- **Finding synergies:** the workshop -provided a starting point for participants to collaboratively merge linguistic insights with AI capabilities in different ways, which could result in further collaboration, project proposals or shared papers. Main aim is fostering collaborations between linguists and engineers, where both expertises could result in disrupting advances.

2. ORGANISATION

6.2 2.1. Organisers from EELISA universities

This workshop was organised by three EELISA universities: Istanbul Technical University, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna and Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, whose representatives are as follows:

- **Gülşen Eryiğit from Istanbul Technical University:** She is an Assoc. Prof. at the Faculty of Computer and Informatics, Artificial Intelligence and Data Engineering, and the founder and manager of Natural Language Processing Group, Turkey’s the first and most rooted team working on Turkish language in the field of Natural Language Processing. She is the most cited academician for scientific publications in the field of Natural Language Processing in Turkey. She is currently acting as an ACL RR Senior Action Editor. She is also acting as the coordinator of ITU Natural Language Processing Research Group, the director of ITU TOMER (Turkish Teaching & Application Center), and the vice leader at EU UniDive Cost Action WG3 (Multilingual and Cross-Lingual Language Technology). Recently, she organised the Unidive WG3 Cost Action meeting at ITU on September 2023 with the participation of around 50 participants from Europe and associated countries.
- **Calogero Maria Oddo from Escuela Superiore Sant’Anna:** He has a Ph.D. in BioRobotics from Sant’Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA), Pisa, Italy, M.Sc. and

B.Sc. in Electronic Engineering from the University of Pisa, 1st and 2nd level degrees in Industrial and Information Engineering as a honours college student of SSSA (3% success rate), all with honours. He is Associate Professor (permanent position) of Bioengineering, he holds the national scientific qualification to be appointed as Full Professor, and he coordinates the Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory at The BioRobotics Institute of SSSA. He has over 70 international journal publications and 7 patents, and a track record in integrating biorobotics, neuroscience and industrial applications, with a core of research interests in touch science and engineering. He has 4000+ citations and 30 h-index in Scopus and he serves as member of the editorial board of scientific journals such as Scientific Reports edited by Springer Nature and the International Journal of Robotics Research. He has a growing portfolio of successful research grants, with scientific responsibilities within EU and National projects and industrial contracts. In 2023 he received the Feltrinelli Prize for young investigators in bioengineering from the Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei.

- **Elena Montiel Ponsoda from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid:** She is an Associate Professor at the Department of Applied Linguistics to Science and Technology at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (since 2012), and a member of the Ontology Engineering Group (since 2006). Her research lies at the intersection between terminologies and ontologies, and includes, among others, the following research areas: localisation and lexicalisation of ontologies (multilingualism), models to represent language resources as linked data, and Knowledge Graph injection in Large Language Models. She has participated in several international and national projects in these areas (NeOn, Monnet, MyLIDER, Pret-a-LLOD), and coordinated the EU Innovation Action Lynx. Since January 2023, she coordinates INESData, a research project on the creation of an incubator for Data Spaces in Spain with a particular interest in the role of language resources.

6.3 2.2. Local Organisers

Since the workshop was held in Madrid, several members of the UPM were involved as local organisers:

- **José Manuel Pardo:** full professor at the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) and Head of the Speech Technology Group (from 2021 Speech Technology and Machine Learning Group) since 1987. He leads a Group of 15 persons specialised in Speech Technology and Machine Learning, and his areas of expertise include technologies for speech-to-text and text-to-speech conversion, spoken language understanding,

speech databases and resources and basic science underlying speech communication processes.

- María Navas-Loro: postdoctoral researcher in Natural Language and Processing, focused on Large Language Models and how to apply them to Teaching, Ethics and Cognitive Sciences. Already participated in the I EELISA Conference as co-organizer of the session “AI in the University: challenges, opportunities and proposals - Ethos+Tekhne school: a new generation of AI researchers”.
- Patricia Martín-Chozas: postdoctoral researcher, focused on the intersection of Terminology, Semantic Web and Natural Language processing. Her current research interests are specifically oriented to the exploitation of terminological resources published as Linked Data to improve the performance of Large Language Models.

3. PARTICIPANTS

The workshop received participants from four EELISA universities. Since the workshop was held in Madrid, most of the attendees were from UPM.

Istanbul Technical University (İTÜ)

- Gülşen Eryiğit
- Tuğba Pamay Arslan
- Doğukan Arslan
- Fatih Bektaş
- Dilara Torunoğlu Selamet

Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna

- Andrea Bandini
- Sara Mazzucato
- Calogero Maria Oddo (remote connection)

Budapest University of Technology and Economics

- Csilla Szabó

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

- José Manuel Pardo Muñoz (THAU-UPM)

- Elena Montiel Ponsoda (OEG-UPM)
- Patricia Martín Chozas (OEG-UPM)
- Alejandra Remacha Delgado (OEG-UPM)
- María Navas Loro
- Pablo Calleja Ibáñez (OEG-UPM)
- Mariano Rico Almodóvar (OEG-UPM)
- Virginia Ramón Ferrer (OEG-UPM)
- Isam Diab Lozano (OEG-UPM)
- Ibai Guillén Pacho (OEG-UPM)
- Joel Pardo Ferrera (OEG-UPM)
- Socorro Bernardos Galindo (OEG-UPM)
- JiaYun (OEG-UPM)
- Shonal Fernandes

The workshop also counted with participants from non EELISA universities such as Universidad Complutense de Madrid, from companies such as Hermes Traducciones, and from the European Parliament.

- Victoria Escandell-Vidal (UCM)
- Ana María Fernández-Pampillón Cesteros (UCM)
- Marianela Fernández Trinidad (UCM)
- Lara Alonso Simón (UCM)
- Óscar García Sierra (UCM)
- Juan José Arevalillo Doval (Hermes Traducciones)
- Victoria Saura Montesinos (European Parliament)

4. AGENDA

The agenda was published online⁷ and as a leaflet, as exposed in Figure 1, which shows the schedule of the first day, and in Figure 2, which shows the schedule of the second day.

6.4 4.1. First Day (7th March)

The workshop was celebrated in the Telecommunications Engineering School from the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, better known as the Escuela Técnica Superior de

⁷ <https://oeg-upm.github.io/eelisa-It-workshop/>

Ingenieros de Telecomunicaciones. José Manuel Pardo is a full professor in this faculty, and for this reason he was in charge of the welcome speech together with Elena Montiel, both acting as local organisers.

The first presentation (Conference 1) was given by Gülşen Eryiğit, founder and manager of the Natural Language Processing Group at Istanbul Technical University. In her talk, she presented the research lines of this group, together with the varied projects in which the group has participated and which are still ongoing, such as the COST action UniDive. In addition, the presentation included an enlightening summary of the teaching activities in which the group members are involved in.

The speaker of the second talk (Conference 1) was, again, José Manuel Pardo, but this time he acted as head of the THAU⁸ research group, acronym for *Tecnología del Habla y Aprendizaje Automático* (Speech Technology and Machine Learning)-. Similarly, this talk was also intended to present the main research lines of this group, including European Projects such as ASTOUND.

After the coffee break (Conference 3), Elena Montiel Ponsoda and Patricia Martín Chozas, as members of the OEG (Ontology Engineering Group) from UPM, gave a similar presentation on the most recent research projects the group is involved in, in the areas of Terminology, Language Resources and NLP. Some of the projects presented were European projects such as Lynx and Prêt-à-LLOD, COST actions such as NexusLinguarum, ornational projects such as TeresIA and INESData.

The next presentation (Conference 4) was delivered by Andrea Bandini from the Interdisciplinary Research Center Health Science at Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna. The talk explored the impact of Artificial Intelligence in the assessment and communication methods of motor speech disorders, to ultimately improve the quality of life for individuals with such conditions.

The following talk (Conference 5) was held after the lunch break, and it was remotely given by Luis Fernando D'Haro, member of the THAU research group. The talk covered the complex and evolving field of AI consciousness. In this talk, the speaker exposed, amongst other elements, reasons in favour, such as the conversational abilities and general intelligence of

⁸ <https://blogs.upm.es/gthau/>

AI; reasons against , such as the lack of self awareness or their statistical nature, and future directions of this matter.

After this fifth conference, the PhD. Symposium took place. This session was intended for predoctoral students to share their works, and to identify collaboration opportunities. The students presented a varied range of research lines, as spelled out in the following:

1. Dilara Torunoğlu Selamet (ITÜ): Word Sense Disambiguation in Turkish
2. Doğukan Arslan (ITÜ): Idiom Corpora Construction via Large Language Models
3. Fatih Bektaş (ITÜ): The Use of NLP in Turkish Language Education
4. Tuğba Pamay Arslan (ITÜ): End-to-End Turkish Coreference Resolution
5. Sara Mazzucato (SSSUP): Predictive models in medicine from Natural Language Processing based Electronic Health Records structuring
6. Ibai Guillén Pacho (UPM): Detecting Causes of Discourse Evolution
7. Isam Diab Lozano (UPM): An Artificial Intelligence based Framework to Automatically Adapt Short Stories in Spanish into Easier and Accessible Versions
8. Joel Pardo Ferrera (UPM): Automatic Knowledge Graph Creation from Text in the Medical Domain
9. Virginia Ramón Ferrer (UPM): Ontological support for Knowledge Graph Question Answering

Finally, the last conference of the day (Conference 6) was given by Calogero Maria Oddo, as an Associate Professor of the Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna and head of the Neuro-Robotic Touch Laboratory at The BioRobotics Institute. In his talk, Calogero Maria Oddo presented his university and gave an overview of the main research topics pursued at his Institute.

Day 1 - 7th March

09:00-09:30

Opening Welcoming Coffee

09:30-10:15

Conference 1: Research on NLP at ITU

Gülşen Eryiğit (ITU)

10:15-11:00

Conference 2: Research on Language Technologies at THAU (UPM)

José Manuel Pardo (THAU-UPM)

11:00-11:30

Coffee break

11:30-12:15

Conference 3: Research on NLP and LLOD at OEG (UPM)

Elena Montiel Ponsoda and Patricia Martín Chozas (OEG-UPM)

12:15-13:00

Conference 4: AI applications in motor speech disorders:
advancing assessment and facilitating communication

Andrea Bandini (SSSUP)

13:00-14:00

Lunch break

14:00-14:45

Conference 5: AI Chatbots: capabilities, challenges and
the race for consciousness

Luis Fernando D'Haro (THAU-UPM)

14:45-15:45

PhD. Symposium: Lightning talks by PhD. students

15:45-16:15

Coffee break

16:15-17:00

Conference 6: Research at SSSUP

Calogero Maria Oddo (SSSUP)

Figure 1. Agenda of the first day.

6.5 4.2. Second Day (8th March)

The second session of the workshop was opened by a group of invited speakers from Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM), one of the most important universities in Spain and with a long history of collaboration with Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. This talk (Conference 1) covered several aspects related to the topics of the workshop. In the first place, Victoria Escandell-Vidal, full professor at UCM, described the Master's program in Linguistics and Technologies, in which UPM collaborates. The second talk was given by Ana María Fernández-Pampillón Cesteros, Associate Professor at UPM, who presented the project ROBOT-TALK, whose aim is to recognize if a text has been created by a Generative AI. Afterwards, Lara Alonso Simón, predoctoral student, presented her research on the identification of texts generated by robots in Spanish. Finally, Oscar García Sierra, also a predoctoral researcher at UCM, presented his work entitled *A proposal for subword segmentation to improve the effectiveness of generative text language models in Spanish*.

The following conference (Conference 2) was delivered by Tuğba Pamay Arslan, who presented the different approaches to teach NLP at ITÜ. The teaching approaches are organised in three levels: undergraduate courses (including NLP fundamentals, statistical approaches and LLMs), Master courses (including annotation of linguistic structures and different NLP applications) and PhD. courses (including words and contextual representations).

After the coffee break, the next conference (Conference 3) was given by Pablo Calleja and María Navas Loro, both assistant professors at UPM. The talk was focused on the Master's Program in Artificial Intelligence at UPM, with a special focus on NLP subjects that, apart from fundamentals of NLP and LLMs, includes specific notions on hardware requirements such as GPUs.

The last conference (Conference 4) of the workshop was offered by Csilla Szabó, head of the Centre of Modern Languages at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, who gave a talk entitled *Using AI tools in teaching language and linguistic mediation (translation and interpreting); upgrading digital skills for trainees and trainers*. The presentation included reflections on how to take benefit from AI application on the translation business.

The networking time started during the lunch break and had a duration of two hours. During this session, participants from different universities engaged in discussions, bridging interdisciplinary boundaries and exploring the intersections of their research lines. Each

participant brought a unique perspective, valuable for forging connections and fostering innovation across academic disciplines.

The workshop closed with a discussion and series of concluding remarks reported in the next section.

Day 2 - 8th March

09:30-10:15

Conference 1:

- 1) Master's Program in Linguistics and Technologies UCM-UPM
- 2) Recognising the Origin of roBOTic Texts. Task Automatisation and Linguistic Knowledge (ROBOT-TALK)
- 3) Identifying texts generated by robots in Spanish
- 4) A proposal for subword segmentation to improve the effectiveness of Generative Text Language Models in Spanish

- 1) Victoria Escandell-Vidal (UCM)
- 2) Ana María Fernández-Pampillón Cesteros (UCM) and Marianela Fernández Trinidad (UCM)
- 3) Lara Alonso Simón (UCM)
- 4) Óscar García Sierra (UCM)

10:15-11:00

Conference 2: Teaching NLP at ITU

Tuğba Pamay Arslan (ITU)

11:00-11:30

Coffee break

11:30-12:15

Conference 3: Master's Program in Artificial Intelligence UPM

Pablo Calleja and Mariano Rico (OEG-UPM)

12:15-13:00

Conference 4: Using AI tools in teaching language and linguistic mediation (translation and interpreting); upgrading digital skills for trainees and trainers

Csilla Szabó (BME)

13:00-14:00

Lunch break

14:00-15:00

Networking time

15:00-15:30

Concluding Remarks

Figure 2. Agenda of the second day.

5. MAIN OUTCOMES

The workshop provided a valuable opportunity to understand the participants capabilities and shared interests. It served as a forum for researchers to foster a deeper understanding of the potential synergies between institutions.

The workshop broadened perspectives and facilitated connections with experts in different fields of Natural Language Processing (NLP). One of these areas is translation. Emphasising the value of computer-assisted translation tools (CAT), participants noted the growing demand for translation services and the need for accurate datasets. The conversation underscored the symbiotic relationship between linguists and NLP experts, highlighting the necessity for interdisciplinary collaboration. One of the main conclusions in this line is that CAT tools should not be perceived as a foe but a friend.

In this regard, some important questions were raised, such as if the language translation sector was in danger. The answer from translation professionals from the industry was negative, in fact, they stated that the sector is growing, since thanks to the revolution of language technologies, there is much more content needed for translation than before. Another note on this field designates that the figure of translation experts is changing. In fact, the translation services using language tools and human post edition are much cheaper now than in previous years, and many companies do not need translators but plain linguists.

On the other hand, in the field of psycholinguistics, discussions were insightful, emphasising the importance of interdisciplinary connections, particularly in neurophysiology and speech and language studies, exploring the links between psychological disorders and physiological diseases. In this regard, collaboration with sign language specialists yielded positive experiences, addressing the importance of understanding available tools in language translation.

Another interesting question was raised regarding the need of computer scientists and NLP experts of linguistic studies. Some discussions on this matter concluded that there is a need of, at least, collaboration, since the gold standards used to evaluate NLP approaches need for expert revision.

In general, the workshop was considered a great success, since it was very convenient to know the capabilities of the participants and the common interests. Looking ahead, some possibilities were opened about professor exchanges within EELISA community and the feasibility of organising a summer school, with funding secured for future EELISA activities following its renewal.

6. PICTURES FROM THE WORKSHOP

EURO

European University

**Ways of Water: Ethical, Socio-Economic,
Environmental, and Engineering Perspectives on
Riverine and Oceanic Commons**

The workshop: program and details

This two-day conference was organized by and held at Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, in cooperation with EELISA Partners Scuola Superiore Normale, Université Paris Sciences et Lettres, and Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem. It focused on two separate yet very interconnected iterations of water: rivers and oceans. We explored the ways these waters are used and understood and can be used and understood in the future. Who owns water? Adjacent countries, all of humanity, or nature itself?

After an initial presentation and brainstorming session, we spent most of the time to gather ideas for potential collaborations. Our gathered ideas include but are not limited to:

Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies - SSSA

1. Genealogy / Ontology of Water - How is water defined and has been used over centuries and in the present time? Could we imagine innovative (even restrictive) usages of water resources?
2. Land and politics, or: Territorial specificity and the linkage with (innovative) political legitimations of water areas / new forms of subjectivity
3. Behavioural Change/Collective Action Problem/Agency - What kind of beliefs do people have about water? What collective action problems arise in relation to water? What kind of agents are involved? A specific focus on specific areas of the world
4. Long-term missions for environmental monitoring of marine ecosystem; Exploration and monitoring with Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs); AUV swarms
5. Development of bio-inspired and biomimetic robots as efficient and non-invasive solutions to explore waters; Biosensing: Exploit living organisms to extract environmental parameters related to the ecosystem health
6. Infrastructures / Institutions - Technological Acceptance/Role of Tech?
7. Justice, Water ethics, Inequalities, and Intergenerational Issues

Scuola Normale Superiore - SNS

1. Hydropolitics and Conflicts on water, 'ontological' struggles (more than human mobilizations) regarding water basins and/or urban governance of water, from sociological/political theory perspective
2. Handling of water as global commons, with special reference to transnational governance from political/regulatory perspective
3. Role of expertise involved in water management also regarding novel technologies, sociological inquiry
4. Alternative value practices (non-monetary valuation, orders of worth, moral economies, alternative innovation approaches, participatory etc., prefigurative practices)

Institut Jean Nicod - PSL/EHESS

1. Human and non-human (technology/other species)/more-than-human Relations (philosophical and sociological insights)
2. Behavioural Change/Collective Action Problem (from a cognitivist perspective)
3. Role of expertise involved in water management also regarding novel technologies, sociological inquiry
4. Water in urban and domestic contexts (Roberto)
5. Representations of water: cognitive distance
6. Micro-management of domestic water

Budapest University of Technology and Economics - BME

1. Explore individual perceptions of water and determinants of behaviour towards water; best ways to increase awareness, role of education; inter-generational knowledge transfer
2. Explore the role of stakeholders: consumers, businesses, different levels of government, agents of water management, local communities, young generations
3. Understand conflicting uses of water and how to resolve water conflicts; short vs. long term objectives
4. Methods for valuing non-market values of water, socio-cultural aspects of water
5. Examine the interrelations among supply, demand, prices and the effects of policy on these
6. Water policy, diplomacy and governance: European, country, regional and local levels: conflicts and harmonisation

Based on these collections, we gathered information to continue our collaboration in the future. The plan is to meet in early July to explore six possible avenues for EU Horizon and other calls. These include proposals on:

1. [New European Bauhaus](#)
2. [Blue Sustainability/Economy](#)
3. [Next generation low-emission, climate-resilient pathways and NDCs for a future aligned with the Paris Agreement](#)
4. [Resilient, inclusive, healthy and green rural, coastal and urban communities](#)
5. [Integration of socio-ecological models into the Digital Twin Ocean](#)
6. [Interreg Central Europe](#).

We divided the group by expertise and research interest and ask them to explore the feasibility and timing of each call, including title and link as well as the rationale of the call, any possible consortium, links to our shared [Brainstorm Document](#), as well as a brief SWOT Analysis with the pros and cons.

SWOT Analysis EELISA Workshop

Ways of Water: Ethical, Socio-Economic, Environmental, and Engineering Perspectives on Riverine and Oceanic Commons

Strengths:

1. International participants: The workshop attracted participants from various countries, enhancing its diversity and bringing together a wide range of perspectives and experiences.
2. Availability and good faith: The participants demonstrated a strong willingness to engage and contribute, fostering an atmosphere of openness and collaboration.
3. Spontaneous academics from the EELISA university network: The presence of academics from the EELISA university network added depth and expertise to the discussions, enriching the overall content of the workshop.
4. Networking opportunities: The workshop facilitated the establishment of new connections and friendships, allowing for potential future collaborations and partnerships.
5. Establishment of Sant'Anna as a valuable host: Both academic and administrative resources have shown to be up to the task of providing adequate conference infrastructure.
6. Dynamically structured form: The workshop's flexible structure enabled open brainstorming sessions, encouraging participants to freely exchange ideas and explore different perspectives.
7. Wide-reaching topics: The workshop's reach was intentionally broad to account for as many different perspectives and overlaps as possible.

Weaknesses:

1. Lack of content clarity: The quick organization of the workshop resulted in a somewhat ambiguous content structure, leaving the specific topics up in the air. This ambiguity may have affected the overall focus and cohesiveness of the discussions.
2. Time-consuming introductions: The considerable time invested in self-introductions slowed down the pace of the workshop, potentially limiting the time available for more substantive discussions and activities. Nevertheless, this was also due to the high number of interested participants and will, in the long run, likely be seen as a strength.

Opportunities:

1. Solid collaborations for the future: The extensive time dedicated to getting to know the participants allowed for the establishment of clear lines of communication and the identification of potential collaboration opportunities. These connections can serve as a foundation for future joint projects and initiatives.
2. In-depth exploration of topics: The decision to hold a follow-up call in early July presents an opportunity to delve deeper into the identified overlapping topics. This additional time will allow for a more comprehensive examination of specific areas and facilitate a more in-depth understanding of the subject matter.

Threats:

1. Potential lack of focus: Without a clearer structure or defined focus, the workshop may risk losing sight of specific objectives and fail to achieve tangible outcomes.
2. Time constraints: The need to cover the topics in more detail during the upcoming call may pose a challenge due to limited time availability. It is crucial to ensure that sufficient time is allocated to each topic to avoid rushing through important discussions.

Overall, the "Ways of Water" workshop provided a valuable platform for interdisciplinary exchange and networking among international participants. Many of the weaknesses can be also seen as strengths, as well as vice-versa. While the quick organization and lack of content clarity posed challenges, the workshop's positive aspects, such as the availability of participants, the establishment of collaborations, and the open brainstorming sessions, create a promising foundation for future endeavors. By addressing the weaknesses and capitalizing on the opportunities, the workshop can progress towards achieving its goals and fostering meaningful advancements within the collaborative framework.

ATTENDANCE LIST

#	Name	Partner	12.06. afternoon	13.06. morning	13.06. afternoon
1	Alberto Pirni	SSSA	x	x	x
2	Cesare Stefanini	SSSA	x		
3	Luigi Pelizzoni	SNS	x	x	x
4	Diana Piroli	SSSA	x	x	x
5	Laura Marcon	SSSA	x	x	x
6	Martina Zanetti	SSSA	x	x	x
7	Binyam Mekonnen Adera	SSSA	x	x	x
8	Andebet Hailu Assefa	SSSA	x	x	x
9	Donato Romano	SSSA		x	
10	Gianluca Manduca	SSSA	x	x	x
11	Alessandro Chiessi	SSSA	x	x	x
12	Jade Nijman	PSL	x	x	x
13	Evan Josselin	PSL	x	x	x
14	Gyula Zilahy	BME	x	x	x
15	Ádám Csuvár	BME	x	x	x
16	Alex Putzer	SSSA	x	x	x
17	Annamária Orbán	BME	x	x	x
18	Roberto Casati	PSL	x	x	x
19	Noémi Nagypál Csigéné	BME	x	x	x

New Horizons

supported by **EELISA innoCORE**

Partnerships for circularity-driven
sustainability research and innovation

Date: April 17-19, 2024

Place: İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi (ITU), Faculty of Architecture, Taşkışla Campus, Harbiye Mah. Taşkışla Cad. No. 2, 34367, Şişli, İstanbul, Türkiye

Conduct: In person

Participation: Upon invitation only, from mostly EELISA member universities, and some non-EELISA foreign and local institutions including universities, public authorities, private sector, and NGOs

The workshop, New Horizons, had two primary aims. The first aim was to create an environment dedicated to research, innovation, and inclusion in the circular economy, from which strategic approaches and project ideas emerge to advance and fortify the research and innovation visions of EELISA. This initiative encompasses activities such as identifying funding opportunities, imparting research methodologies, fostering a culture of innovation, and generating ideas and proposals for research projects. Parallel to the first aim, the second aim was to follow up on the ongoing joint project proposal collaborations from the Circular EELISA Community's Circular Models workshop supported by the EELISA InnoCORE project's first EELISA Connect call and coordinated by UPM in Madrid in July 2023.

*Aligned with three strategic research areas (SRAs) of EELISA, the workshop intertwined with the domains of **Culture, Creativity, and Inclusive Society**, promoting sustainable ideas and disseminating best practices, **Advanced Material Science and Engineering**, focusing on optimization models and circular materials manufacturing for resource-efficient usage, and **Climate Energy and Mobility**, prioritizing clean and sustainable energy production and storage.*

Over two days, the participants will collaborate to explore joint research projects primarily, and also other potential joint research endeavors, such as EELISA activities, and joint publications. In total, New Horizons hosted 38 participants from 6 countries, 8 universities, and one public institution. The participants mostly comprised of professors and researchers from EELISA member universities and also involved one professor

from a non-EELISA university, three PhD students, three university administrative experts of international projects, and three experts from the local metropolitan municipality.

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1. PARTICIPANT LIST

Table 1: Participant List

#	FULL NAME	INSTITUTION	ATTANDANCE		
			17.04.2024	18.04.2024	19.04.2024
1	Justo Garcia Navarro	UPM	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Eutiquio Gallego Vazquez	UPM	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	Jaime Carlos Gálvez Ruiz	UPM	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Diana Robescu	NUSTPB	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Corina Ionela Dumitrescu	NUSTPB	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Georgiana Dunca	NUSTPB	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Tiziana Iannuzzi	SSSA	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Alessio Novi	SSSA	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	Valentine Perrin	ENPC	Yes	Yes	No
10	Quentin Lagache	ENPC	Yes	Yes	No
11	Cécile Reynaud	PSL	Yes	Yes	Yes
12	Abdelkader Slifi	PSL	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	Simon Timothy Cerqua	ZHAW	Yes	Yes	Yes
14	Tetiana Kaufmann	ZHAW	Yes	Yes	Yes
15	Joachim Brötz	TUDa	Yes	Yes	Yes
16	Berfin Sönmez	IMM	Yes	Yes	No
17	Ece Tümer	IMM	No	Yes	No
18	Ümit Sezgi Pişkin	IMM	No	Yes	Yes
19	İmge Akçakaya Waite	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
20	Birgül Çolakoğlu	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
21	Çiğdem Kaya	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
22	Derya Güleç Özer	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
23	Ayşegül Akçay Kavakoğlu	ITU	No	Yes	Yes
24	Eda Yücesoy	ITU	No	Yes	Yes
25	Zeynep Günay	ITU	No	No	No
26	Fatih Terzi	ITU	Yes	Yes	No
27	Kerem Koramaz	ITU	No	No	No
28	Şence Türk	ITU	Yes	Yes	No
29	Gülden Demet Oruç Ertekin	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
30	Emrah Acar	ITU	No	No	No
31	Başak Tiniş	ITU	Yes	No	No
32	Didem Özgür	ITU	Yes	Yes	No
33	Merve Savaşeri	ITU	Yes	Yes	No
34	Nergis Aşar	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
35	Cihan Mert Sabah	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
36	Gamze Kazancı Altınok	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
37	Nursefa Keskin	ITU	No	No	No
38	Hüseyin Özdemir	ITU	Yes	No	No
TOTAL			30	32	24

2. MEETING AGENDA

2.1. AGENDA

New Horizons

Partnerships for circularity-driven
sustainability research and innovation

April 17-19, 2024

PROGRAM

Wednesday, April 17th

9:00 - 9:30

Welcome coffee

9:30 - 11:00

Opening session: Keynote speakers

- Welcome
Prof. Lütfiye Durak Ata, Vice Rector, ITU
Prof. Mehmet Küçükmehtemoğlu, Dean of Faculty of Architecture, ITU
- A journey of circularity & structure of the workshop
Assoc. Prof. İmge Akçakaya Waite, ITU
- Circular EELISA Community and its contributions
to the theme of the circular economy
Prof. Justo Garcia Navarro, UPM
- The EELISA ecosystem as an exemplary European University initiative
Prof. Diana Robescu, UNSTPB
- EU funding schemes and upcoming opportunities
ITU Office of the Dean of Research, International Projects Department

11:00 - 11:30

Coffee break

11:30 - 13:00

Introductory panel: Collaboration ecosystem

- In this panel, academics and researchers from EELISA universities and non-EELISA participants will have the opportunity to share their lines of research, fields of interest, and relevant ongoing projects in the field of circular economy. The aim is to foster collaboration, promote the generation of synergies and explore opportunities to strengthen research and innovation.
- Interactive debate and questions from the audience

13:00 - 14:00

Lunch

14:00 - 15:30

Idea initiation panel 1: Project proposals

- The participants will be able to present challenges or projects that they would like to develop and to which they invite the rest of the attendees (proposals that are in the ideation phase and in the search for partners)
- Comments and feedback from other academics, researchers, and other partners

15:30 - 16:00

Coffee break

16:00 - 17:30

Idea initiation panel 2: Project proposals

- Continuation of presentation of proposal ideas
- Comments and feedback from other academics, researchers, and other partners
- Forming of the work groups

17:30 - 18:30

Thematic roundtables

- Follow up on the ongoing joint project proposal collaborations from the Circular Models workshop of July 2023

19:30

Dinner & networking

New Horizons

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Thursday, April 18th

9:00 - 11:00

Interactive workshop: Setting the course

- Interactive sessions where participants work in groups to address specific challenges
- Exploration of methodologies, tools and practical approaches to promote circularity in different contexts
- Selection of ideas for the proposal development phase

11:00 - 11:30

Coffee break

11:30 - 13:00

Thematic discussion 1: Select EELISA InnoCORE Strategic Research Areas and corresponding funding opportunities

- Culture, creativity, and inclusive society
- Advanced materials science and engineering
- Climate energy and mobility

13:00 - 14:00

Lunch

14:00 - 15:30

Thematic discussion 2: Furthering the proposals

- The working groups will make a brief description of the problem or challenges, type of proposal selected, competitive call, objectives of the proposal and possible partners

15:30 - 16:00

Coffee break

16:00 - 17:30

Thematic discussion 3: Furthering the proposals

- Continuation and conclusion

17:30 - 18:30

Thematic roundtables

- Follow up on the ongoing joint project proposal collaborations from the Circular Models workshop of July 2023

19:30

Dinner & networking

New Horizons

Partnerships for circularity-driven
sustainability research and innovation

April 17-19, 2024

Friday, April 19th

9:00 - 10:00

Thematic roundtables

· Follow up on the ongoing and emerging joint project proposal collaborations

10:00 - 10:30

Coffee break

10:30 - 11:30

Presentation of proposals and collaborations

· Sessions dedicated to the presentation and review of proposals for collaborative research projects
· Comments and feedback from other academics, researchers, and other partners

11:30 - 12:30

Closing session: Conclusions and next steps

· Recap of the main highlights and conclusions of the workshop
· Planning of next steps and recommendations to continue workin and for future collaborations

13:00 - 15:00

Lunch & technical field trip: Blue, green, and grey infrastructures of the Bosphorus, Istanbul

* Dinners are not covered by the workshop.

2.1.1. DAY 1: 17TH APRIL, 2024

Day started with welcome coffee followed by the speeches of keynote speakers in the opening session. In his speech, Mehmet Küçükmehtetoğlu, the Dean of Faculty of Architecture of Istanbul Technical University welcomed all the participants. Imge Akçakaya Waite, the head of organization, summarized previous organization conducted within the circular eelisa community. Further she explained the structure of the workshop. The opening session continued with the presentation of Justo García-Navarro, coordinator of circular Eelisa community. He highlighted the mission of Circular Eelisa community, presented university and industry partners while also summarizing some of the present and future projects of the community.

The next presentation of the session was conducted by Diana Robescu. She informed participants about Eelisa, its context, vision, commitment, and educational offers. The last presentation of opening sessions was made by Didem Özgür from Projects and commercialization Management Office, International Projects Unit of ITU. She gave detailed information of Potential Calls of Horizon Europe and Erasmus + Programs.

The day continued with the introductory panel. In this panel, academics and researchers from EELISA universities and non-EELISA participants will have the opportunity to share their lines of research, fields of interest, and relevant ongoing projects in the field of circular economy. The aim is to foster collaboration, promote the generation of synergies and explore opportunities to strengthen research and innovation.

Table 2: Introductory panel presentations

#	Presentation	Presenter	Institution	Research Topics / Keywords
1	About Me	Justo Garcia Navarro	UPM	Sustainability and circular economy in construction
2	Some of the ITU participants' profiles	İmge Akçakaya Waite	ITU	Misc.
3	Institute of Materials and Process Engineering (IMPE) / Laboratory of Adhesives and Polymer Materials	Simon Timothy Cerqua	ZHAW	Materials, process Engineering; chemistry
4	BIPREE Research Group	Eutiquio Gallego Vazquez	UPM	Numerical modelling; Biomass materials
5	Construction and Building Materials: Sustainability & Durability	Jaime Carlos Gálvez Ruiz	UPM	Sustainability of materials; Durability; Artificial intelligence applied to sustainability
6	National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest	Diana Robescu	NUSTPB	Circular economy in energy; Water and carbon footprint; Water and waste water treatment
7	Design Thinking	Valentine Perrin	ENPC	Design; Design thinking; Design fiction;

				Sustainable design; Project management; Collaborative workshops
8	Priorities for the Development of Smart Cities	Berfin Sönmez	IMM	Urban logistics; Digital twin; Digital transformation; Smart application
9	Sustainability Management Laboratory SuM Lab	Alessio Novi	SSSA	Environmental management; Circular economy management
10	ZHAW School of Life Sciences and Facility Management, Institute of Natural Resource Sciences	Tetiana Kaufmann	ZHAW	Educational projects; MSc. Circular Economy Management
11	Darmstadt- city of the future	Joachim Brötz	TUDa	Circular materials
12	About Me	Cécile Reynaud	PSL	Musicology; Teaching history

The afternoon sessions focused on idea initiation panels. Participants presented project proposals that they would like to develop and to which they invite the rest of the attendees. Project proposals were presented by following three thematic groups: Social sciences-humanities; Engineering-technical issues; Education. During the session other academics, researchers and other partners were welcomed to comment and give their feedbacks. In total 11 projects were proposed, 4 related to Technical / Engineering Thematic group, 2 Social Sciences and Humanities thematic group and 5 Education thematic group.

Table 3: Proposed research projects

#	Proposal	Responsible	Institution	Thematic Groups
1	Improvement of handling equipment used for biomass residues employed for combustion	Eutiquio Gallego	UPM	Technical / Engineering
2	Improving agricultural infrastructures to avoid depopulation in rural areas	Eutiquio Gallego	UPM	Technical / Engineering
3	Three scenarios for the use and production of basalt in the construction sector in the industrial symbiosis perspective	Tiziana Iannuzzi	SSSA	Technical / Engineering
4	Strengthening circular economy and industrial symbiosis initiatives within Europe	Alessio Novi	SSSA	Technical / Engineering
5	Reuse of architectural heritage elements / spolia	Derya Güleç Özer	ITU	Social sciences-Humanities
6	Planning and designing urban areas with nature: Towards a regenerative urbanism	Eda Yücesoy	ITU	Social sciences-Humanities
7	Design for circular futures	Çiğdem Kaya	ITU	Education
8	EELISA joint degree programs: MSc and PhD	Eutiquio Gallego Vazquez / Justo Garcia Navarro	UPM	Education

9	EELISA double degree program: ZHAW's MSc in CE Management	Tetiana Kaufmann	ZHAW	Education
10	The future of mobility in Higher Education and Research	Quentin Lagache	ENPC	Education
11	Webinar series for students, professors, researchers	Simon Timothy Cerqua	ZHAW	Education

2.1.2. DAY 2: 18TH APRIL, 2024

The second day of the workshop began with Interactive workshop to set the course. The proposed project ideas are listed and addressed one by one and matched with the institution that were interested.

Theme	Proposed Project	Proposed by	Institution	ITU	UPM	UNSTPB	SSSA	ENPC	PSL	ZHAW	TUDa	IMM
Technical / Engineering	Improvement of handling equipment used for biomass residues employed for combustion	Eutiquio Gallego	UPM		X	X	X			X		
Technical / Engineering	Improving agricultural infrastructures to avoid depopulation in rural areas	Eutiquio Gallego	UPM	X	X	X	X					X
Technical / Engineering	Three scenarios for the use and production of basalt in the construction sector in the industrial symbiosis perspective	Tiziana Iannuzzi	SSSA				X					
Technical / Engineering	Strengthening circular economy and industrial symbiosis initiatives within Europe	Alessio Novi	SSSA	X	X	X	X			X	X	
Social sciences- Humanities	Reuse of architectural heritage elements / spolia	Derya Güleç Özer	ITU	X	X				X			
Social sciences- Humanities	Planning and designing urban areas with nature: Towards a regenerative urbanism	Eda Yücesoy	ITU	X	X	X			X			X
Education	Design for circular futures	Çiğdem Kaya	ITU	X	X	X		X				
Education	EELISA joint degree programs: MSc and PhD	Eutiquio Gallego Vazquez / Justo Garcia Navarro	UPM	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Education	EELISA double degree program: ZHAW's MSc in CE Management	Tetiana Kaufmann	ZHAW	X	X	X			X	X		

Education	The future of mobility in Higher Education and Research	Quentin Lagache	ENPC	X	X	X		X	X	X		
Education	Webinar series for students, professors, researchers	Simon Timothy Cerqua	ZHAW	X	X	X	X			X		

Following the project-institution pair-ups, representatives of each institution distributed to the thematic working groups. Within each thematic working group 11 project topics are further elaborated. The day concluded with the presentations of each thematic working groups. The presenters explained the projects, describe the problems or challenges. Participants gave feedbacks. The representatives of Projects and commercialization Management Office, International Projects Unit of ITU proposed funding calls that projects can be suitable for.

2.1.3. **DAY 3: 19TH APRIL 2024**

The third day of the workshop started with thematic roundtables. Working groups focused on maturing the project proposals and designing the timeplan for the future. The day continued with the presentation of the proposals. The comments and feedbacks of the participants were welcomed. Closing session took place after the final presentations. The closing session included the recap of the proposals, highlights and results of the workshop. The necessity next steps to further improve and realize the projects were discussed.

The day and the workshop ended with the technical field trip of the Bosphorus that focuses on the blue, green and grey infrastructure of Istanbul.

The Projects

Project-2: Improving agricultural infrastructures to avoid depopulation in rural areas

The importance of focusing on the rural population was emphasized. It was stated that different areas and countries should be taken into consideration. It was emphasized that the selection of case areas is very important for the project. An example from Spain was already chosen for the project. It was stated that a second project area could be chosen from Turkey. The suitability of the Digital Europe fund to fund the project was discussed. It was stated that the application deadline for the said fund was at the end of May, so the preparation process should be rapid. However, it was stated that the demand for the Digital Europe fund is not as high as Horizon Europe, so the chance of receiving funding is higher.

Project-4: Strengthening circular economy and industrial symbiosis initiatives within Europe

The project currently has partners from four countries: Romania, Spain, Italy and Germany. Identifying a specific industry sector and categorizing the types of waste materials were mentioned as essential steps. It was planned to incorporate various industrial elements from each country to create diverse components. The aims of this project mentioned to align with the priorities of the Horizon Europe program. Further it was mentioned that the project can seek support from the LIFE program.

Project-5: Reuse of architectural heritage elements / spolia

The project participants worked on addressing logistical considerations such as location arrangements. Their main focus stated to be identifying appropriate call for proposals, similar to those provided by Digital Europe, with a specific emphasis on calls related to heritage elements. Their search was guided by keywords such as documentation, collaboration, and identifying potential partners.

Project-6: Planning and designing urban areas with nature: Towards a regenerative urbanism

Discussions were held on the DUT project (driving urban transition partnership), which encompasses circular economy, positive energy, and the concept of the 15-minute city. DUT is divided into these three branches. It was stated that discussing possible projects might be beneficial. Participants from Madrid, Paris, Bucharest, ITU (Istanbul Technical University), and IMM (Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality) were generally interested in observing practices. The application deadline was expected to be on late November and April. They suggested conducting the work online, followed by each team working with their own.

Project-7: Design for circular futures

They emphasize the significance of collective imagination and is investigating methods for co-designing studio work. Their goal is to develop a fresh urban concept through design fiction, collaborating with d-design to establish a unified curriculum. They are considering utilizing **Jean Monnet calls** as a potential platform for proposals and foresee the potential for joint masters programs to offer opportunities for other projects. They've already submitted applications for the **EELISA Joint-Community Calls**, involving multiple institutions. Moreover, they are exploring innovative techniques like design thinking models and fictional narratives.

Project-8: EELISA joint degree programs: MSc and PhD

Regarding **joint degrees**, there are three possible funding actions to integrate new techniques, which involve three different steps: 1- We are considering making an immediate application in the first meeting. 2- We need to see how they can fit to apply for a logical master proposal. Additionally, **joint master degrees** are very important.

There are three potential funding options: 1- Erasmus Mundus, 2- Jean Monnet, which might function as a public-oriented program like a summer or evening school, with extra compensation for instructors if it becomes Jean Monnet. 3- The third option is EELISA, but it's unlikely to offer funding support.

Project-9: EELISA double degree program: ZHAW's MSc in CE Management

Double master degrees - ELISA joint call - Design thinking can be practical but also bring innovation - Each student desires two diplomas because of this - We should include this. A suitable syllabus will be prepared - This way, a more solid and strong proposal can be submitted - Perhaps it could be something like the Erasmus fund and be utilized.

Project-10: The future of mobility in Higher Education and Research

Master degree- mobility-design thinking experiment- future of mobility- to be part of new technic of master degrees- **Different from 8 and 9 projects. They need to discuss Master degree programme.** The primary objective of this program is to secure funding.

2.2. PRINCIPAL OBJECTIVES ACHIEVED

The New Horizon workshop was held with the participation of 8 universities and one municipality. The diversity in the research fields of the participating universities and departments ensured that the project proposals were also diverse. 11 projects were proposed within the scope of the workshop. The mentioned 11 projects were categorized under 3 thematic groups. Accordingly, 3 working groups were formed. The presence of representatives from different universities in the working groups ensured the representation of the member universities and also ensured the constant presence of different perspectives.

The diversity of universities involved in the projects has also enabled collaboration and strengthening of connections between universities, which are among the main objectives of EELISA and EELISA innoCORE.

In line with the workshop proposal submitted to EELISA innoCORE's second EELISA Connect call in November 2023, the anticipated outcomes of New Horizons were met as follows:

- **Identification of research opportunities:** The workshop provided a dynamic environment for participants to delve into and discuss experiences, challenges, and research opportunities within the realm of the circular economy, emphasizing social, citizenship, and industrial dimensions from an inclusive perspective. This collaborative exploration aimed to uncover promising research areas, defining specific topics, and leveraging knowledge and infrastructure to collectively address shared challenges.
- **Generation of joint research project ideas and proposals:** Facilitating an exchange of knowledge, experiences, and innovative approaches, the workshop became a fertile ground for generating research project ideas aligned with the three EELISA Strategic Research Areas. Participants shared insights that led to the creation of original and viable ideas for collaborative research endeavors. Drawing on the support and feedback from fellow academics, researchers, sector representatives and students, participants were able to refine their project ideas and craft robust proposals that align with the requisites of European funding calls or other potential funding sources.
- **Further enhancement of ongoing project ideas and/or proposals from the former EELISA Connect workshop, Circular Models:** In addition to the primary aim of generating new joint research ventures, as indicated in the second aim of the workshop mentioned above, the workshop intended to act as a follow-up opportunity for the ideas generated during the first EELISA Connect workshop of the Circular EELISA Community held in Madrid in July 2023. This was to ensure that those ideas are further elaborated and matched with possible new consortiums and administrative decisions.
- **Promotion of inter-university and university-industry collaborations:** An integral objective was to promote the EELISA Alliance among a diverse spectrum of stakeholders, including students, researchers, academics, companies, and partners. Through vibrant idea exchange between participating institutions, the workshop fostered the establishment of research networks, laying the foundation for joint research projects, and expansion of the Circular EELISA Community.
- **Capacity building for research and innovation:** Beyond project ideation, the workshop housed capacity-building and training activities encompassing research methodologies, innovation techniques, and other pertinent aspects of the circular economy. These activities

aimed to enhance the research and innovation capacities of participants, ultimately elevating the quality of the proposals generated.

3. **MEETING DEVELOPMENT**

The workshop followed the steps of participants getting to know each other, proposing projects, forming working groups, and developing the proposed projects.

By introducing themselves, their teams, their research areas and their research participants enabled the first ideas to emerge about future collaborations. Project proposals were listed under the thematic headings of technical/engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities and Education. The proposed projects were started to be discussed by following these thematic groups. Thus, the similarities and differences between the research proposals were made visible.

The institutions selected the project proposals that they want to involve in. As a result of a total of 11 projects being proposed and the institutes wanting to take part in more than one project, it was decided to carry out the project development processes by dividing them into 3 working groups following three themes. Each working group continued to develop ideas by focusing on all or some of the project proposals under the theme.

The improve projects then shared with the entire participants to get comments and feedbacks. Also, the representatives of Projects and commercialization Management Office, International Projects Unit of ITU, suggested possible fundings such as specific calls of Horizon Europe and Jean Monnet.

4. PENDING TASKS, AGREEMENTS, AND MEETINGS

Since the proposals had been previously developed by the authors and subsequently commented on by the workshop leaders, the leaders of each proposal committed to organizing and following up on the work through meetings to continue developing the projects with the workshop leaders interested in each case, and with the objective of its subsequent presentation to the corresponding competitive calls.

No dates were set, but verbal commitments were made for immediate meetings, with estimated dates for calls for proposals between late 2023 and early 2024.

The possibility of promoting new plenary meetings with the participation of all attendees was raised.

The EELISA partner universities will be attentive to new EELISA Connect calls from the EELISA innoCORE project, to consider the request for aid to organize new workshops that give continuity to CIRCULAR MODELS and NEW HORIZONS held by the Circular EELISA Community in 2023 and 2024, respectively.

EELISA Connect Workshop

Interactions in nonlinear analysis: variational methods, reaction-diffusion equations, dynamical systems and applications

Report of the workshop

EELISA

This is an activity funded under EELISA InnoCORE project. EELISA InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020

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1. General data

Title of the workshop

Interactions in nonlinear analysis: variational methods, reaction-diffusion equations, dynamical systems and applications

Dates

10-11-12 April 2024

Format

Hybrid (onsite at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería y Diseño Industrial - ETSIDI - and online on Zoom)

Organizers

- Makrina Agaoglou (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)
- Emeric Bouin (Paris Sciences et Lettres)
- Pedro González Manchón (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)
- Andrea Malchiodi (Scuola Normale Superiore)
- Andrea Tellini (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

Webpage

<https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisaconnect-workshop-interactions-in-nonlinear-analysis-variational-methods-reaction-diffusion-equations-dynamical-systems-and-applications/>

Observations

The official communication that this workshop proposal had been selected, due to a cancellation of a workshop that was previously selected, was received on March 7th 2024, together with the indication that the workshop had to be held by April 12th 2024.

2. Announcement and advertisement of the workshop

The workshop has been announced as follows:

- Real Sociedad Matemática Española, weekly newsletter (n. 841, 22nd March 2024, page 7)
<https://www.rsme.es/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Boletin-841.pdf>
- EELISA Social Networks (including Twitter and LinkedIn profiles)
https://twitter.com/eelisa_eu/status/1770829915614482844
https://www.linkedin.com/posts/eelisa-european-university_eelisaconnect-physics-ecology-activity-7176602538387894273-SBXh
- Webpage of the EELISA Community SSERIES: <https://blogs.upm.es/sseries-eelisa/workshop-eelisa-connect-interacciones-en-analisis-no-lineal/>

During the development of the workshop, some pictures have been posted on the ETSIDI and EELISA Twitter profile:

- https://twitter.com/ETSIDI_UPM/status/1777972274504605781
- https://twitter.com/ETSIDI_UPM/status/1778020164111352092
- https://twitter.com/eelisa_eu/status/1777977638482551087

3. Agenda

The workshop consisted of 14 seminars by the invited speakers, all of them experts in different techniques in Nonlinear Analysis. The speakers were Ph. D. students from EELISA institutions or Professors and Researchers from EELISA institutions or other universities (the latter mainly from Madrid). 10 of the seminars took place in presence at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (School of Engineering and Industrial Design), while 4 of them were delivered online. The whole workshop has been broadcasted online.

Each seminar lasted 45-50 minutes, followed by a short discussion between the speaker and the audience. Discussions about the content of the seminars also continued during the breaks.

The agenda/timetable of the workshop has been the following one.

Time	Wednesday, April 10 th (Sala Azul – Blue room – Floor -1)	Thursday, April 11 th (Salón de actos – Conference hall – Floor 2)	Friday, April 12 th (Sala Azul – Blue room – Floor -1)
9:30-10:00	Welcome session		Fabrizio Macià Lang Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
10:00-10:30	Andrea Malchiodi Scuola Normale Superiore	François Hamel Aix-Marseille Université	Andrea Tellini Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
10:30-11:00	María del Mar González Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	Juan Carlos Sampedro Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	<i>Break</i>
11:00-11:30			
11:30-12:00	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	Luca Ziviani Université Paris Sciences et Lettres
12:00-12:30	Francesco Malizia Scuola Normale Superiore	Mattia Freguglia Scuola Normale Superiore	Eduardo Muñoz-Hernández Universidad Complutense de Madrid
12:30-13:00			
13:00-13:30	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	
13:30-14:00			
14:00-15:00	Miguel A. F. Sanjuán Universidad Rey Juan Carlos	Idriss Mazari-Fouquer Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	<i>Conclusion and final lunch</i>
15:00-16:00	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	
16:00-16:30			
16:30-17:30	Michele Caselli Scuola Normale Superiore	Makrina Agaoglou Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	

Titles and abstracts of the talks are available at this [link](#), and are also attached at the end of the document.

4. Participants

Registration for the workshop was free but mandatory, and it has been carried out through the following form

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScWzx2r2bdAiGYz55ItwCW9LuhwVLpLQauga5qwqnFjimigBQ/viewform>

Overall, a total of 54 people registered and, finally, 24 participants attended at least one session of the workshop in person, and 15 online.

The following tables list the participants (in person/online) during the different days of the workshop. Participation is marked with an X.

In person participants				
Name	Institution	10/04	11/04	12/04
EELISA institutions				
Makrina Agaoglou	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X	X	X
María Barbero Liñán	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid			X
Pedro Carlos Feijoo Guerra	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid		X	X
Mattia Freguglia	Scuola Normale Superiore	X	X	X
Pedro González Manchón	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid			X
Nóra Hezam	Budapest University of Technology and Economics		X	X
Ágoston Knoll	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	X	X	X
Francesco Malizia	Scuola Normale Superiore	X	X	X
Susana Merchán	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X		X
Cristóbal Meroño	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid		X	X
Márton Nagy	Budapest University of Technology and Economics		X	X
Beatriz Pascual Escudero	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid			X
Juan Carlos Sampedro	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X	X	X
Juan Carlos Sanz Nuño	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid			X
Máté Stift	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	X	X	X
Andrea Tellini	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X	X	X
María Jesús Vázquez Gallo	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X	X	X
Luca Ziviani	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres (Ceremade)	X	X	X
External institutions				
Itahisa Barrios-Cubas	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	X		
María del Mar González Noguera	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	X	X	X
François Hamel	Université Aix-Marseille		X	X
Jesús Hernández	I.M.I. Universidad Complutense de Madrid	X	X	X

Eduardo Muñoz Hernández	Universidad Complutense de Madrid	X		X
Miguel A.F. Sanjuán	Universidad Rey Juan Carlos	X		X
Institutional participants				
Jose Antonio Benavent Oltra	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid			X
Roque Calvo Irazo	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid			X
Cecilia Elisabet García Cena	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X		
TOTAL NUMBER OF IN-PERSON PARTICIPANTS		16	16	25

Online participants				
Name	Institution	10/04	11/04	12/04
EELISA institutions				
Emeric Bouin	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres (Ceremade)	X		
Michele Caselli	Scuola Normale Superiore	X		
Carlos Castro	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X		X
Carlos García Gutiérrez	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X	X	
Elahe Ghanaee	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid		X	
Pedro Gómez Molina	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X	X	
Joao Gabriel Gomes de Oliveira	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X		
Fabrizio Macià	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X		X
Andrea Malchiodi	Scuola Normale Superiore	X	X	X
Idriss Mazari-Fouquer	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres (Ceremade)	X	X	X
Manuel Mendoza de Haro	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	X		
Beatriz Pascual Escudero	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid		X	
Matteo Pizzinga	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna		X	
External institutions				
Ouahab Abdelghani	Sidi-Bel-Abbès	X		
Fatima Zohra Bengrine	Tlemcen University	X	X	X
Guglielmo Feltrin	Università degli Studi di Udine			X
TOTAL NUMBER OF ONLINE PARTICIPANTS		12	8	6

5. Topics, analysis and conclusions of the workshop

7.1 5.1 Topics

The mathematical field of nonlinear analysis is used as a tool to study models in several areas of Science and Technology like Physics (e.g., dynamics of bodies, electromagnetism, phase-transitions), Materials Science (e.g., elasticity), Ecology and Epidemiology (e.g., through population dynamics or agent based models) or Chemistry (e.g., reaction-diffusion equations).

In particular, as it is apparent from the titles and abstracts of the talks of the workshop, models from the following fields have been considered during the workshop:

- Population dynamics, with special emphasis on ecology, species distribution and resources.
- Dynamics of chemical reactions
- Oceanography
- Physical modeling (heat distribution and transfer, inverse problems in Electronics, phase-transition problems)

In this sense, the scientific content of the workshop fits into the EELISA Innocore Strategic Research Area of Mathematical Modelling. Moreover, these models have direct ties with the challenges of several SDGs (SDG3: Good health and wellbeing, SDG9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, SDG 13: Climate Action, SDG14: Life below water, SDG15: Life on land).

7.2 5.2 Analysis

Several techniques from nonlinear analysis can be used to tackle the models and the technical problems that arise in their study; for example, variational methods, comparison methods, topological methods, dynamical systems methods. One of the purposes of this workshop has been to bring together experts of the different techniques, stimulating interdisciplinary connections and applications of the techniques to new fields or problems.

In addition, the discussions at the end of the talks and during the breaks allowed speakers and other participants to be updated about recent work done by others researchers, which also was of particular interest for outlining future research.

Another important aspect of the workshop has been the participation of both experienced researchers and several young researchers (Ph.D. candidates or recently established academic staff). Thus, the workshop has been a great opportunity for the new generation of researchers to be introduced to different research lines and stimulate new collaborations.

7.3 5.3 Conclusions and future perspectives

Due to the fact that the workshop was confirmed only one month before the deadline for its execution, it did not fully reach the initial foreseen scope, because some of the speakers indicated in the proposal could not participate and others could only participate online. In addition, having to go through the external travel agency service linked to the UPM has led to inefficiencies, considerably slowing down and making this part of the management complicated.

Despite these inconveniences, the workshop has been an extremely positive experience due to the high scientific profile of the participants (among them some of the leading experts in nonlinear analysis) and the satisfactory number of total participants: 24 people have participated in person to some sessions and 15 online.

Since this was a first contact between such different groups, in order to fully conceive and develop research projects in the future, workshops of this type would need to be repeated with a certain regularity, which requires a certain stability of funding.

Due to the presence of many young researchers, another possibility to strengthen the links between the different research groups in the future is the organization of seasonal schools, combining mini-courses of initiation to new research topics with presentation of the results by the participants. To this end, the different possibilities offered by EELISA will be analyzed.

Another important aspect that has arisen in relation to young researchers has been the continuation of their careers. Different possibilities for postdoctoral contracts and early career positions in the different countries of the EELISA alliance universities participating in the workshop have been compared. For this purpose, the web page <https://eelisa.eu/internships-job-postings-2/> is a very useful tool.

To conclude this report, the organizers wish to acknowledge all the people that have facilitated the organization of this workshop. In particular: Ignacio González Tejada (Associate Vice-rector at UPM for the EELISA Alliance), Isabel Carrillo (Dean of the School of Engineering and Industrial Design at UPM) and the whole directive team, Alejandro Zarzo (Director of the Department of Applied Mathematics to Industrial Engineering at UPM), Isabel Salgueiro (EELISA Innocore Project Manager at UPM), Sara Barsanti (EELISA Innocore Project Manager at SSA), all the staff at School of Engineering and Industrial Design at UPM.

Interactions in nonlinear analysis: variational methods, reaction-diffusion equations, dynamical systems and applications

EELISA Innocore Connect Workshop
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería y Diseño Industrial

April 10th – 12th 2024

Updated information will be available at this [link](#)

Organizers

- Makrina Agaoglou (UPM)
- Emeric Bouin (PSL)
- Pedro González Manchón (UPM)
- Andrea Malchiodi (SNS)
- Andrea Tellini (UPM)

Schedule

Time	Wednesday, April 10 th (Sala Azul – Blue room – Floor -1)	Thursday, April 11 th (Salón de actos – Conference hall – Floor 2)	Friday, April 12 th (Sala Azul – Blue room – Floor -1)
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10:00-10:30	Andrea Malchiodi Scuola Normale Superiore	François Hamel Aix-Marseille Université	Andrea Tellini Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
10:30-11:00			<i>Break</i>
11:00-11:30	María del Mar González Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	Juan Carlos Sampedro Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	
11:30-12:00			<i>Break</i>
12:00-12:30	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	Luca Ziviani Université Paris Sciences et Lettres
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13:00-13:30			
13:30-14:00	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	
14:00-15:00			
15:00-16:00	Miguel A. F. Sanjuán Universidad Rey Juan Carlos	Idriss Mazari-Fouquer Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	
16:00-16:30	<i>Break</i>	<i>Break</i>	
16:30-17:30	Michele Caselli Scuola Normale Superiore	Makrina Agaoglou Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	

This is an activity funded under EELISA InnoCORE project. EELISA InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N. 101035811

EELISA
European University

The method of Lagrangian descriptors: applications in geoscience and in chemical reactions

Abstract

In this talk, I will present the method of Lagrangian descriptors explaining the transport in a chemical reaction and also in oceanic models. I will also present a new uncertainty quantification measure appropriate for quantifying the performance of models in assessing for example the origin or source of a given observation. We have noticed that in a neighborhood of the observation this uncertainty measure is related to the invariant dynamical structures of the model such as hyperbolic trajectories and their stable and unstable manifolds.

8 Classification of finite index solutions to the fractional Allen-Cahn equation and geometric consequences

Michele Caselli

Scuola Normale Superiore

Abstract

In this talk, I will describe a recent result, jointly with Enric Florit-Simon and Joaquim Serra, on the finite index version of the fractional De Giorgi (and Bernstein) conjecture in dimension 3 and 4. Then, we will deduce some geometric consequences regarding the fractional Allen-Cahn equation on Riemannian manifolds.

9 Phase-field approximation of the Willmore functional and a conjecture of De Giorgi

Mattia Freguglia

Scuola Normale Superiore

Abstract

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in geometric energies, as for example the Area functional or the Willmore functional. Some interesting problems arise in the study of the associated geometric flows or in proving the existence of critical points of suitable types. However, these questions are usually difficult to answer, and sometimes it is useful to approximate the original functionals with simpler ones.

In 1991, De Giorgi conjectured a possible approximation of the Willmore functional, in the sense of Gamma-convergence, based on the first variation of the Allen-Cahn functionals.

Since then, several authors have investigated this problem, and some modifications of the approximating functionals have been considered. For some of these, it has been proven that they actually approximate the Willmore functional on smooth sets.

After reviewing some of the most relevant contributions originated from this conjecture over time, we will present a result obtained in collaboration with G. Bellettini and N. Picenni, where we provide a negative answer to the original conjecture.

10 Spectral properties of Levy Fokker-Planck equations

Maía del Mar González Noguera

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid

Abstract

We study the spectrum of a fractional Laplacian equation with drift. This operator arises when studying the fractional heat equation in self-similar variables. We find, in the radially symmetric case, a suitable functional space framework such that all the spectrum reduces to eigenvalues, and we calculate precisely all the eigenfunctions in terms of Laguerre polynomials. The proofs involve conformal geometry, Mellin transform and complex analysis methods.

11 Large-time dynamics of solutions of reaction-diffusion equations in \mathbb{R}^N

François Hamel

Université Aix-Marseille

Abstract

The talk will focus on the large-time dynamics of bounded solutions of reaction-diffusion equations in \mathbb{R}^N with general bounded or unbounded initial support. I will discuss the existence of spreading speeds and spreading sets of the solutions in any direction, in connection with the existence of planar traveling fronts. I will also explain some results on the asymptotic one-dimensional symmetry of the elements of the Ω -limit sets of the solutions. Lastly, I plan to discuss the influence of the fragmentation of the initial support on the large-time dynamics.

The talk is based on joint works with Matthieu Alfaro, Lionel Roques, and Luca Rossi.

12 Solving ill-posed inverse problems via the Born approximation

Fabricio Macià Lang

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Abstract

In this talk we discuss recent work on inverse problems for elliptic partial differential equations revolving around the concept of Born approximation, a tool originally introduced in the context of Scattering Theory that has been extensively used in the physics and computational literature. We will focus on the inverse problem of recovering the potential of a Schrödinger operator from the knowledge of its Dirichlet-to-Neumann map. This is known as the Calderón problem, or Electric Impedance Tomography, and has been intensively studied in the past forty years. This inverse problem is severely ill-posed, which makes the task of designing efficient algorithms to solve it particularly difficult. We will rigorously prove, in the simplified setting of radial potentials in the euclidean unit ball, the existence of the Born approximation, a function that encodes the whole DtN map and enjoys several interesting qualitative and quantitative approximation properties. We use this function to factorize the inverse problem into a linear (ill-posed but explicit) and a nonlinear (well-posed, Hölder continuous) part. This factorization gives a (partial) characterization of the set of DtN maps and we will show how this can be used to ultimately design efficient algorithms to solve the inverse problem. Our analysis is based on results on inverse spectral theory for Schrödinger operators on the half-line, in particular on the concept of A-amplitude introduced by Barry Simon in 1999. This talk is based on joint works with Juan Antonio Barceló, Carlos Castro, and Cristóbal Meroño (UPM), Thierry Daudé (Besançon), François Nicoleau (Nantes).

13 Yamabe metrics on conical manifolds

Andrea Malchiodi

Scuola Normale Superiore

Abstract

We prove existence of Yamabe metrics on singular manifolds with conical points and conical links of Einstein type that include orbifold structures. We deal with metrics of generic type and derive a counterpart of Aubin's classical result. Interestingly, the singular nature of the metric determines a different condition on the dimension, compared to the regular case. We derive asymptotic expansions on the Yamabe quotient by adding a proper and implicit lower-order correction to standard bubbles, whose contribution to the expansion of the quotient can be determined combining the decomposition of symmetric 2-tensor fields and Fourier analysis on the conical links.

This is joint work with M. Freguglia.

14 Compactness of certain Palais-Smale sequences for a Liouville-type equation

Francesco Malizia

Scuola Normale Superiore

Abstract

This talk will address the study of compactness for Palais-Smale sequences relative to a mean-field equation of Liouville type, that is, a 2-dimensional equation with exponential nonlinearity.

While the blow-up analysis for sequences of exact solutions is now well-known, the behaviour of general Palais-Smale sequences is still unknown. In this direction, I will present a result showing that if one considers Palais-Smale sequences with an additional asymptotic control on the Morse index, then it is possible to prove a concentration-compactness result analogous to the one known for exact solutions.

This is part of an ongoing project with Andrea Malchiodi.

15 Spatial ecology and game theory

Idriss Mazari-Fouquer

Université Paris Sciences et Lettres

Abstract

In this talk, we will discuss two recent works in collaboration with Z. Kobeissi and D. Ruiz-Balet, dealing with game-theoretical issues in population dynamics. The overall question we are seeking to address is: assuming that a population of fish lives in a domain, what is the influence of fishing on this population? Is it possible to quantify the fact that fishing is harmful? What happens if we assume that fishers compete and act rationally? To shed some light on this issue, we'll focus on two main models: 1) In the first, a finite number of agents attempt to find an equilibrium. We'll discuss some results on the existence of Nash equilibria, and present some qualitative properties. 2) In the second, an infinite number of agents are competing, and the formalism adopted is that of mean-field games. In this case, the question is that of the tragedy of the commons: is it possible for a species of fish that is invasive in the absence of fishermen to become extinct if the latter act in such a way as to optimize what they catch? And can collaboration between fishermen not only remedy this, but also enable each fisherman to obtain more fish in the end?

16 Topological tools for the analysis of BVPs and periodic problems

Eduardo Muñoz-Hernández

Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Abstract

During the last fifty years, a wide range of topological methods have been developed and sharpened for the analysis of differential equations. While for boundary value problems bifurcation theory has turned out to be a very important tool, for periodic problems a more classical approach has been the use of fixed point theorems and topological indices, e. g. the Poincaré-Birkhoff theorem and the Conley-Zehnder index, respectively, in order to get existence and multiplicity of periodic solutions. In this talk, we present different BVPs and periodic problems in which the different topological approaches above-cited have been applied. This is a joint work with J. López-Gómez (Universidad Complutense de Madrid), A. Boscaggin (Università di Torino) and F. Zanolin (Università di Udine).

17 A priori bounds for superlinear indefinite elliptic PDE in divergence form

Juan Carlos Sampedro

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Abstract

In this talk we present some new blow-up estimates for the positive explosive solutions of a paradigmatic class of elliptic boundary value problems of superlinear indefinite type:

$$\begin{aligned}Lu &= \lambda u + a(x)u^r && \text{in } \Omega, \\Bu &= 0 && \text{on } \partial\Omega,\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where Ω is a bounded domain of \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 1$, of class C^2 , $\lambda \geq 0$,

$$L u = -\operatorname{div}(A(x) \nabla u),$$

uniformly elliptic in Ω and B is any boundary operator of non-classical mixed type on $\partial\Omega$. These estimates are obtained by combining the scaling technique of Gidas–Spruck [2] together with a generalized De Giorgi–Moser weak Harnack inequality found, very recently, by Sirakov [4, 5]. In a further step, based on a comparison result of Amann and López-Gómez [1], we will show how these bounds provide us with some sharp a priori estimates for the classical positive solutions of (1). It turns out that this is the first general result where the decay rates of the potential $a(x)$ do not play any role for getting a priori bounds for the positive solutions when $N \geq 3$. This is a joint work with J. López-Gómez [3].

17.1 References

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- [4] B. Sirakov, A new method of proving a priori bounds for superlinear elliptic PDE, *J. Math. Pures et Appl.* **141** (2020), 184–194.
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18 Exploring the Unpredictability of Physical Systems: Basin Entropy and Testing for Wada Basins

Miguel A. F. Sanjuán

Universidad Rey Juan Carlos

Abstract

In nonlinear dynamics, basins of attraction are defined as the set of points that, taken as initial conditions, lead the system to a specific attractor. This notion appears in a broad range of applications where multistability is present, which is a common situation in neuroscience, economy, astronomy, ecology, and other disciplines. Nonlinear systems often give rise to fractal boundaries in phase space, hindering predictability. When a single boundary separates three or more different basins of attraction, we call them Wada basins. Usually, Wada basins have been considered even more unpredictable than fractal basins. However, this particular unpredictability has not been fully unveiled until the introduction of the concept of basin entropy. The basin entropy provides a quantitative measure of how unpredictable a basin is. With the help of several paradigmatic dynamical systems, we illustrate how to identify the ingredients that hinder the prediction of the final state. The basin entropy together with two new tests of the Wada property have been applied to some physical systems such as experiments of chaotic scattering of cold atoms, models of shadows of binary black holes, and classical and relativistic chaotic scattering associated to the Hénon-Heiles Hamiltonian system in astrophysics.

18.1 References

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- [7] A. Daza, A. Wagemakers, M.A.F. Sanjuán. Ascertaining when a basin is Wada: the merging method. *Scientific Reports* 8, 9954 (2018)

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- [12] A. Daza, A. Wagemakers, M.A.F. Sanjuán. Unpredictability and basin entropy. EPL, 141 43001 (2023)

Andrea Tellini

18.1.1 Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Multiplicity of nodal steady-states for classical logistic equations

Abstract

Using as a base the result on multiplicity of 1-node solutions for degenerate logistic equations by Lopez-Gómez and Rabinowitz (2020), I will first show how multiplicity also occurs for classical logistic equations, for weights which are small perturbations of the degenerate case. Then, I will show how multiplicity is valid far beyond this perturbative case, even arriving at cases arbitrarily close to situations where there is uniqueness.

These results are joint work with P. Cubillos and J. López-Gómez (Universidad Complutense de Madrid).

18.1.2 Université Paris Sciences et
Lettres

L^2 Hypocoercivity methods for kinetic Fokker-Planck equations with factorised Gibbs states

Abstract

This contribution deals with L^2 hypocoercivity methods for kinetic Fokker-Planck equations with integrable local equilibria and a *factorisation* property that relates the Fokker-Planck and the transport operators. Rates of convergence in presence of a global equilibrium, or decay rates otherwise, are estimated either by the corresponding rates in the diffusion limit, or by the rates of convergence to local equilibria, under moment conditions. On the basis of the underlying functional inequalities, we establish a classification of decay and convergence rates for large times, which includes for instance sub-exponential local equilibria and sub-exponential potentials.

This contribution is based on joint work with Emeric Bo

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

The Budapest University of Technology and Economics hosted the EELISA Workshop on AI Ethics and Law on 18-19 March 2024. In four panel discussions, they investigated the possible research directions in the topic, as well as the implications of regulation, especially on Copyright matters and the EU AI Act. The event

also featured a backcasting exercise and a documentary screening.

Report on Workshop EELISA Workshop on AI Ethics and Law on 18-19 March 2024

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4. Pending tasks and agreements	143
5. Forthcoming meetings	143

1. Participant list

BME Students

Name	Identifier	Day1	Day2
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Erdei Anikó	XUC3LP	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Ruzsa Kata	VE3OS8	Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Prohászka Botond Bendegúz	DG1647	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Árok Anna	BJF7AG	Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Kiss-Beck Regina	Z5RXKY	Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Németh Ákos	FOQ6HR	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Ökrös Réka Berta	Jeoqix	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Albert Máté	FQOEIL	Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Kiss-Beck Tamara	WXFJG0	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Bornemissza Mátyás	ENLI90	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Szombati Olivér	P37PLU	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Liska Tamás	IWGB4I	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Jakusch Tamás	IE3CJS	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Elekes Zsófia	C977X1	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-	

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		19:00	
Döbrönte Tamás	F7BMNI	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Simon Gergely Balázs	S6LOR6	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Futó Dániel	VW2VFJ	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Görömbey András István	GF9L18	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Terék Zoltán Tamás	DKLNXS	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Palotás M. Péter	K8GD4Q		Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Gyulai Gergő László	JJY2VO	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Bihari Bence	IVXWF8	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Kibédi Péter	TDHOE9	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Pichler Márton	WN3TN1	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Csicsely Dóra Andrea	PITFA2	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Gyömbér Péter	PIM313	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30,	

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		Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Orsolya Széll	QEJ65R	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Széll Dávid	D4VKW2	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Frink Dávid	HU7WN7	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Péter Zoltán	D60NMP	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Bodnár Barbara	LXXAMS	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	
Petrich Tamás Ákos	FA0B9B	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	
Farkas Ádám	Y2QB11	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Meglécz Máté	A7RBKU	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Varga Viktor	OV12GX	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Sopár Adrián	KKTHLE	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Kis Milán	API8EM	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Josepovits Gábor	BQESH6	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Schneider Dávid	LKRG12	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Szőke Bence	FU2B66	Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Hujbert Patrik	D83AE5	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	

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Sinkó Viktor Péter	XCT9YC	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Bozó Balázs	QR8EDT	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Mihalkó Nóra	G6ML4L	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Szász Luca Lina	YT5VG5	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Nyilas János Attila	G23VOZ	Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Burányi Dániel Bence	APC6AN	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	
Tóth Gábor	F041OM	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Kekesi Laura Emilia	Qldcsb	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30

Other participants

Gabriella Völgyesi dr.	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Békés Gergely	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30
Miklós Márton	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Strausz György	Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Varga Pál	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30

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György Kratochwill	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Zsolt Ziegler	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Sógor Zsuzsa	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Dr. Csibra Klára	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Szoboszlai Kinga	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	
Beáta Laki	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	
Orsolya Széll	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Zarka Dénes	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30, Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30, Documentary screening 18:00-19:00	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Eva Szalma	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	Session 3: 9:00- 10:30, Session 4: 11:00 - 12:30
Wágner Bánk	Session 1: 14:00 - 15:30	
Barbara Darcsi	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	
Ábel Kovács	Session 2: 16:00 - 17:30	

(49 Students, 17 Staff and participants)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2. Agenda

EELISA Workshop on AI Ethics and Law

Budapest University of Technology and Economics

18-19 March 2024

Day 1, 18 March 2024	
Location: Building "E", room E202, BME Campus, 1111 Budapest	
13:55-14:00	The Organizers: Welcome to the workshop
Panel 1 - Research directions in ethics of AI	
14:00-15:30	Mihály Héder (BME Philos) ; Emine Gorgul (ITU); Merve C. Akgun (ITU); Ralf Mitschke (FAU); Marcell Sebestyén (BME), Alessio Tartaro (Sassari, CEN/CENELEC), Lidia Marassi (UNINA). Transparency & Bias; Alignment & Existential Risks; Social Impact of AI; Gender and AI; Responsible Innovation Policy Research; The Political Economy of AI; Theological Perspectives of AI.
15:30-16:00	Break
Panel 2 - The EU AI Act and other related regulation	
16:00-17:30	Gabriele Franco (Panetta) ; Celia Fernandez Aller (UPM); Kitti Mezei (BME), Anikó Grad-Gyenge (BME), Alessio Tartaro (Sassari, CEN/CENELEC), Pilar C. I. Gracia (UPM). The EU AI Act and its implications; regulatory strategies; sandboxes.
17:30-18:00	Break
18:00-19:00	Documentary screening (16+): Musings of a Mechatronic Mistress: The Peculiar Purpose of Tiffany the Sex Robot (by Jasmin Hagendorfer) - Introduction by Ralf Mitschke (FAU). Trailer: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QZWh_MW6jC
Day 2, 19 March 2024	
Location: Building "E", room E202, BME Campus, 1111 Budapest	
Panel 3 - AI vs. copyright	
9:00-10:30	Anikó Grad-Gyenge (BME Law) , Zsolt Ziegler (BME Philos), Gabriele Franco (Panetta); Celia Fernandez Aller (UPM); Aida Elamrani (PSL), Daniele Cavalli (PSL). Artificial Authors; The future of creativity; Originality and Creativity as preconditions of Copyright protection and the AI.
10:30-11:00	Break
Panel 4 - Synergies, future directions	
11:00-12:30	Mihály Héder (BME) , Gabriele Franco (Panetta); Celia Fernandez Aller (UPM), Anikó Grad-Gyenge (BME), Jesús Salgado-Criado (UPM), Stefano Marrone (UNINA); Pilar C. I. Gracia (UPM); Synergies between Ethics and Law; Future directions in research Ethics of AI and Law of AI; Education of ethics of AI and Law.

Organizing Institutions

Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)
 Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)
 İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi (ITU)
 Ecole Normale Supérieure Paris (PSL)
 Universidad Politécnica Madrid (UPM)

Funding

This is an activity funded under **EELISA InnoCORE** project. EELISA InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No **101035811**

Registration

Click here:
<https://forms.gle/oBZFzosC5Kmqrk8b6>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

3. Meeting report

The first session opened up the space of ideas with several philosophical topics. Ralf Mitschke (Friedrich-Alexander University), Merve Calimli Akgun (Istanbul Technical University), Emine Görgül (Istanbul Technical University), Marcell Sebestyén (Budapest University of Technology and Economics), Lidia Marassi (Federico II University of Napoli), Alessio Tartaro (University of Sassari; CEN/CENELEC) and Mihály Héder (Budapest University of Technology and Economics) discussed a wide range of topics from dark

enlightenment through AI education to the political and international relations aspects of AI.

The second session was dedicated to the AI Act, finalized on 13 March 2024. This was the most subscribed panel and the room was full. With the moderation of legal expert Gabriele Franco (Panetta Law Firm, Rome), Jesus Salgado-Criado (Technical University of Madrid), Celia Fernandez Aller (Technical University of Madrid), Kitti Mezei (Budapest University of Technology and Economics) and Alessio Tartaro went through the main points of the AI Act and the implications of it to the European landscape.

Session 3 was a documentary screening, introduced by Ralf Mitschke the movie was titled *Musings of a Mechatronic Mistress: The Peculiar Purpose of Tiffany the Sex Robot* (by Jasmin Hagendorfer).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

By the end of day 1, the backcasting exercise took off with audience input:

Panel 3 discussed the issues of AI creativity and copyright. Moderated by Anikó Grad-Gyenge (Budapest University of Technology and Economics), Gabriele Franco, Celia Fernandez Aller, Daniele Cavalli (Ecole normale supérieure Paris), Aïda Elamrani (Ecole normale supérieure Paris) and Zsolt Ziegler (Budapest University of Technology and Economics), the panel explored almost unfathomable implications of generative AI and the way it uses data.

Finally, panel 4 embraced the future. From the current standardisation efforts to the expected behavior of companies and society in general, Gabriele Franco, Celia Fernandez Aller, Jesus Salgado-Criado, Alessio Tartaro, Stefano Marrone (Federico II University of Napoli) and Mihály Héder shared their visions on what the next years or decades might hold.

With 113 visitors, most of them local students but also some experts from the field, and several fruitful discussions in the breaks as well as in the upcoming classes, the organizers believe that EELISA Workshop on AI Ethics and Law was a fun and useful event.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

4. Pending tasks and agreements

All tasks planned for the local event has been fulfilled. An agreement was made for a multi-authored article will be written based on the workshop, titled: *A rights based and human-centered approach to artificial intelligence in public services*. A tentative agreement was made among some of the participants to explore the possibility of creating an EELISA Community “Community for Philosophy, Law, and Culture”. The initiative will be led by BME.

5. Forthcoming meetings

The possibility of promoting new plenary meetings with the participation of all attendees was raised, both for Turkey and for Spain as potential locations. This will have to happen in EELISA 2 and to be finalized in the next years.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

**Engineering a Sustainable Future:
Bridging Minds, Building Skills**

18-19 March 2024, Istanbul (hybrid event)

UNIVERSIDAD
POLITÉCNICA
DE MADRID

This is an activity funded under EELISA InnoCORE project. EELISA InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

SusCo - Interdisciplinarity for Sustainable Competences in Engineering Education

WORKSHOP REPORT

Workshop name: "Engineering a Sustainable Future:	Place: Istanbul Technical University (ITU)
	Date: 18/03/2024 - 19/03/2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Bridging Minds, Building Skills”	Format: Hybrid
<p>This workshop brought together researchers, educators, and students to explore the integration of sustainability and transversal skills into engineering education, fostering collaborative research ideas and skill development. Discussions spanned innovative education approaches, industry expectations, collaboration opportunities, and future plans. Key topics included barriers to implementing sustainable practices, project opportunities, and student involvement, all aimed at enhancing sustainability education and fostering collaboration between academia and industry. Participants shared research results and best practices, igniting discussions on potential collaborative projects. Additionally, students contributed their perspectives on the future of sustainability education, guiding future initiatives and ensuring active involvement in shaping the engineering landscape.</p>	

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1 1. List of Participants

	Name	Institution	Online/ In-Person	Day 1 (18/03/2024)	Day 2 (19/03/2024)	Speaker/ Participant
1	Mária Szalmáné Csete	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
2	Shakhashiro Hiba	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
3	Mariann Szabó	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
4	György Horvath	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
5	Orsolya Barna	External	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
6	Elena Fleaca	NUSTPB	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
7	Mirela Stanescu	NUSTPB	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
8	Simona Mihaela Bibic	NUSTPB	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
9	Elena Corina Cipu	NUSTPB	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
10	Sanda Maiduc	NUSTPB	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
11	Antonia Pacios	UPM	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
12	Gülin Yücel	Brika Sust.Conslt.	In-Person	NO	YES	Speaker
13	Ruihan Lin	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
14	Xueqing Gao	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
15	Márton Pluzsik	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
16	Árpád Mátyás Balogh	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
17	Botond Kozman	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant

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18	Attila Bajner	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
19	Bende Barcza	BME	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
20	Reyna Yaltır	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
21	A.Tolga ILTER	ITU	In-Person	YES	NO	Participant
22	Borana Topçu	ITU	In-Person	YES	NO	Participant
23	Gökçe Ceylan	ITU	In-Person	YES	NO	Speaker
24	Aslı Can Karaca	ITU	In-Person	YES	NO	Participant
25	Hamza Salih Erden	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
26	Börte Köse Mutlu	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
27	Semra Ahmetolan	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
28	Didem Özgür	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
29	Ebru Acuner Türet	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
30	Emrah Acar	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Speaker
31	Hür Bersam Sidal	ITU	In-Person	YES	YES	Participant
32	Başak Tiniş	ITU	In-Person	NO	YES	Participant
33	Balazs Nagy	BME	Online	YES	NO	Speaker
34	Brad Tabas	ENSTA Bretagne	Online	YES	NO	Speaker
35	Tamás Lovas	BME	Online	YES	NO	Speaker
36	Dániel Nagy	CBRE	Online	NO	YES	Speaker
37	Rita Péterné Baranyi	Michelin	Online	NO	NO	Speaker
38	Suha Yazıcı	ITU	Online	YES	NO	Participant
39	Mustafa Remzi Bayoğlu	ITU	Online	YES	NO	Participant

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40	JAVIER GARCIA MARTIN	UPM	Online	YES	NO	Participant
41	Bilguun Boldtur	BME	Online	YES	NO	Participant
42	Bilal Karakaş	ITU	Online	YES	NO	Participant
43	Klara Kövesi	ENSTA Bretagne	Online	YES	NO	Participant
44	Fatih Şen	ITU	Online	YES	NO	Participant
45	Mehmet Oğuz Şalış	ITU	Online	YES	NO	Participant

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2. Meeting Agenda

2.1. Agenda Program of the first day

EELISA SusCo Community Workshop
Engineering a Sustainable Future: Bridging Minds, Building Skills
 18-19 March 2024, Istanbul Technical University
 ITU Ayazaga Campus, Suleyman Demirel Cultural Center, Senate Room

18 March 2024 - Monday	
09.00 - 09.30	Registration - Welcome coffee
09.30 - 10.00	Welcome ceremony: İTÜ, EELISA, SusCo
10.00 - 10.40	SusCo Research Results
10.40 - 11.00	Coffee Break
11.00 - 12.20	Innovative Education Approaches - I Moderator: Emrah Acar, Ph.D. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Börte Köse Mutlu, Ph.D. & Ebru Acuner Türet, Ph.D. (ITU) - "ITU Sustainability M.Sc. Program" György Horváth, Ph.D. (BME) - "Green Certificate" Mariann Szabó, Ph.D. (BME) - "NICE project" Corina Cipu, Ph.D. (UPB) - "Innovative Methods for a Sustainable Future"
12.20 - 12.25	Group Photo
12.25 - 13.20	Lunch
13.20 - 13.40	Balázs Vince Nagy, Ph.D. - Keynote Speech
13.40 - 14.40	Innovative Education Approaches - II Moderator: Elena Fleaca, Ph.D. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tamás Lovas, Ph.D. (BME) - "Teaching non-technical skills to engineering students" Brad Tabas, Ph.D. (ENSTA Bretagne) - "Teaching Anticipation as a Sustainable Development Competence through Future Labs" Gökçe Ceylan (ITU) - "Inventing Engineers of the Future"
14.40 - 15.00	Coffee Break
15.00 - 17.00	Reflective Workshop - Participants & Observers (On-site only) Moderator: Orsolya Barna

EELISA-InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 R & I programme under GA No. 101035811.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Program of the second day

19 March 2024 - Tuesday	
9.00 - 9.30	Opening
9.30 - 10.00	Industry Expectations Moderator: Mária Szalmáné Csete, Ph.D. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ms. Gülin Yücel (Brika Sustainability Consultancy) • Dániel Nagy (CBRE) • Rita Péterné Baranyi, Ph.D. (Michelin)
10.00 - 10.40	Collaboration Opportunities and Good Practices Moderator: György Horváth, Ph.D. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Didem Özgür, Ph.D. (ITU International Projects Coordination Dept.) - "Relevant Calls" • Elena FLEACA, Ph.D. (UPB) - "International cooperation projects for sustainability education in business engineering – good practices from the exchange of experiences" • Antonia Pacios Alvarez, Ph.D. (UPM) - "Circular EELISA Community Ecosystem. Recent activities and future collaborations."
10.40 - 11.00	Coffee Break
11.00 - 12.00	Future Plans (Format: World Café / Menti for Online Participation) Moderator: Orsolya Barna / Hamza Salih Erden, Ph.D. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Barriers of implementing sustainability in engineering programmes 2. Ideas for future projects with Funding Opportunities 3. Sustainability for SusCo - operational, funding, organizational, recruiting people, etc., 4. Strategies for increasing the student involvement, 5. Focus of SusCo in the future of your interest 6. Research interests and gaps in practice
12.10 - 12.15	Closing Session
12.15 - 12.20	Group Photo
12.20 - 13.15	Lunch

EELISA-InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 R & I programme under GA No. 101035811.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2.1.1. Day 1: 18th March, 2024

The EELISA SusCo Community Workshop opened with an introduction by Dr. Hamza Salih Erden, showcasing Istanbul Technical University's role as the host. EELISA President Mr. Dale Martin provided a welcoming address, setting a collaborative tone, which was followed by the introduction to the SusCo community by Dr. Mária Szalmáné Csete. Following the introductions, Ms. Orsolya Barna shared key results from the joint research activities conducted within the SusCo community in 2023, which is subject to a journal publication currently under review.

A highlight of the morning was the session on Innovative Education Approaches, steered by Dr. Emrah Acar, which underscored the need for pedagogical innovations and stakeholder collaboration to enhance teaching methods in sustainability. Presentations ranged from ITU's MSc program, BME's "Green Certificate" program, to the NICE project and NUSTPB's methods for a sustainable future, all converging on the imperative of interdisciplinary education and real-world engagement.

The afternoon continued with Dr. Elena Fleaca moderating discussions on non-technical skill development, the necessity of experiential learning settings, and international collaboration as a lever for cultural understanding and anticipation skills in engineering education. Dr. Tamás Lovas, Dr. Brad Tabas, and Ms. Gökçe Ceylan presented their unique pedagogical approaches, emphasising the organic development of next-generation European Engineers equipped for sustainability challenges.

The closing session of the first day was the reflective thinking workshop particularly aimed at developing transversal skill development led by Ms. Barna Orsolya conducted by the student participants of the workshop showcasing debating skills on controversial topics in education.

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2.1.2. Day 2: 19th March, 2024

The second day delved into industry expectations with a discussion panel moderated by Dr. Mária Szalmáné Csete., featuring speakers from sustainability consultancies and industry leaders, emphasising the pervasive nature of sustainability across all sectors and the imperative to embed sustainability in engineering curricula. Ms. Gülin Yücel (Brika Sustainability Consultancy) highlighted the need for education that equips graduates with relevant competencies such as systematisation, data analysis, and adaptability to ensure their readiness for industry demands. Following the contributions to the discussion by Mr. Dániel Nagy (CBRE), and Dr. Rita Péterné Baranyi (Michelin), reflective learning and the integration of more multidisciplinary approaches were deemed crucial, alongside practical tools such as energy audits and simulations for a more experiential understanding of sustainability.

Dr. György Horváth, steered the following session on collaboration opportunities and good practices, with international perspectives on sustainable education in engineering. Dr. Didem Özgür spotlighted the potential of Erasmus+ programs to enrich higher education and to create more inclusive and interconnected educational structures, offering micro-credentials to accommodate continuous learning and to address the specific needs of the industry. Dr. Elena Fleaca shared her experiences in relevant joint-research channels and on embedding STEAM into more management-focused curricula. The EELISA community's Circular Project represented by Dr. Antonia Pacios Alvarez, with its 7 partners across countries and 5 knowledge areas, exemplifies a multi-faceted approach to integrating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into higher education.

The workshop on Day 2 concluded with a World Café session, guided by Ms. Orsolya Barna, which discussed barriers, strategies, and future plans regarding sustainability in engineering. Challenges such as the "classical" mindset in engineering and cultural differences in education were identified as barriers. To increase student involvement, ideas like changing homework styles and offering more hands-on, project-based activities were proposed. Funding opportunities were explored with suggestions like new Erasmus+ projects and green jobs, while the sustainability of the SusCo community was debated, considering operational and financial aspects, as well as keeping people involved. Research interests were also noted, emphasising the need for sustainable mindsets in education, early development, and addressing practical gaps such as sustainability in corporate life.

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SusCo Workshop Group Photo

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2.2. Principle Objectives Achieved

The workshop's objectives of fostering innovation in educational approaches were strongly demonstrated by the variety of presentations and discussions. The importance of integrating non-technical skills, anticipation, social responsibility, and international perspectives in engineering programs was particularly highlighted. Moreover, a commitment to sustainable development competencies was made evident through the diverse methodologies presented.

All the sessions have broadened the perspective on how academia and industry can collaborate to shape an education system that is not only responsive to the current sustainability challenges but also anticipates the needs of the future. The discussions have set a clear path toward curricula that are deeply integrated with sustainability, preparing students to become adaptable, ethically grounded, and technically proficient professionals who will drive the sustainable transformation of our societies.

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3. Meeting Development

The workshop exemplified the innovative spirit and commitment of EELISA towards sustainable education. It successfully showcased good practices to bridge the gap between academia's theoretical frameworks and the industry's practical expectations. Interactive sessions highlighted the importance of integrating sustainability into curricula, emphasising skills development to address industry needs effectively.

Good practices from the Circular Community provided a template for integrating companies and communities in educational programs. The STEAM approach suggested by Dr. Elena Fleaca signified the shift towards incorporating more management and entrepreneurship within technical curricula, an essential step for fostering project experience and skills of the future.

Discussion on collaboration opportunities shed light on the value of inclusive education and capacity building in higher education. Programs like Jean Monnet Activities and Erasmus+ highlighted the need for international cooperation, policy experimentation, and the pursuit of excellence in creating an adaptive and responsive educational ecosystem.

The World Café provided a forum for identifying obstacles and generating innovative ideas to implement sustainability in engineering programmes. The discussions revolved around enhancing curricula with real-world sustainability audits, simulations, and multidisciplinary approaches. Strategies for future planning of SusCo, such as workshops and webinars, were aligned with EELISA's goals of sustainable education. Furthermore, the session pinpointed research interests, spotlighting the importance of linking sustainability with corporate life.

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4. Pending Task and Agreements

The momentum needs to be harnessed with clearly defined tasks and firm agreements to ensure the continuity of the progress achieved. A detailed analysis of the workshop outcomes will be made to create a roadmap for the organisational, operational and financial sustainability of the SusCo EELISA community. Further collaborations are needed to continue fostering interdisciplinary approaches and designing initiatives like modular courses that can respond dynamically to emerging sustainability challenges and to transform ideas into actionable projects. Key tasks will involve organising new projects potentially on embedding sustainability into curricula, and securing the operational and financial sustainability of SusCo. Sharing best practices, research findings, and teaching materials within the SusCo and EELISA network to build deemed to be essential to ensure a robust knowledge exchange platform.

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5. Forthcoming meetings

The necessity for regular meetings is a key component for sustained collaboration. Future meetings will aim to assess the integration of the workshop outputs into potential project development ideas not only limited to educational or research activities. Dates will be set for follow-up meetings and activities. There will be a concerted effort to involve more stakeholders besides academics, including students, policymakers and educational authorities to ensure that the future of engineering education is more comprehensive.

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CIRCULAR MODELS:

Research, innovation, and partnerships towards circularity.

REPORT OF THE WORKSHOP

<p>Workshop name: Circular Models: Research, innovation, and partnerships towards circularity.</p>	<p>Place: Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM-ETSIABB) Date: 03/07/2023 to 05/07/2023 Format: Face-to-face</p>
<p>This workshop aims to promote research and innovation in the field of circular economy. This workshop brought together researchers, academics and business representatives to explore innovative, inclusive and circular solutions.</p> <p>The two-and-a-half-day event covered key topics related to the circular economy such as culture, creativity and inclusive society; advanced materials science; and climate change, energy and sustainable mobility. Through expert panels, thematic roundtables and interactive sessions, participants were able to share knowledge, experiences and best practices.</p> <p>The main objective of the workshop was to stimulate the generation of collaborative research projects and strengthen alliances between universities, companies and other institutions. It also aims to create opportunities to present proposals that will allow the establishment of cooperation channels and alliances for future inter-university cooperation at European level, such as: seasonal school, blended intensive programmes (BIP) or joint degrees (Master, Doctorate). This event also aims to involve young researchers, including masters and doctoral students, to bring them closer to research projects, the development of social and sustainable competences and the resolution of global challenges.</p> <p>We invited academics, researchers, companies and other interested parties to participate in this workshop and contribute their knowledge and experience. Together, let us drive research, innovation and collaboration towards a circular economy model.</p>	

Edition: 0001

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1 PARTICIPANTS LIST:

Table #1: List of attendees:

#	SURNAME AND NAME	COMPANY / INSTITUTION	ASSISTANCE (Yes/No)		
			03/07/2023	04/07/2023	05/07/2023
	EELISA				
1	BONTOS MARIUS DANIEL	UPB	Yes	Yes	No
2	CASTILLO RODRÍGUEZ ANABEL	UPM-ETSIAAB	Yes	Yes	Yes
3	COLAKOGLU MERYEM BIRGUL	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	CROCE ROBERTA	SSSA	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	FLORES DE LA COLINA MARÍA AURORA	UPM-ETSE	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	GÁLVEZ JAIME	UPM- ETSICCP	Yes	Yes	No
7	GARCÍA NAVARRO JUSTO	UPM-ETSIAAB	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	HORTA BELLIDO ANA	UPM-Innovación y Emprendimiento I&E	Yes	Yes	No
9	GONZALEZ RODRIGUEZ SILVIA VIVIANA	UPM-ETSICCP	Yes	Yes	Yes
10	KAYA CIGDEM	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
11	MARTIN BAUTISTA-CERRO BEATRIZ	UPM-ETSIAAB	Yes	Yes	Yes
12	MOICEANU GEORGIANA	UPB	Yes	Yes	No
13	MOSQUERA JUAN CARLOS	UPM-ETSICCP	No	No	Yes
14	NAVARRO CARRILLO ELISA	UPM-Innovación y Emprendimiento I&E	Yes	Yes	No
15	PACIOS ÁLVAREZ ANTONIA	UPM-ETSIAE	Yes	Yes	Yes
16	PÉREZ TEMBLEQUE LAURA	UPM-ETSIAAB	Yes	Yes	Yes
17	R. FOGAÇA DIEGO	UPM-CSTO2NE, PhD student	Yes	Yes	No
18	RAMIREZ MASFERRER JAVIER ÁNGEL	UPM- ETSIAAB	Yes	Yes	Yes
19	ROBESCU LACRAMIOARA DIANA	UPB	Yes	Yes	No
20	SALGUEIRO ISABEL	UPM-innoCORE	No	No	Yes
21	SIMON MARIAM	UPM-ETSA	Yes	No	Yes
22	TAHIROĞULLARI MEHTAP YALÇIN	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
23	TORRODERO NUMPAQUE VANESSA	UPM-ETSIAAB	Yes	Yes	Yes
24	VERDE MARÍA	UPM OPI	Yes	Yes	No
25	WAITE JR IMGE AKCAKAYA	ITU	Yes	Yes	Yes
	EXTERNAL				
26	BLANCO ARAN	KVELOCE I+D+i	Yes	Yes	No
27	CALVO SARA	SURUS	Yes	Yes	Yes
28	FERRI SANZ MIREIA	KVELOCE I+D+i (SENIOR EUROPA SL)	No	Yes	No
29	GARCÉS FERRER JORGE	POLIBIENESTAR	Yes	Yes	Yes
30	GOMBKÖTŐ IMRE	UNIVERSITY OF MISKOLC	Yes	Yes	Yes
31	GONÇALVES JOSÉ	IPCB - CBPBI	Yes	Yes	Yes
32	NAVALHAS INÉS	NOVA	Yes	Yes	No
33	JIMÉNEZ PULIDO CRISTINA	Arquitectura	No	No	No
34	LOPEZ DAVID	AFANIAS	No	No	No
35	LÓPEZ CRUZ JORGE	SURUS	Yes	Yes	Yes
36	NAVARRO TOMÁS	SCAPHARI VENTURES	No	No	No
37	SERRA CARLOS	POLIBIENESTAR	Yes	Yes	Yes

38	TRAVESÍ BUGALLO BLANCA	U4IMPACT	Yes	No	No
39	URZE PAULA CRISTINA	NOVA	Yes	Yes	Yes
	TOTAL, ATTENDANTS		33	32	24
			03/07/2023	04/07/2023	05/07/2023

2 MEETING AGENDA

2.1 Agenda:

Image 1: Program of the first day:

Image 2: Program of the first day:

TO SEE WHAT WE HAVE IN MIND
The new panels are now dedicated to giving attendees the opportunity to propose ideas or present drafts in progress, with the aim of joining efforts and designing consortia that can promote and present winning proposals to the next European calls. It is an opportunity to share and refine draft research and innovation projects that can be the basis of future proposals.

16:00-18:30 **Circular panels** (to present proposals)

- The participants will be able to present challenges or projects that they would like to develop and to which they invite the rest of the attendees (proposals that are in the ideation phase and in the search for partners).
- Comments and feedback from other academics, researchers and company representatives.

20:00 **DINNER* & NETWORKING**

***Dinners are not covered by the workshop.**

Image 3: Program of the second day:

04th July 2023

TO ORGANIZE WORKING GROUPS
Considering the conclusions and results of the first day, we will start with some thematic roundtables focusing on three [EELISA innoCORE Strategic Research Areas \(SRAs\)](#)¹. Attendants can move and interact in the different rooms, to look for the appropriate group to continue working.

9:00-11:00 **Thematic round tables** (divided into groups)
Working groups focusing on the three EELISA InnoCORE Strategic Research Areas (SRAs):

- Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society.
- Advanced Materials Science and Engineering.
- Climate Energy & Mobility.

11:00-11:30 **COFFEE BREAK**

11:30-13:00 **Practical workshop** (divided into groups)

- Interactive sessions where participants work in groups to address specific challenges.
- Exploration of methodologies, tools and practical approaches to promote circularity in different contexts.
- Selection of ideas for the proposal development phase.

13:00-14:00 **LUNCH**

¹ **EELISA innoCORE SRAs** (Strategic Research Areas) are research areas selected as "key strategic" by the EELISA consortium at the Kick-off meeting, namely: 1. Digital; 2. Climate, Energy & Mobility; 3. Social Sciences & Humanities; 4. Health; 5. Artificial Intelligence; 6. Connectivity; 7. Food, Bio-economy, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment; 8. Culture, Creativity & Inclusive Society; 9. Smart Industry & Space Technologies; 10. Natural Sciences; 11. Advanced Materials Science and Engineering.

Image 4: Program of the third day:

2.1.1 Day 1: 3rd July, 2023

Justo García-Navarro (JGN), coordinator of the workshop, opened the session and welcomed all the attendees, explaining the agenda and the objectives of the workshop. Also, Eutiquio Gallego Vazquez deputy director of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid extended a warm welcome to the participants.

Then each participant was introduced, stating their name, position and interest in attending the Circular Models Workshop, with the aim of getting to know each other. Once the introductions were finished, the coordinator/host opened the way for the presentations, starting with his own, explaining the ongoing projects from his research group, giSCI-UPM, the Circular EELISA Community composition, aims and goals; and the main activities developed so far in the community.

Afterwards, the participants were then invited to present their organizations, activities and ongoing projects and their respective interests in the research and innovation areas they would like to participate in. JGN ask for summarizing the interest using keywords, and the results are showed in the table below.

Table #2: Institution and companies' presentations:

Nº	Presentation/ Area of work	Responsible	Institution / Company	Working Key words
1.	giSCI –UPM, EELISA, Circular EELISA Community and CIRC.LE project	Justo García-Navarro	Circular EELISA Community	Industrial symbiosis, construction waste, Materials (9R)
2.	Construction and Building Materials: Durability & Sustainability	Jaime Galvez	UPM-ETSICCP	Sustainability of materials, durability, ECO-friendly, construction materials
3.	Instituto de Investigación de Políticas de Bienestar Social, Universitat de València	Carlos Serra	Polibienestar	Democracy, Governance, Social Impact
4.	University Politehnica of Bucharest	Lacramioara Diana Robescu	UPB	Impact on the environment: soil, air, water, energy, water footprint, Smart cities
5.	Istanbul Technical University: Faculty of Architecture	Birgul Meryem Colakoglu	ITU	Smart circular cities, smart infuse, construction materials, circular education, lifecycle design.
6.	Clean Cities ClimAccelerator Solutions for a climate neutral future	Elisa Navarro Carrillo & Ana Horta Bellido	UPM Innovación y Emprendimiento I&E	Entrepreneurship cities, sustainability
7.	Valorisation in Circular Dismantling	Jorge López Cruz	SURUS	Planning, benefits, technology, EoW
8.	Department of Urban and Regional Planning: Urban planning, Participation and Governance.	Imge Akcakaya Waite Jr.	ITU	Collaborative Governance, stakeholders, engagement, participatory and inclusive, planning
9.	Research in which ETSIAE-Airport Group is involved	Antonia Pacios Álvarez	UPM-ETSIAE	Eco-design, biomimicry, Indicators
10.	KVELOCE I+D+i: Research	Aran Blanco	KVELOCE I+D+i	Public Engagement,

	capacities and expertise			Social Impact assessment
11.	Products-Services-Systems (PSS) Digital + physical = phygital: use-share, a circular co-use of products that are supported by services	Cigdem Kaya	ITU	Use-Sharing
12.	Sustainability Management Laboratory, SuM Lab	Roberta Croce	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa	Environmental impact assessment (LCA /Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) CE, Monitoring tools
13.	U4IMPACT: The platform that connects companies with university students to deliver innovation, sustainability and impact projects	Blanca Travesí Bugallo	U4IMPACT	Thesis, transfer of faculties, collaborative
14.	Funding Opportunities for International Research on Circularity	Maria Verde	UPM-OPI	International Funding

During the presentations, the comments and interests of the academics and companies participating in the day were exchanged. There was a high level of participation and interest in topics related to the circular economy, governance, social aspects, education and energy, which led to the following merging of proposals and projects, in which attendants continue working to make the possible proposals feasible.

The last presentation, by Maria Verde from OPI UPM's International Projects Office, explained in detail the alternatives to competitive calls at European level, the types of projects and the funding timetables, with the aim of giving participants a broad vision of their projects and motivating them to participate and submit calls.

2.1.2 Day 2: 4th July, 2023

On the second day, after a brief welcome by the Director of the School of Agricultural, Food and Biosystems Engineering (ETSIAAB), of Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, the session started with the presentation of project proposals, where the participants discussed the feasibility, main issues, strengths and weaknesses of the projects, giving ideas and developing the themes in a deep level. It was also discussed how, when, under what conditions, financing, etc. of each proposal.

The following table shows the proposals and topics presented for discussion during the workshop. Initially, it was decided to work in groups according to the topics presented, but given the great interest shown, all the proposals made were discussed by all participants.

Table #3: Proposals presentations:

Nº	PROPOSAL	RESPONSIBLE	THEMATIC
1.	JOINT DOCTORAL DEGREES	Justo García-Navarro	Education
2.	SYSTEMIC CIRCULAR SOLUTIONS FOR A SUSTAINABLE TOURISM	Carlos Serra	Governance, social impact
3.	GREENCOMP (PISA_GC)	Beatriz Martín Bautista-Cerro	Education and Sustainable assessment
4.	CIRCULAR GOVERNANCE: A COLLABORATIVE AND CIRCULAR URBAN GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK	Imge Akcakaya Waite Jr.	Governance, social impact
5.	ENERGY WASTE TREATMENT	Lacramioara Diana Robescu	Environment, Energy
6.	GREEN SCHOOLS	Mehtap Yalçın Tahiroğulları	Education
7.	JOINT MASTER PROGRAM: CIRCULAR DESIGN, LCA	Birgul Meryem Colakoglu	Education
8.	EPR AND ECO-DESIGN REGULATION	Roberta Croce	Governance, LCA

Thus, the proposals were given added value by the participants, making them more viable and creating links between the different organizations to formalise the projects and generate commitments towards future collaborations. As a result, from the proposal details in the previous table, a convergence of proposals was obtained, and a total of six proposals were achieved feasible for future projects.

During the afternoon, the proposals were commented on and modified, agreements were made to cooperate in the further development of the various projects, and finally Maria Verde from OPI UPM's International Projects Office get involved to check the compatibility of the various proposals with the funding requirements at European level.

2.1.3 Day 3: 5th July, 2023

On the last day, the participants presented the final version of the proposals, and the convergent proposals presented integration with the applied modifications. In addition, institutions and companies promised to continue working on the proposals, agree to a new meeting in the following days to review the progress and organize the work while waiting for the launch of the appropriate European calls.

Table #4: Final Proposals:

Nº	PROPOSAL	RESPONSIBLE	THEMATIC
1.	JOINT MASTER DEGREE IN CIRCULAR BUILDING DESIGN AND JOINT DOCTORAL DEGREE IN CIRCULAR ECONOMY	Birgul Meryem Colakoglu & Justo García-Navarro	Education
2.	GREENCOMP (PISA_GC)	Beatriz Martin Bautista-Cerro	Education and Sustainable assessment
3.	CIRCULAR GOVERNANCE: A COLLABORATIVE AND CIRCULAR URBAN GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK AND SYSTEMIC CIRCULAR SOLUTIONS FOR A SUSTAINABLE TOURISM	Imge Akcakaya Waite Jr. & Carlos Serra	Governance, social impact
5.	ENERGY WASTE TREATMENT	Lacramioara Diana Robescu	Environment, Energy
5.	GREEN SCHOOLS (Adaptation to the regulation)	Mehtap Yalçın Tahiroğulları	Education, Regulation
6.	EPR AND ECO-DESIGN REGULATION	Roberta Croce	Governance, LCA

2.2 Principal Objectives Achieved

Among the participants, a great variety of lines of activity stands out, such as architecture, construction, building, urban planning, materials, economics, environmental sciences; Regarding companies and other organizations, there is a great interest in research, development, professional training, educational institutions, and international support. In accordance with this variety, it was necessary to approach the proposals from different perspectives, which generated the development of six different proposals and a commitment between the public and private sectors for the participation in projects at an international level towards circularity and sustainability.

One of the main objectives achieved was to promote the generation of research projects in a collaborative way. Likewise, the strengthening of alliances between universities, companies and other institutions, the establishment of cooperation channels and agreements for future cooperation.

Proposals for the development of joint degrees in the field of the EELISA Alliance of Universities stand out, such as the aforementioned Master's and Doctorate programs. Also, of special interest is the proposal led by Istanbul Technical University, in which Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, the Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, the University of Miskolc and the Polibienestar Institute of the University of Valencia are involved; or the possible alliance led by the University POLITEHNICA of

Bucharest, with Universidad Politécnica de Madrid and SURUS, in the field of the circularity of wind farms.

The Circular Models Workshop has promoted research and innovation in the field of circular economy and sustainability, and in the areas of education, governance, climate change, inclusive society, environment and energy. By sharing experiences, knowledge, good practices and viable solutions for a sustainable circular economy, the workshop brought together researchers, academics and business representatives to explore innovative solutions, develop social and sustainability competencies, tackling global challenges.

The results of the workshop make the balance very satisfactory, with six large projects in the development process for presentation in future European calls, with the aim of implementing new circular models.

3 MEETING DEVELOPMENT

As the sessions and presentations continued, different topics arose in which all the participants could intervene by contributing a specialized vision from their field. One of the debates produced addressed the importance of academic and scientific development, using the EELISA network to promote interdisciplinary teaching and the development of green skills with a common framework, but also with a wide interdisciplinary and cultural diversity that promotes the integration of sustainable values towards circularity. In this area, four proposals were proposed to provide solutions to higher and secondary education.

This topic generated different questions and ideas in the implementation of the different programs and diagnoses, where it was discussed how educational programs are designed and how to intervene and implement effective programs towards sustainability and circularity, which are also aligned with solutions to current problems in business and in society, such as eco-design, new materials, green skills, among others.

Another recurring theme during the workshop sessions was governance and its social impact, from which two new initiatives emerged. It was discussed to what extent government institutions are established in relation to the circular economy and its relationship with society, and how society can get involved in sustainable solutions through collaborative governance experiments, recognising the general lack of knowledge in society on issues of sustainability and circular economy. One of the solutions points to the creation of systemic circular solutions for sustainability, also involving citizens through various means, such as circular tourism, AI, blockchain, job creation, program adoption and further replication.

Finally, academics and organizations participating in the Circular Models workshop discussed solutions to climate change, waste management from renewable energy sources, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), implementation of eco-design results, including solutions according to the type of waste, and more sustainable product designs, as well as supporting standards and frameworks for development, research, innovation and partnerships towards circularity.

4 PENDING TASK AND AGREEMENTS

Since the proposals had been previously developed by the authors and subsequently commented on by the workshop leaders, the leaders of each proposal committed to organizing and following up on the work through meetings to continue developing the projects with the workshop leaders interested in each case, and with the objective of its subsequent presentation to the corresponding competitive calls.

No dates were set, but verbal commitments were made for immediate meetings, with estimated dates for calls for proposals between late 2023 and early 2024.

5 FORTHCOMING MEETINGS

The possibility of promoting new plenary meetings with the participation of all attendees was raised.

The EELISA partner universities will be attentive to new EELISA Connect calls from the EELISA innoCORE project, to consider the request for aid to organize new workshops that give continuity to the CIRCULAR MODELS one.

EELISA Connect Workshop - Technology Diplomacy in Engineering Education

Final Report

1. General information

Date: 26-27 October 2023

Place: BME Main Building, room K I 95

Title: Technology Diplomacy in Engineering Education

Program: Please see in the Annex

2. Participants

The total number of participants was 56

The gender ratio was 25:31 (F:M)

The participant group was diverse counting with the presence of multiple EELISA colleagues from FAU, ITU, UPM and BME, students from FAU, ITU and BME and various colleagues from institutions outside of EELISA. Thus the workshop served the purpose of disseminating and promoting EELISA results and activities to other alliances and European higher education institutions.

The workshop welcomed the panel participation of prominent guests such as the ambassador of Türkiye to Hungary and the president of the Hungarian Diplomacy Academy. Among the participants were representatives of the Brazilian Embassy in Hungary.

3. The workshop was directly organized by the EELISA Community TechDiplomacy, with the participation of the community leader along with several members of the community. The discussions served as part of the event series of the community.

4. Participant institutions

- a. EELISA: BME, FAU, UPM, ITU
- b. others: UNIMI, SU, UOC

5. Main outcomes

As part of the TechDiplomay community activities the workshop brought up a continuing discussion on related topics (ethics, education, standardization, interdisciplinarity etc.) that are being further addressed by the community members internally and towards external partners in future events.

Altogether 24 students benefited from the workshop and receive EELISA credentials related to SDG8 and SDG9. The student population was: 5 PhD, 4 MSc, 15 BSc.

Beside the active exchange of information and opinion some of the workshop results are intended to be published in the Journal Information Society (ISSN 1587-8694). This work is under preparation.

The workshop outcomes have already been further discussed in the FAU online course on Introduction to Science and Tech Diplomacy: the new geopolitics of technology by multiple panelists of the workshop but with a different student population.

The new collaborations established at the workshop are intended to lead to further joint work with an ultimate goal of preparing joint projects.

Budapest, 26th of November, 2023

Dr. Balázs Vince Nagy

Annexes:

- Workshop programme
- Photos of the workshop

• • • **SESSION I. - PROGRAM**

• • • **DATE:** 26/10 Thursday

• • • **TIME:** 10:30 a.m. - 01:00 p.m.

• • • **Venue:** BME Main Building, K 1st floor, room 95.
(Pécsi Eszter)

Session: Ethics of engineering, the responsibilities related to technology

Moderator: Mihály Héder (BME)

SPEAKERS

1. **Merve Calimli Akgun**, (ITU)
2. **Ralf Mitschke** (FAU)
3. **Emine Gorgul** (ITU)
4. **Dr. Magda Luthay** (FAU)

**TECHNOLOGY DIPLOMACY IN
ENGINEERING EDUCATION**

EELISA WORKSHOP

SHORT DESCRIPTION

Join us for a transformative workshop session that delves deeply into the exploration of ethics in engineering education. This curated event provides a platform where different engineering universities will meet, fostering discussions on the uniqueness of engineering ethics, challenges in its teaching, and envisioning its future trajectories. Participants will engage in insightful dialogues, sharing experiences and strategies, covering a spectrum from curricular design to the power dynamics in engineering disciplines.

**OCTOBER
26-27
2023**

BUDAPEST / HUNGARY
BME MAIN BUILDING

EELISA
European University
EVENT

• • • **SESSION II. - PROGRAM**

• • • **DATE:** 26/10 Thursday

• • • **TIME:** 02:00 p.m. - 04:30 p.m.

• • • **Venue:** BME Main Building, K 1st floor, room 95.
(Pécsi Eszter)

Session: Technology diplomacy in engineering education

Moderator: Dr. Alper Yurttas (ITU)

SPEAKERS

1. **Gülşen Karanis Ekşioğlu**
The ambassador of the Republic of Türkiye to Hungary
2. **Ralf Mitschke (FAU)**
3. **Ildikó Furka (BME)**
4. **Tamás Lovas (BME)**
5. **Emine Gorgul (ITU)**

SHORT DESCRIPTION

Technology diplomacy, a relatively new concept, has increased the need for interdisciplinary studies, especially between social sciences and engineering departments. This session, which will be attended by distinguished academics from different universities, will focus on the intersection of engineering education and technology diplomacy. In the session, which is planned as an interactive discussion, experiences in different countries will be shared on the axis of how technology diplomacy can be integrated into engineering education.

EELISA
European University
EVENT

**TECHNOLOGY DIPLOMACY IN
ENGINEERING EDUCATION**

EELISA WORKSHOP

**OCTOBER
26-27
2023**

BUDAPEST / HUNGARY
BME MAIN BUILDING

• • • **SESSION III. - PROGRAM**

• • • **DATE:** 27/10 Friday

• • • **TIME:** 09:30 a.m. - 12:00 a.m.

• • • **Venue:** BME Main Building, K 1st floor, room 95.
(Pécsi Eszter)

Session: Standardization – opportunities & challenges

Moderator: Ralf Mitschke (FAU)

SPEAKERS

1. **Gergely László Vigh (BME)**
2. **José Miguel Atienza (UPM)**
3. **Balázs Vince Nagy (BME)**
4. **Corinne Aubert (Sorbonne)**
5. **Mohamed Elsayed (FAU)**

SHORT DESCRIPTION

Session III delves into the world of standardization. As technology diplomacy has brought together diverse academic fields, this session gathers experts from various universities to explore the pivotal nexus between engineering education and the complexities of standardization. Expect an interactive discussion that transcends borders as experiences from around the globe converge to unravel the integration of technology diplomacy into engineering education. Join us in this session where the foundations of standards are questioned, power structures dissected, and the post-colonial dimensions of tech diplomacy explored. Be part of the discourse shaping the future of technology and diplomacy.

EELISA
European University
EVENT

**TECHNOLOGY DIPLOMACY IN
ENGINEERING EDUCATION**

EELISA WORKSHOP

**OCTOBER
26-27
2023**

BUDAPEST / HUNGARY
BME MAIN BUILDING

ONSITE EVENT

- • • **SESSION IV. - PROGRAM**

- • • **DATE:** 27/10 Friday

- • • **TIME:** 01:00 p.m. - 02:00 p.m.

- • • **Venue:** BME Main Building, K 1st floor, room 95.
(Pécsi Eszter)

Session: Political, sociotechnical and cultural aspects of tech diplomacy

Moderator: Claudio Feijoo (UPM)

SPEAKERS

1. **Orsolya Pacsay-Tomassich (HU)**
2. **Kristóf Lehmann (MNB)**
3. **José Miguel Atienza (UPM)**
4. **Bernold Hasenknopf (Sorbonne)**

SHORT DESCRIPTION

Technology diplomacy encompasses a range of practices to gain an advantage within a technological landscape, using overt or covert strategies. It involves international collaborations in technology and innovation to achieve policy goals. Related concepts like data, cyber, digital, and Internet diplomacy handle digital challenges at global and national levels. Nearly all technologies can become diplomatic issues. Current topics include semiconductor industry shifts, renewable energy competition, biotechnology, quantum tech, robotics, 6G communications, cybersecurity, data processing, and AI. Explore these global tech dynamics with us.

EELISA
European University
EVENT

**TECHNOLOGY DIPLOMACY IN
ENGINEERING EDUCATION**

EELISA WORKSHOP

**OCTOBER
26-27
2023**

BUDAPEST / HUNGARY
BME MAIN BUILDING

ONSITE EVENT

Annex - Photos

Sustainable Business Research Week

Workshop on Research on Sustainable Business Models and Value Creation for Stakeholders

4-5 March 2024, Madrid

EELISA
European University

ETS I SISTEMAS
INFORMÁTICOS

FAU
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität
Erlangen-Nürnberg

ITÜ

POLITÉCNICA

UNIVERSIDAD
POLITÉCNICA
DE MADRID

Sant'Anna
Scuola Universitaria Superiore Pisa

REPORT OF THE WORKSHOP

PROF. JAIME GONZALEZ MASIP
UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID

This is an activity funded under EELISA InnoCORE project. EELISA InnoCORE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

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1. Summary description

Workshop name	Sustainable Business Research Week (a.k.a. Sustainable Business Week)
Place	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid – ETSISI (ETSI de Sistemas Informáticos)
Date	03/03/2024 to 05/03/2024
Format	Face-to-face
Project Main Coordinator (PI)	Jaime González Masip (UPM)
Co-coordinators	Nihan Yıldırım (ITÜ) Gianluca Gionfriddo (Sant'Anna) Supriya Singh (FAU)
Description	
<p>The project aims to identify shared lines of work and define spaces for collaboration between researchers from the EELISA alliance dedicated to research on various aspects of business models for sustainability and the creation of value for their stakeholders, understood as the groups affected by or that can influence organisational activity (including the natural environment). The outcome of the project will directly or indirectly affect both the quality of the research of the participants in the workshop through their exchange of knowledge and research experience, as well as the knowledge transfer or teaching activities that could be derived in each member university from the exchange of advice and good practices in the spaces for debate and networking planned for the event. The event will allow the collection of suggestions and feedback from the workshop participants to improve the ongoing research work by participants.</p> <p>In the long term, this workshop aims to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish stable collaborative links between the participating researchers to carry out joint work, leading to high-impact scientific publications. 2. Design a project proposal to be submitted to a European call for research proposals. The workshop will assess possible alternatives among the existing calls. 3. It should have continuity and be repeated periodically within the EELISA alliance and hosted by any participating universities in a rotatory way. In this way, the brand "Sustainable Business Week" would become a reference event for research and dissemination of knowledge on sustainable business models and entrepreneurship at the European EELISA level. 4. Finally, the workshop will offer the opportunity to jointly design training programmes, courses, or curricula for knowledge transfer in entrepreneurship, sustainable business, and social and environmental value creation. More than one of the universities organising the workshop may offer and participate in these programmes, enriching the training offered in the field. These training proposals will also be one of the workshop's outcomes. 	

Relevance of the topic for EELISA partners and communities

The workshop's theme covers three fundamental issues closely linked to EELISA's objectives. The first of these (1) is research into the keys to business models, an essential aspect of any initiative related to entrepreneurship. Business models are conceptual structures that articulate value-creation mechanisms for organisations' stakeholders. On the other hand, (2) research on pivoting towards business models that fit better into the sustainable development paradigm (the so-called business models for sustainability) fosters social and technological innovation and economic and social transformations with a positive impact. Finally, (3) the project seeks to analyse the fundamentals of stakeholder value creation from a sustainability perspective to ensure the creation of lasting and responsible socio-economic initiatives. This is an issue that engineering students need to consider to evolve from an inventor to an innovator with a positive social and environmental impact.

Links with EELISA InnoCORE SRAs

The objectives of this workshop align with the EELISA Strategic Research Areas (SRAs) as follows:

- **Social Sciences and Humanities:** Social and technological innovation, economic and social transformations and governance.
Business models for sustainability are a vital part of socio-economic organisation, conditioning human transactions, social contracts and the impact on people and the environment.
- **Culture, creativity, and inclusive society:** The ethical and philosophical aspects of technology, social innovation and inclusion, and the politics of science and technology.
Designing business models for sustainability naturally implies the existence of ethical and political constraints, which regulate how social impacts are generated in the form of change.
- **Smart industry and space technologies:** Circular economy and manufacturing models.
Generating value in business models requires production processes immersed in more sustainable value-creation chains, highlighting circular economies as a reference scheme.

The “Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-2027 Analysis” highlights several societal priorities and challenges for the future, including Circular Economy and Societal Issues. Among the latter are *Research to strengthen democratic societies*, *Research to address ethical concerns and democratic risks in an IT-driven society* and *Solutions to increase the resilience of society*. This workshop fits into this strategic plan and is intended to actively participate by carrying out one or more research projects within this framework.

2. List of participants

Table 1. List of attendees

NAME	SURNAME	INSTITUTION / AFFILIATION	03/07/2023	04/07/2023	05/07/2023
Esben Rahbek Gjerdrum	Pedersen	Copenhagen Business School*	YES	YES	YES
Francisco	Layrisse	FAU	YES	YES	YES
Klemens	Hering	FAU	YES	YES	YES
Vittorio	Cerulli	FAU	YES	YES	YES
Supriya	Singh	FAU	YES	YES	YES
Elif	Karaosmanoğlu	ITÜ	YES	YES	YES
Sukru Alper	Yurttas	ITÜ	YES	YES	YES
Nihan	Yildirim	ITÜ	YES	YES	YES
Deniz	Tuncalp	ITÜ	YES	YES	YES
Gianluca	Gionfriddo	Sant'Anna	NO	YES	YES
Silvia	Iossa	Sant'Anna	NO	YES	YES
Martina	Tafuro	Sant'Anna	NO	YES	YES
Valentina	Cucino	Sant'Anna	NO	YES	YES
Jesús	Salgado	UPM	NO	YES	YES
Jaime	González Masip	UPM	YES	YES	YES
Rafael	Miñano Rubio	UPM	NO	YES	YES
Giannicola	Scarpa	UPM	NO	NO	YES
Celia	Fernández Aller	UPM	NO	YES	YES
Pilar Cristina	Izquierdo Gracia	UPM	YES	NO	NO
TOTAL ATTENDANTS			11	17	18

* Prof. Esben R.G. Pedersen is not a member of the EELISA Alliance. He was invited to the workshop to give a keynote presentation on Tuesday, March 5, and participated in the rest of the workshop activities.

Table 2. Gender balance of participants (in % of total)

Criteria	Female	Male	Declared as preferring not to say
All participants	44,44%	50,00%	5,56%
International visiting participants	41,67%	58,33%	8,33%

3. Workshop agenda

Agenda Summary

Sunday 3 rd March	
17:30h	Welcome Activity Cultural visit to the city centre. Traditional snack. Place: Historical centre of Madrid.
21:00h	End of the session.

Monday 4 th March	
09:15h	Pick-up and transport to campus
10:00h	Getting to know the School Welcome from the School Director. Place: ETSISI school facilities.
11:00h	Coffee Break Place: ETSISI Board Room
11:30h	Matching and learning Presentation of participants' research and sharing of best practices. Place: ETSISI Classroom 4303
14:00h	Lunch Place: ETSISI Board Room
15:00h	Framing the research Identify future lines of research. Place: ETSISI Classroom 4303
18:00h	End of the session.

Tuesday 5 th March	
09:15h	Pick-up and transport to campus
10:00h	Matching and learning Presentation of participants' research and exchange of best practices. Place: ETSISI Classroom 4303
11:00h	Coffee Break Place: ETSISI Board Room
11:30h	Keynote Presentations Place: ETSISI Grade Room <u>Giannicola Scarpa</u> (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid) <i>"Quantum Computing to foster sustainability: the case of Decision Theory."</i> <u>Esben Pedersen</u> (Copenhagen Business School) <i>"Stakeholders and Sustainability – Past Experiences and Future Perspectives"</i>

14:00h	Lunch Place: ETSISI Board Room
15:00h	Framing the research Define plans for collaboration and joint research. Place: ETSISI Classroom 4303
18:00h	End of the session.
21:00h	Social dinner and Networking Dinner for workshop participants. Place: Madrid city centre.

Detailed agenda

Sunday 3rd March

Welcome Activity (17:30h)

Jaime González Masip called all the workshop participants who were already in Madrid on Sunday at 17:30h at Plaza de Oriente (Oriente Square) to have a first meeting and make a cultural tour of the centre of Madrid. The objective was to create a first activity to bring the participants closer to the city's environment and history. Also, we were looking for a first approach between the workshop participants (team building). Many workshop participants met for the first time at this activity.

The activity was organized by Prof. Pilar Cristina Izquierdo Gracia (UPM) and carried out by Mariano Bas Uribe, who acted as a cultural guide for the visit. At the end of the visit, the group enjoyed a typical Madrid snack to continue bonding among the participants.

Cultural activity in the centre of Madrid.

Monday 4th March

Getting to know the School (10:00h)

The collective transport picked up the group of participants from their hotel in the centre of Madrid at 9:15h, arriving at ETSISI at 10:00h. First, the director of the School, Prof. Agustín Yagüe Panadero, officially welcomed the group of participants to the workshop. After a brief meeting, the school facilities were visited to show the participants the resources and facilities of the school, as well as to guide them in case they needed to move around the campus individually. The visit ended with a 30-minute coffee break.

The Director of ETSISI, Prof. Agustín Yagüe Panadero, the Project PI, Prof. Jaime González Masip, and the international workshop participants.

Matching and learning (11:30h)

Starting with the host, Prof. Jaime González Masip, each participant of the workshop presented to the rest of the participants their current lines of research and other academic initiatives related to the research in which they are involved. The aim was to provide context to identify possible avenues for collaboration and to receive recommendations from the other participants. This activity will continue the following day at 10:00h.

Martina Tafuro (Sant'Anna) is doing his presentation.

Framing the research (15:00h)

This activity was led by Jesus Salgado (UPM) and consisted of identifying future lines of research that met the following three conditions: firstly, they should be of academic interest; secondly, they should be of social utility; and lastly, they should be motivating for the academics participating in the workshop. The activity aims to identify lines of research in which the participants could collaborate at the end of the workshop. This activity will continue the following day at the same time.

Participants working in groups.

Tuesday 5th March

Matching and learning (10:00h)

The collective transport picked the participants up from their hotel in the centre of Madrid at 9:15 a.m., arriving at ETSISI at 10:00 a.m.

This activity follows the one held the day before at 11:30h. Each workshop participant presented to the rest of the participants their current lines of research and other academic initiatives

related to the research in which they are involved. The aim was to provide context to identify possible avenues for collaboration and to receive recommendations from the other participants.

Keynote Presentations (11:30h)

Experts in their respective topics gave two keynote presentations related to the workshop's theme. These two presentations were:

- By Giannicola Scarpa (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid): *"Quantum Computing to foster sustainability: the case of Decision Theory."*
- By Esben Pedersen (Copenhagen Business School): *"Stakeholders and Sustainability – Past Experiences and Future Perspectives"*

The session was offered as an activity within the UPM PhD programme. In addition to the workshop participants, 10 UPM PhD students attended the activity.

Professors Scarpa (left) and Pedersen (right) during their keynote presentations.

Framing the research (15:00h)

This activity follows the one held the day before at 15:00h.

In the first half, this activity was led by Jesus Salgado (UPM) and consisted of identifying future lines of research that met the following three conditions: firstly, they should be of academic interest; secondly, they should be of social utility; and lastly, they should be motivating for the academics participating in the workshop. The activity aims to identify lines of research in which the participants could collaborate at the end of the workshop.

In the second half, the activity is led by Prof. Jaime González Masip. The objective is to identify specific lines of research collaboration between the workshop participants. The lines of collaboration identified are:

4. Principal Objectives Achieved

The objectives achieved in the event can be grouped into three main sets listed below. Firstly, participants had the opportunity to get to know each other's lines of work and research. It should be noted that, with a few exceptions, the participants did not know each other before the workshop. In this sense, peer-to-peer contacts were made, with plans for collaboration following the affinity criterion in lines of work.

Secondly, stable communication channels and platforms were established for coordination among the participants to facilitate collaboration on initiatives of group interest. Table 3 compiles a list of lines of collaboration grouped by type of action that the participants identified as being of common interest. For its realisation, a timetable was defined to monitor the progress of the tasks. The group committed to organizing and following up on the work through meetings to continue developing the projects with the workshop leaders interested in each case. Some dates were set for the first online meetings, and some verbal commitments were made for immediate meetings. In addition, the EELISA partner universities participating in the workshop will be attentive to new EELISA Connect calls of the EELISA innoCORE project to consider applying for grants to organise new workshops that give continuity to the Sustainable Business Research Week workshop.

Table 3. Collaboration lines

GROUP	Initiative or Program	Collective actuation
Existing conferences or initiatives	EURAM Conference (Florence, 2025)	Propose a specific track or session.
	New Business Models Conference 2025	Propose a specific track or session.
	R&D Management Conference (Rome, 2025)	Propose a specific track or session.
	EGOS conference (Athens, 2025)	Propose a specific track or session.
	Academy of Management (2025, Copenhagen)	Participate in a specific track or session.
	Society for Business Ethics Conference (Chicago, 2024)	Participate in a specific track or session (for the next year).
	European Marketing Academy (EMAC) Annual Conference (Madrid, 2025)	Propose special sessions or a Symposium (+Journal Special Issue).
Funding	European Funding (HORIZON/Erasmus +)	Information gathering and sharing.
	Workshop not European funding (Research + Methodologies)	Information gathering and sharing.
Research and publish	Book on the topic covered in the workshop	Publication of a book by compilation of chapters with the participation of all workshop attendees.

Finally, the workshop achieved the objective of bringing the participants together. The social agenda in the event and the networking activities generated proximity links to facilitate future collaboration, especially in tasks requiring recurrent collaborations or face-to-face meetings. Madrid's cultural and leisure offer facilitated the development of this aspect of the workshop and the achievement of the objective.

Participants at the closing of the workshop at ETSISI

5. Final assessment

The overall assessment of the workshop is positive. The feedback received from the participants was favourable, accompanied by intense activity, public recognition, and satisfaction with the event and its organisation on social networks. The proposed objectives have been achieved in the short term. However, the proposed schedule of tasks has been slightly delayed due to the administrative management of the workshop itself.

There was a total consensus about research activities to develop several of them and to look for calls for projects that support the collaboration of the partners. As for teaching or dissemination activities, it was shown that it is more difficult to achieve consensus due to, on the one hand, the different professional stages of each of the participants and, on the other hand, the different teaching load of each participant and the work assignment policies of their institutions. Therefore, joint work seems to mainly focus on developing research activity.

In the coming weeks, it is expected to be able to continue with the planned tasks. A series of network collaborations between the participants is also foreseeable. The possibility of repeating the workshop in future InnoCORE meetings is being considered. However, whether it will be held in Madrid or other participating EELISA partner venues has not yet been decided.